

D9.9 Compilation of our contributions towards international technical, operational and ethical standards for use of AI in health imaging

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Abbreviations

ABR	Abbreviation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIA	Artificial Intelligence Act
AIMS	Artificial Intelligence Management System
API	Application Programming Interface
CDM	Common Data Model
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CENELEC	(Comité Européen de Normalisation Électrotechnique; European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization)
CLAIM	Checklist for Artificial Intelligence in Medical
CLEAR	CheckList for EvaluAtion of Radiomics research (CLEAR)
CONSORT	Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials
DICOM	Digital Imaging and Communication In Medicine
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EHDS-R:	European Health Data Space Regulation
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity
ESR	European Society of Radiology
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FDA	U.S. Food and Drug Administration
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation.

GD	Guideline
H2020	Horizon 2020
HDABs	Health Data Access Bodies
HER	Electronic Health Record
HIPAA	Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act
HIS	Health Information Systems
HL7	Health Level Seven
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
ISO	International Standards Organization
JTC	Joint Technical Committee
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
PACS	Picture Archiving and Communication Systems
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
SME	Medium-Sized Enterprises
SPIRIT	Standard Protocol Items: Recommendations for Interventional Trials
SQuaRE	Systems and software Quality Requirements and Evaluation
STARD	Standards for the Reporting of Diagnostic Accuracy Studies
TRIPOD	Transparent Reporting of a multivariable prediction model for Individual Prognosis or Diagnosis
US	United States
XAI	Explainable Artificial Intelligence

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1 Introduction

1.1 Scope of the document

The main objective of this document is to provide an in-depth review of the contributions made by the scientific community and the CHAIMELEON project to the promotion of Artificial Intelligence (AI) standards in the particular field of medical imaging. The main objective of this document is to provide an in-depth review of the contributions made by the scientific community and the CHAIMELEON project to the promotion of Artificial Intelligence (AI) standards in the field of medical imaging.

AI is one of the fields that has seen more rapid developments in recent years, although it can be said that it has formally existed since the decade of the 1950s. At present, it is a field that is attracting considerable investment, interest and commitment from the private sector, industry and public administrations, among many others. With the potential benefits of this technology come certain challenges, not only for industry and government, but for society as a whole.

It has become clear to political authorities, regulators, experts and the scientific and technological community that standardisation and regulation by official bodies should be implemented and followed to guarantee human rights and fundamental values and facilitate the framework for developing technologies and related businesses. The recent publication of the European Artificial Intelligence Act (EU AIA)¹ demonstrates the importance of technical and operational standards to ensure high impact and ethical development of AI systems. It could be argued that all these aspects to be guaranteed become even more critical in cases such as those considered by the EU AIA as high-risk AI systems, such as many AI health applications. To conceive, create, operate, update and maintain data frameworks related to healthcare, private companies, research institutions and public authorities need to agree on the standards and rules to be followed to comply with specific international and national laws, but also to respect the rights of patients and users, while guaranteeing full technical capabilities to achieve their objectives.

The scientific and technical community is working to translate the rapid progress in the field of AI systems into its practical application in various use cases in the healthcare ecosystem, such as the field of medical imaging.

¹ European Commission. (2021). Proposal for a Regulation laying down harmonized rules on Artificial Intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act). Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52021PC0206>

The present report therefore aims to provide a thorough summary of the state of AI in medical imaging and how the development of the CHAIMELEON project has contributed to this particular field. To achieve this goal, the report first focuses on the field of AI, providing a context of the relevant entities, bodies and standardisation initiatives, as well as important projects or initiatives, etc.

Once the reader has a clearer vision of the AI standardisation ecosystem and its current situation at the time of publication of this report, an in-depth analysis of scientific publications on AI in healthcare and medical imaging is carried out. This analysis is intended to provide a common vision for the scientific community, AI researchers, and relevant public and private organisations working on the development of AI systems for medical imaging.

The analysis of the scientific bibliography ended with a sandbox of recommended guidelines to ensure the development of medical imaging AI systems. The sandbox will be complemented with relevant research on new AI models, technologies to ensure their implementation, data models and all the knowledge used and generated during the execution of the CHAIMELEON project.

2 General context

The CHAIMELEON project has developed a data repository of images and clinical data for the most prevalent cancers in Europe: lung, breast, prostate, and colorectal. The secure sharing and reuse of anonymised imaging and clinical data is a key feature of the infrastructure, as the primary purpose of the project is to enable AI developers to create, train, or improve tools and solutions for cancer management.²

Health imaging-based AI approaches can be useful tools for improving cancer management and treatments. However, many challenges need to be addressed, such as ensuring sufficient quantity, quality, and representativeness of data, or strict compliance with ethics and data protection regulations.

CHAIMELEON is a large-scale interoperable repository at EU level. It has established a distributed infrastructure, built on existing initiatives, and implemented online processing pipelines to improve the integrity and interpretability of its data. This framework then aims to

² <https://chaimoleon.eu/>

contribute to the development of AI solutions that can help improve diagnosis, treatment, or follow-up, and ultimately support clinicians in their decision-making processes. As an ambitious undertaking in the field, the project is committed to actively contributing to the current technical, operational and ethical standards in the discipline of health imaging.

From the outset of the project, the consortium decided to conduct studies to benchmark best practices from relevant international bodies, research organisations and international projects in the field of AI standards and medical imaging. A key objective of CHAIMELEON is to develop credible standards for the implementation of AI systems in health imaging. Our recommendations on technical and operational standards should have a direct impact on the development of medical imaging AI systems, which are classified as high-risk in the EU AIA. Therefore, we expect a significant contribution to innovation, economic growth and a positive impact on patient's lives and healthcare organisations' services.

The challenge ahead required thorough work with two distinct steps. The first part is a benchmarking and literature review to identify the most relevant work and documentation related to the implementation of standards in AI and medical imaging. The second part of the study involves an in-depth discussion to define a set of guidelines for the implementation of technical and operational standards in the field of AI applied to medical imaging. Members of the CHAIMELEON community will share their knowledge and experience to propose specific inputs for the implementation of reliable and value-added AI systems. This document summarises our studies in two parts (benchmarking and final recommendations).

2.1 Sources of Information related with the development of AI standards in health.

As such, we have undertaken a comprehensive review of the existing literature to encapsulate the primary dimensions associated with the development of AI-based solutions. We have explored various sources of information to develop a comprehensive vision for the development of technical and operational standards in the field of medical imaging AI systems. The study will consider four sources of information:

1. **Legal Framework for AI systems development:** Conducting a contextual analysis of the current regulatory framework for the development of AI systems and comparing policies across countries. Although we will gather information from legal initiatives around the world, we will focus our study on Europe, with a particular emphasis on the European Artificial Intelligence Act.

2. **Technical committees on Standardization for AI:** The creation of new technical standards is a high-stakes activity, especially when the technology is characterised by strong network effects or system competition. This is the case with artificial intelligence in healthcare. AI is now at the forefront of discussions in international, European and national technical committees. They have set up working groups and subcommittees to address the challenging implementation of AI systems and the definition of standards to ensure the appropriate development of AI systems in different economic sectors. We have reviewed the most active and relevant ones to provide the basis for new proposals for standards.
3. **Public or Private Initiatives fostering AI development:** This source will incorporate information from three different levels. Firstly, will try to identify which **initiatives at the national level** are guiding the development of artificial intelligence systems, particularly in the eHealth sector. Understand their perspective, commitment and impact. Secondly, we will work on the identification of **consortia dedicated to AI:** Identify well-established consortia (especially at EU level) with a deep understanding of the AI landscape. Finally, we will analyse **relevant projects for medical imaging** enhanced with AI and how they are approaching the development of technical and operational standards. Given the large number of projects in this area, we will focus on those funded by the European Union.
4. **Literature Review on AI standards applied to Medical Imaging:** An exhaustive literature review will be conducted to summarise the main aspects that emerge across different authors and institutions.

Numerous European Union member states, leading technology companies and international associations have published guidelines that address the key concerns and opportunities associated with AI. We believe that the following documents encapsulate the most relevant and valuable dimensions and concepts impacting the development of AI solutions for medical imaging.

3 Legal Framework for AI development

3.1 An overall vision of Legal frameworks for AI development

Currently, the main legal framework for the development of AI models is established by national data protection regulations and laws.³ Until the application of the AI law, the development of

³ <https://legalnodes.com/article/global-ai-regulations-tracker>

this technology has been based, from a legal point of view, on the GDPR, on sectoral national laws - for example when special categories of data are involved - or on laws relating to intellectual property, trade secrets or civil liability. These regulations can vary significantly in scope. In general, while these laws guide the collection, processing and use of data, there is a need for specific legislation that encompasses the inherent characteristics of AI solutions.

In December 2023, as a pioneer, the EU adopted the EU AIA to harmonise all AI regulations developed. More information on the impact of the EU AIA, and in particular on the development of AI systems for medical imaging, which the EU AIA considers to be high-risk systems, is provided in section 3 of this document.

In addition to the EU AIA, other efforts are underway and it is expected that other countries, such as Canada, Brazil and India, will begin to enact their own specific laws to regulate artificial intelligence. However, other countries, including the UK and Switzerland, have opted not to introduce these specific laws, preferring instead to incorporate AI development into a broader regulatory framework.

The United States has adopted a different strategy, dealing with each situation on a case-by-case basis.

3.2 The role of the United States

The legal framework for the development of artificial intelligence in the United States and the EU is diverse. And so is the philosophical approach. This is the case both in terms of data protection and in the field of AI.

There is no federal data protection law. Only states such as California have data protection laws and authorities. The legislation is sectoral. The Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) scope includes privacy matters. This is a significant regulation in the United States that aims to protect the privacy and security of individuals' health information. Here is a summary of its main characteristics, challenges, and threats:

This rule establishes national standards to protect individuals' medical records and other personal health information. It applies to health plans, healthcare clearinghouses, and healthcare providers that conduct certain healthcare transactions electronically. In addition, the law sets standards for the protection of electronic protected health information (ePHI) that is created, received, used, or maintained by a covered entity. It requires appropriate administrative, physical, and technical safeguards to ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and

security of ePHI.⁴ And requires covered entities and their business associates to provide notification following a breach of unsecured protected health information.

The HIPAA Privacy Rule establishes the conditions under which protected health information (PHI) may be used or disclosed by covered entities for research purposes. Research is defined as a systematic investigation designed to develop or contribute to generalizable knowledge.⁵

1. Authorization: Generally, the use and disclosure of PHI for research purposes require an authorization from the research subject unless an exception applies.
2. De-Identification: A covered entity may use or disclose de-identified health information for research without regard to the Privacy Rule's provisions.
3. Institutional Review Board (IRB) or Privacy Board Approval: To use or disclose PHI without authorization, a covered entity must obtain documented approval from an IRB or Privacy Board. This approval may include an alteration or waiver of the research participants' authorization.
4. Limited Data Set: Researchers may use a limited data set, which excludes certain direct identifiers, for research purposes. A data use agreement must be in place to ensure the protection of the data.
5. Accounting of Disclosures: Covered entities must provide an accounting of disclosures of PHI for research purposes upon request by the individual.

In the area of AI, the Executive Order announced on January 14, 2025 aims to solidify the United States' leadership in artificial intelligence infrastructure. The order emphasizes the importance of AI as a defining technology of our era, with significant implications for national security, economic competitiveness, and technological innovation.⁶

The order also highlights the necessity of building AI infrastructure within the United States. The policy of the United States to develop and operate AI infrastructure domestically, adheres to five guiding principles:

- Advancing national security and leadership in AI.
- Ensuring the development of AI infrastructure benefits workers and communities.
- Promoting a competitive and open technology ecosystem.

⁴ <https://www.hhs.gov/sites/default/files/ocr/privacy/hipaa/administrative/securityrule/riskassessment.pdf>

⁵ <https://www.hhs.gov/hipaa/for-professionals/special-topics/research/index.html>

⁶ <https://bidenwhitehouse.archives.gov/briefing-room/presidential-actions/2025/01/14/executive-order-on-advancing-united-states-leadership-in-artificial-intelligence-infrastructure/>

- Maintaining low consumer electricity prices.
- Advancing leadership in clean energy technologies.

A second Executive Order announced on January 23rd, 2025, aimed to enhance America's leadership in artificial intelligence (AI).⁷ The new executive order focuses on several key areas:

1. Removing Barriers to AI Innovation:
2. Enhancing America's AI Leadership
3. Continuing Prioritization of AI

3.3 The role of the European Union

As a key political actor, the European Union plays an important role in the regulation of AI activities, both through direct strong initiatives and legislation in EU markets, and by bringing together AI expertise in some of the most relevant standardisation organisations. Notably, significant investments have been made through programs like Horizon Europe and Digital Europe, with over €1 billion annually dedicated to AI research and development.

Figure 1: Chronology of relevant regulatory progress for the development and adoption of AI in Europe.

⁷ <https://www.whitehouse.gov/fact-sheets/2025/01/fact-sheet-president-donald-j-trump-takes-action-to-enhance-americas-ai-leadership/>

These efforts are designed to position the EU as a global leader in AI, driving economic growth, enhancing competitiveness, and ensuring that AI technologies benefit society as a whole. In a nutshell, the European Union has played a pivotal role in promoting artificial intelligence (AI) through a comprehensive strategy focused on excellence and trust. Below is a summary of some of the milestones in EU policy towards AI:

- **Tallinn Digital Summit:** Due to the growing importance of digital technologies in the overall economy and society, the EU hosted the Tallinn Digital Summit in September 2017. The summit brought together EU leaders, policymakers and stakeholders to discuss key issues related to digital transformation, innovation and the digital single market. Several topics were carefully considered and discussed, to establish further plans for digital innovation and ensure that Europe does not lose its pace in the digital technology era. Some of the main topics discussed were cybersecurity, digital skills, innovation or data economy.

During these discussions, the topic of initiatives to harmonise digital regulations and a roadmap to achieve progress towards this goal in the coming years emerged. Initiatives such as the **European AI Alliance**, launched in June 2018, are a direct result of the Tallinn Digital Summit agenda, and were created to facilitate an open dialogue between AI experts, leading representatives of the AI community and relevant stakeholders. The Tallinn Digital Agenda is seen by many experts as a starting point for making further progress in the regulation of artificial intelligence.

- **EU White Paper on AI:** This document was published in February 2020. The paper identifies and reaffirms the strong need for the EU to be at the forefront of technological leadership. The European Commission recognises the importance of a common European approach to AI, the promotion of AI to enable progress in society and the economy, and the need to advance the AI regulatory and policy framework. The document provides a careful analysis of the challenges that this framework should address, such as the rapid evolution of technologies. Healthcare is mentioned several times in the document as a sector where AI applications could pose significant risks due to its specific context.
- **EU Digital Decade policy program** This document defines objectives to reach by the end of the decade regarding a series of pre-defined IT & digital targets, such as the digitalization of public services, infrastructure security, business digital transformation, or IT skills. The values and commitments of the EU-level trajectories established on all

those fields should be taken into account and be aligned with the EU AIA and complain with it when the AI domain is addressed.

3.3.1 The Legal basis for processing electronic health data. European Health Data Space Landscape Overview

The EHDS is an initiative by the European Union (EU) aimed at creating a secure and standardized environment for the exchange of health data across EU member states. This framework is intended to facilitate the free flow of health data within the EU for both individual care and research purposes while respecting individuals' privacy rights.⁸

The European Health Data Space (EHDS) represents a foundational element of the European Health Union, and it signifies the EU's first specialized data space as part of its European strategy for data. In the spring of 2024, the European Parliament and the Council reached a political consensus on the European Health Data Space Regulation proposal from the European Commission. Finally, a final version was published by the European Parliament and is expected to be published in the European Official Journal in March⁹ 2025.

The EHDS aims to:

- Empower individuals by giving them control over their health data and facilitating data exchange across the EU to improve healthcare delivery (primary use of data).
- Create a unified market for electronic health records, allowing for standardized access and usage.
- Establish a secure, consistent framework for reusing health data for research, innovation, policy development, and regulatory functions (secondary use of data).
- By enabling secure data exchange and reuse, the EHDS will help the EU maximize the benefits of health data for patients, researchers, innovators, and regulators.

Trust is critical for the EHDS's success, offering a secure environment for accessing and processing health data, while leveraging frameworks such as:

- General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)
- Data Governance Act

⁸ European Commission. (2022). European Health Data Space (EHDS): Shaping Europe's digital future. Retrieved from <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/european-health-data-space> .

⁹ See <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2025/01/21/european-health-data-space-council-adopts-new-regulation-improving-cross-border-access-to-eu-health-data/>

- Data Act
- Cybersecurity (NIS 2)

This legal framework confers relevant opportunities for the development of platforms, such as the Cancer Image EU (EUCAIM) that could ensure regulatory compliance framework related to the development of research, products or medical devices, and particularly those based on AI or integrating embedded AI resources. The landscape of laws integrates:

- Artificial Intelligence Act.
- Medical Diagnostic Device Regulation.
- In Vitro Medical Device Regulation.
- Health Technology Assessment Directive.

These horizontal laws provide general rules for the health sector, while the EHDS-R adds sector-specific regulations given the sensitive nature of health data.

The EHDS-R establishes a comprehensive legal framework to facilitate access to and secondary use of electronic health data in the European Union. The EHDS-RR operates as a *lex specialis* and offers legitimation for the processing of electronic health data and transfers the administrative function of providing governance, managing the granting of access permissions and supporting the operation of the system to the Health Data Access Bodies (HDABs). At the European level, cross-border data processing will be coordinated by HealthData@EU with the support of authorised participants and cross-border registries or databases of electronic health data for secondary use where appropriate. The EHDS-R is integrated with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in the health sector. It defines a set of secondary uses that are combined with the legal bases of the GDPR for processing health data for secondary purposes, while limiting the ability of Member States to set additional conditions to the processing.

Secondary use of health data is crucial to facilitate scientific research, innovation and public policy development in health. It allows for harnessing the value of health data beyond their primary healthcare use, contributing to improving the quality and efficiency of healthcare systems. To achieve this aim, very specific strategies are deployed.

- A commitment to anonymisation and pseudonymisation as key techniques to protect the privacy of individuals.

Anonymisation allows the use of data without personal data protection restrictions, while pseudonymisation facilitates the processing of data while maintaining adequate safeguards aligned with article 89 GDPR aims to protect the patient's rights.

- Secure Data Spaces (SPEs).

Safe data spaces are a crucial component of the EHDS, designed to enable secondary use of health data in a secure and data protection-compliant manner, thus facilitating health research and innovation. The minimum regulation of Article 73 of the EHDS-R should be combined with the high standards of some national rules, policies defined by data protection authorities (DPAs) or European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA), and existing or future certifiable standards.

- Data cataloguing, quality and usability.

The EHDS-R establishes the need to create catalogues of electronic health data available for secondary use that must include information on the available datasets, their origin, and nature and access conditions. HDABs are responsible for maintaining these catalogues at the national level, with integration at the European level. Data holders must ensure that the shared datasets meet established quality standards including accuracy, completeness, consistency and up-to-datedness of the data. The EHDS-R foresees the development of standards and guidelines to assess and improve the quality of health data. It stresses the importance of data being useful and relevant for their intended purpose. The usefulness of data relates to their ability to generate knowledge, improve health care and contribute to scientific progress, and the need to balance the usefulness of data with the protection of privacy and the rights of individuals is emphasised. The EHDS-R recognises the critical importance of the cataloguing, quality and usability of health data to facilitate and promote their effective secondary use, setting out a framework for improving these aspects in the context of the EHDS.

- Interoperability of information systems and their information content.

The EHDS-R also implies a commitment to interoperability. In its technical dimension, it should facilitate the cross-border processing of data and the creation of flexible processing models based on federated data processing and, in the long term, on the interaction between different

data spaces. The semantic dimension of interoperability is also of major importance, enabling the processes of cataloguing, quality and usability.

- A common ethical and legal approach.

The EHDS-R, except for some specific authorisations to national legislation, creates a common regulatory scenario that implies a homogeneous ethical and legal framework to be assumed and applied by all actors concerned by the EHDS-RR.

- A nuclear purpose: the digital transformation of the EU for the benefit of mankind.

The comprehensive regulatory package in this area (DGA, Data ACT, AI ACT, EHDS-R) is aimed at digital transformation and European competitiveness in research, innovation, business entrepreneurship and improving the capacities of the public sector in the human being's benefit, based on the principles of respect for fundamental rights and guaranteeing the rule of law and democracy.

3.3.2 The Artificial Intelligence Act

This document was finally adopted by the European Parliament in March 2024. It encompasses the EU legal framework and aims to provide developers, users, SMEs and the AI community at large with a clear legal guideline of requirements and obligations, as well as a governance structure at the European and national level. The European Union's Artificial Intelligence Act (EU AIA) aims to establish a comprehensive regulatory framework for AI, ensuring the development and deployment of safe, trustworthy AI systems across the EU. The EU AIA classifies AI systems based on risk levels: unacceptable, high, limited, and minimal risk¹.

Its primary goal is to protect fundamental rights and safety while fostering innovation and investment in AI technologies. The EU AIA introduces stringent requirements for high-risk AI systems, including robust data governance, transparency, and human oversight. It also prohibits certain AI practices, such as social scoring and real-time biometric identification in public spaces¹.

By setting clear standards, the EU AIA is expected to boost consumer trust in AI, stimulate economic growth, and position the EU as a leader in AI innovation. It also aims to create a balanced environment where innovation can thrive while ensuring ethical and safe AI deployment. The 4-level risk regulatory approach is designed to encourage responsible AI development, potentially leading to significant advancements in various sectors, including healthcare, finance, and public services. In section 3 of this document there is more information

about the impact of the EU AIA and the need of operational standards to develop medical imaging AI systems in compliance with the EU AIA requirements for category 3, high risk systems.

Figure 2: EU AIA 4- level of Risk based approach. Image under Creative Commons license.

The regulation aims to improve the functioning of the internal market by laying down a uniform legal framework for the development, placing on the market, putting into service, and use of AI systems in the Union. The regulation ensures the free movement of AI-based goods and services across Member States, preventing restrictions unless explicitly authorized by the regulation. It promotes the uptake of human-centric and trustworthy AI while ensuring a high level of protection of health, safety, fundamental rights, democracy, the rule of law, and environmental protection.

The AI Act is based on the following principles, values and purposes:

1. Guarantee of Fundamental Rights (Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment)

The AI regulation establishes the need to conduct impact assessments on fundamental rights. These assessments are essential to ensure that AI systems respect and protect individuals' fundamental rights. Potential risks that AI systems may pose to fundamental rights, such as privacy, non-discrimination, and freedom of expression, must be identified and mitigated.

2. Risk Analysis for Democracy

The AI regulation also addresses the risks that AI systems may pose to democracy. This includes evaluating how AI systems can influence democratic processes, such as elections and referendums. Safeguards must be implemented to prevent AI systems from being used to manipulate public opinion or interfere with democratic processes.

3. Prevention of Risks to Health and Integrity of Individuals

The AI regulation includes measures to prevent risks to the health and integrity of individuals. This involves evaluating the potential negative impacts that AI systems may have on the physical and mental health of individuals. Controls and safeguards must be implemented to ensure that AI systems do not cause harm to individuals, whether through automated decisions, recommendations, or any other form of interaction.

4. Prohibited Practices

The AI regulation prohibits certain practices that are considered unacceptable due to the significant risks they pose. These practices include:

- Subliminal and Manipulative Techniques: Prohibited if they distort behaviour and cause significant harm.
- Exploitation of Vulnerabilities: Prohibited if it causes significant harm.
- Social Scoring Systems: Prohibited if they lead to unjustified unfavourable treatment.
- Criminal Risk Assessment: Prohibited if based solely on profiling or personal characteristics aimed at prediction.
- Facial Recognition: Prohibited in certain contexts, such as scraping and emotional inference.
- Biometric Categorization: Prohibited in special categories of data.
- Real-Time Biometric Identification Surveillance: Prohibited in certain contexts.

5. Conditions for the development of High-Risk AI Systems:

Article 6 outlines the classification of high-risk AI systems. It specifies that AI systems intended for use in critical infrastructure, education, employment, essential services, law enforcement, migration management, and administration of justice are considered high-risk. In addition, high-risk AI systems are those intended to be used as safety components of products within the scope of Union harmonization legislation, or the AI system itself is one of those products.

AI systems that are components of medical devices (Medical Devices Regulation (EU) 2017/745) or in vitro diagnostic devices (Vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices Regulation (EU) 2017/746) are subject to these regulations. These regulations ensure that AI systems used in medical devices meet safety and performance requirements. The EU AIA lists specific high-risk AI systems related to health and healthcare, including:

- AI systems for biometric identification and categorization.
- AI systems for managing critical infrastructure in healthcare.
- AI systems for assessing eligibility for health insurance and benefits.

These systems must comply with stringent requirements to ensure they do not pose significant risks to health, safety, or fundamental rights. In the health sector, AI systems used for medical devices, patient management, and diagnostics are classified as high-risk. These systems must undergo third-party conformity assessment before being placed on the market or put into service.

High-risk AI systems must comply with ethical design principles and ensure data protection and privacy. Chapter III of the EU AIA details the requirements for high-risk AI systems, including risk management, data governance, technical documentation, record-keeping, transparency, human oversight, accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity. It mandates that high-risk AI systems must have a risk management system in place to identify, assess, and mitigate risks throughout the lifecycle of the AI system.

The regulation aims to improve the functioning of the internal market by laying down a uniform legal framework for the development, placing on the market, putting into service, and use of AI systems in the Union. The regulation ensures the free movement of AI-based goods and services across Member States, preventing restrictions unless explicitly authorized by the regulation. It promotes the uptake of human-centric and trustworthy AI while ensuring a high level of protection of health, safety, fundamental rights, democracy, the rule of law, and environmental protection.

3.4 Relevant entities and bodies for AI standardization

Several organizations and entities contribute to the standardization efforts within the realm of AI. Some of these entities are also devoted to many other fields apart from AI, but they have specific technical boards or committees that are dedicated to developing, advocating, and promoting standards that ensure the reliability, integrity, and interoperability in the use of AI technologies.

Europe is particularly active in this area. The European Commission issued standardisation requests to the European Standardisation Organisations (ESOs) i.e. CEN, CENELEC and ETSI) to cover the requirements of the EU AIA. The Commission shall assess the conformity of the documents drafted by the ESOs with its initial request. Where a harmonised standard meets the requirements which it is intended to cover and which are set out in the relevant Union harmonisation legislation, the Commission shall immediately publish a reference to that harmonised standard in the Official Journal of the European Union.

Other Standardisation Organisations, such as ISO or IEC, are also working on the development of technical and operational standards to ensure the proper development of AI systems. A summary of the main ones is given below, followed by a description of the specific committees that focus on AI standardisation.

3.5 Main Standardisation Organizations working on the AI

3.5.1 International Standards Organization - ISO

ISO is an independent, non-governmental organisation that brings together experts from around the world who agree to develop and publish standards in various fields. ISO was founded in 1947 and is endorsed by representatives from government, academia, research, industry and NGOs.

ISO's work is guided by the principles of impartiality, consensus, relevance and inclusiveness, always promoting international co-operation despite political differences between countries or companies. It operates through a network of national standards bodies, with each member country having its own ISO member body responsible for coordinating standardisation activities within its jurisdiction. ISO standards are developed through a fully transparent and inclusive process involving technical committees, working groups and stakeholders from around the world. Specifically, Joint Technical Committee 1 (JTC-1), together with the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC), is the committee focused on information technologies. More specifically, the subcommittee SC-42 is the one focused on AI. (For more information on JTC-1/SC-42 and its publications, see 2.3.1).

This committee has recently published ISO/IEC 42001, an international standard that specifies requirements for establishing, implementing, maintaining and continually improving an Artificial Intelligence Management System (AIMS) within an organisation. It is intended for organisations that provide or use AI-based products or services, to ensure the responsible development and use of AI systems. Unfortunately, the document is very general and does not

contain specific recommendations for the health imaging field. The main initiatives and projects are listed in section 2.3.1 of this document.

3.5.2 International Electrotechnical Commission – IEC

The IEC is a global organisation established in 1960. Its work includes the preparation and publication of International Standards for electrical, electronic and related technologies. It works closely with experts from industry, academia and government. Its work is carried out through a network of technical committees and subcommittees.

The IEC works closely with other organisations, including ISO, to coordinate and harmonise standards. Many standards are adopted as ISO/IEC standards. There are also Joint Technical Committees (JTC), such as JTC 1 - Standardisation Programme on Artificial Intelligence, which is described in more detail in section 2.3.2.

3.5.3 European Committee for Standardization – CEN

CEN is a European Standardisation Organisation established in 1961 and recognised by the European Union. As stated on its website, it "*provides a platform for the development of European standards and other technical documents relating to various types of products, materials, services and processes*".

The dynamic of the organisation is similar to that of the IEC, and standards are developed through a consensus-based process involving experts from industry, government, academia and other stakeholders. Specific technical committees and working groups work together to draft and revise standards, considering the latest technological advances, market needs and regulatory requirements.

CEN also seeks full alignment with international standards wherever possible and works closely with ISO and IEC to facilitate global trade, engineering and business.

3.5.4 European Electrotechnical Committee for Standardization – CENELEC

Founded in 1973, CENELEC is also the organisation recognised by the European Union as responsible for the development of electrotechnical standards. Like other bodies and organisations, CENELEC's membership is drawn from key industries, academia, government and other related stakeholders, it is made up of sector-specific Technical Committees and works closely with the IEC to further promote alignment and coordination.

The JTC-21 is a Joint Technical Committee jointly launched by CEN-CENELEC in June 2021 with the primary objective of steering standardisation efforts towards AI systems, while

prioritising and addressing key issues such as their trustworthiness or respect for fundamental human rights. The JTC-21 and its activities concerning the development of safe, reliable, and ethically sound AI systems are described in section 2.3.2.

3.5.5 National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST)

NIST is another relevant organisation to consider. It is a non-regulatory agency of the United States Department of Commerce and was established in 1901 to help develop and advance the scientific and technological competitiveness of the United States. The organisation includes the development of standards in many fields, as well as metrology and calibration services. It works closely with other international organisations to develop appropriate standards and technologies.

NIST's AI-related activities include initiatives such as the AI Risk Management Framework (AI RMF 1.0) in January 2023, or the establishment of the Artificial Intelligence Safety Institute Consortium (AISIC) and defined working groups in February 2024. NIST also played an active role in the US-EU Trade and Technology Council Joint Statement (May 2022), which includes a section on the importance of AI technologies and the need for cooperation and coordination to standardise them.¹⁰

3.6 Initiatives from Standardisation Organizations in IA.

Standardisation organisations play a crucial role in various aspects of global trade, technology and the safety of new technologies such as Artificial Intelligence. Artificial intelligence has been on the roadmap of these organisations since around 2017, but in recent years the involvement of organisations such as ISO or CEN has increased significantly. In fact, in December 2022, the European Commission issued a draft standardisation request to CEN and CENELEC (the main standardisation organisations in Europe), which are expected to deliver their joint final report by January 2025. The requested standards relate to the essential requirements for high-risk AI systems, such as almost all developments in medical imaging. CEN and CENELEC, as well as similar organisations in other regions, are also working to promote standards for artificial intelligence systems. The following figure shows a chronology of selected reports and publications from standardisation organizations, as well as important milestones:

¹⁰ <https://www.nist.gov/itl/ai-risk-management-framework>

Figure 3: Chronology of relevant standard reports and publications.

All of these reports and publications are critical to the development of operational guidance for the implementation of AI systems and are expected to facilitate compliance with the technical obligations prescribed by international regulations.

3.6.1 ISO/IEC Joint Technical Committee-1

JTC-1 is the **Joint Technical Committee** from ISO and IEC for information technologies (IT). This committee is made up of experts from over 100 countries, representing their national standards body or committees, as well as experts from certain key industry partners. Its role is to develop and agree information technology standards. These global technology standards cover many areas, such as sensor networks, cyber security, cloud computing or digital storage.

JTC-1 is made up of a number of subcommittees, each dedicated to a specific area. However, these subcommittees can all be part of a working group to address a particular challenge or area of knowledge that includes a range of approaches from different areas of expertise (e.g. smart cities or quantum information technologies). The **JTC-1/SC-42 subcommittee** is the one focused on artificial intelligence. As stated on its website, it is "the first international committee to address the entire AI ecosystem". The subcommittee is formed by representatives from 40 countries. There are experts from 26 countries participating as observers. Its inaugural meeting was held in April 2018. The scope of SC-42 includes:

- Serve as the focus and proponent for JTC 1’s standardization program on AI.
- Provide guidance to JTC 1, IEC, and ISO committees developing IA applications.

- Contribute to the development of standards to address the entire AI ecosystem, ensuring interoperability, trustworthiness, and ethical considerations

The bi-annual meetings that the SC-42 organizes constitute an interesting and stimulating dialogue about the AI ecosystem, its trends, applications, etc. The subcommittee website displays 27 publications currently available, and the list of the main publications which had been made by the JTC-1/SC-42 can be located on the reference below.¹¹ Table 1 shows JTC-1/SC-42 publications that have been selected according to their relevance to the standardization of AI. Together, these publications contribute to the development of robust, reliable and ethical AI systems by providing standardised guidelines and frameworks across different sectors. Where these publications address the healthcare domain, this is noted in the comment column.

Publication	Remarks
2018/02: ISO/IEC TR 20547-2:2018 – Information technology – Big Data reference architecture – Part 2: Use cases and derived requirements	It provides a set of use cases to illustrate big data reference architecture (BDRA). The point 5.5 is “Health care and life sciences”, and it tackles the BDRA and standard procedures that should be used by a series of use cases: Use case 16: Electronic Medical Record Data Use case 17: Pathology Imaging/Digital Pathology Use case 18: Computational Bioimaging Use case 19: Genomic Measurements. Use case 20: Comparative Analysis for Metagenomes and Genomes Use case 21: Individualized Diabetes Management Use case 22: Statistical Relational Artificial Intelligence for Health Care Use case 23: World Population-Scale Epidemiological Study Use case 24: Social Contagion Modelling for Planning, Public Health, and Disaster Management. Use case 25: Biodiversity and LifeWatch
2020/05: ISO/IEC TR 24028:2020 - Overview of trustworthiness in artificial intelligence ¹²	Possible approaches to mitigating AI system vulnerabilities that relate to its trustworthiness. This document overall identifies the need for developing new International Standards for AI systems that can go beyond characteristics and requirements of conventional software development.
2021/05: ISO/IEC TR 24030: Information technology – Artificial intelligence (AI) – Use cases	This TR is illustrating the applicability of AI standardization across a variety of application domains, sharing the collected use cases in support of fostering collaboration, and point out possible new requirements to stakeholders (standardized demands), from the real-world developments and the market. The healthcare domain is a main use case, with several subcases. (29) Nevertheless, there are no references to the case of medical imaging.
2021/11: ISO/IEC TR 24027: Information technology – Artificial intelligence (AI) – Bias in AI systems.	Careful study of the bias in AI, potential sources, its assessing through metrics, and treatment strategies.

¹¹ https://www.iec.ch/dyn/www/f?p=103:22:::::FSP_ORG_ID:21538

¹² <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/en/#iso:std:iso-iec:tr:24028:ed-1:v1:en>

2022/07: ISO/IEC 22989:2022: Information technology – Artificial intelligence – Artificial intelligence concepts and terminology	This document provides standardized concepts and terminology to help AI technology to be better understood and used by a broader set of stakeholders.
2023/06: ISO/IEC 25059:2023 normative: Systems and Software Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuaRE): Quality model for AI systems.	It is establishing a thorough reference for evaluating AI systems attending to its specific domain characteristics. Interesting document to: - use as a reference point from previous bibliography. - identify fields for defining KPI's
2023/12: ISO/IEC 42001:2023 Information technology – Artificial Intelligence – Management system.	Document providing a guide for establishing, implementing, maintaining, and continually improving an AI management system within the context of an organization, depending on the use case. It tackles the search of the appropriate balance between governance mechanism and innovation itself.
2023/12: CEN/CLC ISO/IEC TR 24027:2023: Information technology – Artificial intelligence (AI) – Bias in AI systems and AI aided decision making.	This document is an updated version of ISO/IEC TR 24027:2021, and addresses bias in relation to AI systems, especially with regards to AI-aided decision-making. Measurement techniques and methods for assessing bias are described, with the aim to address and treat bias-related vulnerabilities.
2024/01: ISO/IEC 5339:2024 Information technology - Artificial intelligence - Guidance for AI applications.	Thorough guidance for AI applications in different domains, using the framework "make", "use", and "impact" perspective. It is also contributing to help the AI developer's community and stakeholders with the answer to the important question: "What are the characteristics and considerations of an AI application?"

Table 1: Selection of relevant publications by ISO/IEC JTC-1/SC-42.

3.6.2 CEN-CENELEC Joint Technical Committee-21

The JTC-21 Joint Technical Committee between CEN and CENELEC was launched in June 2021 based on the recommendations of the public documents '*CEN-CENELEC response to the EC White Paper*', and the '*German Standardization Roadmap for Artificial Intelligence*'.

JTC-21 describes on their website the following: '*CEN-CLC/JTC 21 will proceed with the identification and adoption of international standards already available or under development from other organizations like ISO/IEC JTC 1 and its subcommittees, such as SC 42 Artificial Intelligence. Furthermore, CEN-CLC/JTC 21 will focus on producing standardization deliverables that address European market and societal needs, as well as underpinning EU legislation, policies, principles, and values.*'

The paper of June 2020, where CEN-CENELEC are addressing the EU White Paper on AI, had identified 12 important themes, adding for a total of 34 recommendations for the European Commission that were considering the Road Map for AI standardization. The 12 themes were:

- Fundamental considerations
- Definitions and terminology
- Defining the scope of the regulatory framework
- Addressing the risks and values
- Voluntary labelling of non-high-risk AI systems
- Role of Digital Sovereignty
- Explainability (AI)
- Virtual/digital testing
- Safety and conformity assessment
- Connecting Research and Development (R&D) with standardization
- Shaping Europe’s Digital Future
- European data strategy

It is worth highlighting that one of the recommendations of that document was to request European Standardization Organizations to provide sector-specific standardization conformity assessments schemes. The CEN-CENELEC Joint Technical Committee 21 (JTC 21) also plays a significant role in the development of AI standards for accomplishing the requirements stated in the EU AIA, particularly those for high-risk AI systems. The specific case of the healthcare domain was included in the European Commission mandate to the JTC 2.

Therefore, the JTC 21 is working on several documents to identify the gaps in existing standards and provide recommendations for future standardization efforts. A selection of relevant documents where JTC-21 is involved is shown in the table below. Most of these documents are currently under drafting or in a preliminary version.

A complete an up-to-date table with all the documents in the JTC-21 Work Programme can be found on their website¹³.

Publication	Remarks
<p>FprCEN/CLC ISO/IEC/TS 12791 (WI=JT021013) Information technology - Artificial intelligence - Treatment of unwanted bias in classification and regression machine learning tasks (ISO/IEC DTS 12791:2023) Status: <u>Approved</u></p>	<p>This document describes how to address unwanted bias in AI systems that use ML to conduct classification and regression tasks.</p>

¹³https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:22:0:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:2916257,25&cs=1827B89DA69577BF3631EE2B6070F207D

<p>prCEN/CLC/TR 17894 (WI=JT021001) Artificial Intelligence Conformity Assessment <u>Status: Under Drafting</u></p>	<p>It defines the objects of conformity related to AI systems and all other related aspects of the process of conformity assessment. The document also reviews to what extent AI poses specific challenges with respect to assessment of, for example, software engineering, data quality and engineering processes.</p>
<p>prEN ISO/IEC 12792 (WI=JT021022) Information technology - Artificial intelligence - Transparency taxonomy of AI systems <u>Status: Under Approval</u></p>	<p>The document defines a taxonomy of information elements to assist AI stakeholders with identifying and addressing the needs for transparency of AI systems.</p>
<p>prEN ISO/IEC 23282 (WI=JT021012) Artificial Intelligence - Evaluation methods for accurate natural language processing systems. <u>Status: Under Drafting</u></p>	<p>It sets the evaluation of NLP systems in the sense of measuring the quality of the system's results. It provides a definition of evaluation methods together with guidance on how to select, implement and interpret them.</p>
<p>prEN ISO/IEC 24029-2 (WI=JT021015) Artificial intelligence (AI) - Assessment of the robustness of neural networks - Part 2: Methodology for the use of formal methods <u>Status: Preliminary</u></p>	<p>This document provides methodology for the use of formal methods to assess robustness properties of neural networks. The document focuses on how to select, apply, and manage formal methods to prove robustness properties.</p>
<p>prEN ISO/IEC 25059 (WI=JT021014) Software engineering - Systems and software Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuaRE) - Quality model for AI systems (ISO/IEC 25059:2023) <u>Status: Under Enquiry</u></p>	<p>This document outlines a quality model for AI systems and is an application-specific extension to the standards on SQuaRE</p>
<p>prEN ISO/IEC 8183 (WI=JT021020) Information technology - Artificial intelligence - Data life cycle framework (ISO/IEC 8183:2023) <u>Status: Under Enquiry</u></p>	<p>It defines the stages and associated actions for data processing throughout AI system life cycle, including acquisition, creation, development, deployment, maintenance and decommissioning. It does not define specific platforms or tools, but it is applicable to all organizations regardless of type, size, or nature, that use data in the development and use of AI.</p>

Table 2: Selection of documents and reports part of the CEN/CENELEC JTC-21 Work Programme.

An analysis of the reports included in table 1 and table 2 shows that there is too much room for improvement in the development of technical and operational standards in the field of AI applied to medical imaging. Most of the reports and guidelines published so far by standardisation organisations are not specific to the medical sector, whose products depend on other regulations that are not AI-specific. For example, Table 3 shows some specific CEN, CENELEC or ISO guidelines and standards for the medical field that contain or may contain AI-based components.

Publication	Remarks
EN 60601-1 - Medical Electrical Equipment – Part 1: General Requirements for Basic Safety and Essential Performance	Requirements for the safety and essential performance of medical electrical equipment. It is crucial to ensure that medical devices are safe for both patients and healthcare providers
EN ISO 14971:2019 - Medical Devices – Application of Risk Management to Medical Devices	Processes for managing risks associated with medical devices, including those incorporating AI. It helps manufacturers identify hazards, estimate and evaluate risks, and implement control measures
EN ISO 13485:2016 - Medical Devices – Quality Management Systems – Requirements for Regulatory Purposes	Requirements for a quality management system specific to the medical devices industry, ensuring consistent design, development, production, and delivery of medical devices.
EN ISO 15223-1:2021 - Medical Devices – Symbols to be Used with Information to be Supplied by the Manufacturer – Part 1: General Requirements:	Symbols used to convey information on the safe and effective use of medical devices. It is essential for ensuring clear communication and compliance with regulatory requirements
EN ISO 20417:2021 - Medical Devices – Information to be Supplied by the Manufacturer:	Guidelines on the information that manufacturers must supply with medical devices, including instructions for use, labelling, and other essential information
EN ISO 17664-1:2021 - Processing of Health Care Products – Information to be Provided by the Medical Device Manufacturer for the Processing of Medical Devices – Part 1: Critical and Semi-Critical Medical Devices	Information that manufacturers must provide to ensure the proper processing (cleaning, disinfection, and sterilization) of medical devices

Table 3: Selection of documents and reports from Standardisations in the field of medical devices that could be related to the development of AI systems.

However, the analysis of this source of information shows that these documents lack specific recommendations for developing specific AI systems in the medical field. This insufficient information is also detected when we enter a more specific knowledge domain like medical imaging. Fortunately for the CHAIMELEON consortium anticipated the need for operational and technical standards in medical imaging. The analysis of this source of information shows that these documents lack specific recommendations for developing specific AI systems in the medical field. This insufficient information is also detected when we enter a more specific knowledge domain like medical imaging. Fortunately for the CHAIMELEON consortium anticipated the need for operational and technical standards in medical imaging.

3.7 Public or Private Initiatives fostering AI development.

The analysis of sources of information about Legal Frameworks for AI development (section 3.3) or the main documentation published by international standardisation organizations (section 3.6) involves a top-down approach, starting with the mission and objectives of important bodies such as the European Commission. However, this document also aims to gather information from a bottom-up approach. The bottom-up perspective includes initiatives at the national level and learning experiences from high-impact projects or independent researchers publishing their work in relevant scientific journals

3.7.1 National initiatives

Many countries and leading technology companies have published reports on the development of AI. However, including all of them would result in overlapping information. We have therefore carefully selected a subset of these documents that comprehensively cover all the key factors to be addressed.

- **How can humans keep the upper hand? Report on the ethical matters raised by AI algorithms.**¹⁴ *French Data Protection Authority (CNIL), France.* This document covers many different areas regarding AI, from social perception to specific ethical issues.
- **Second edition of the German Standardization Roadmap on Artificial Intelligence.**¹⁵ *German Institute for Standardization, Germany.* This document address AI from a high-level conceptual view and focuses on specific domains and use cases.
- **AI4People's Ethical Framework for a Good AI Society: Opportunities, Risks, Principles, and Recommendations.**¹⁶ *ATONIUM EISMD, EU.* The report summarizes the opportunities and risks of AI for society, present five ethical principles and twenty recommendations.
- **Ethics of AI in Radiology: European and North American Multisociety Statement.**¹⁷ *International.* This document outlines considerations relevant to the application of AI in medical imaging.

¹⁴ https://www.cnil.fr/sites/cnil/files/atoms/files/cnil_rapport_ai_gb_web.pdf

¹⁵ <https://www.din.de/resource/blob/916798/ed09ae58b60f0d3a498fa90fa5085b7c/nrm-ki-engl-2023-final-web-250-neu-data.pdf>

¹⁶ Floridi, L., Cows, J., Beltrametti, M., Chatila, R., Chazerand, P., Dignum, V., & Vayena, E. (2018). AI4People—an ethical framework for a good AI society: opportunities, risks, principles, and recommendations. *Minds and machines*, 28, 689-707.

¹⁷ <https://www.acr.org/-/media/ACR/Files/Informatics/Ethics-of-AI-in-Radiology-European-and-North-American-Multisociety-Statement--6-13-2019.pdf>

- **Montréal Déclaration for a Responsible Development of Artificial Intelligence.**¹⁸ *Université de Montréal, Canada.* Extensive reports with the purpose of developing an ethical framework for AI, guiding the digital transition and opening discussion a national and international forum.
- **Work in the age of artificial: Four perspectives on the economy, employment, skills and ethics.**¹⁹ *Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment, Finland.* The report collects four main articles that discuss the effects of AI on economics, labour market and work transformation, educational reforms and skill maintenance and ethics.
- **Artificial intelligence and privacy.**²⁰ *Norwegian Data Protection Authority, Norwegian.* The report thoroughly discusses the technical aspects of AI and the challenges it presents in the context of data protection and compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).
- **The AI Now Report: The Social and Economic Implications of Artificial Intelligence Technologies in the Near-Term.**²¹ *AI Now Institute, USA.* The report covers AI focusing on the dimensions of Healthcare, Labour, Inequality and Ethics.
- **AI Principles Progress Update 2023.**²² *Google, USA.* Annual report covering AI principles focused on four main areas: culture and education, structures and progress, tools, techniques and progress and external engagement and partnerships.
- **The assessment list for trustworthy artificial intelligence (ALTAI).**²³ Independent high-level expert group on artificial intelligence set up by the European Commission, EU. Report covering a practical tool used for self-assessing the trustworthiness of AI under development.
- **Artificial Intelligence Australia’s Ethics Framework A Discussion Paper.**²⁴ Government Department of Industry Innovation and Science, Australia. The report covers key principles and measures to maximize AI outcomes while keeping the well-being of national priorities.

¹⁸ https://declarationmontreal-iaresponsable.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/UdeM_Decl_IA-Resp_LA-Declaration-ENG_WEB_09-07-19.pdf

¹⁹ Koski, O., Husso, K. (2018). Work in the age of artificial intelligence: Four perspectives on the economy, employment, skills and ethics.

²⁰ <https://www.datatilsynet.no/globalassets/global/english/ai-and-privacy.pdf>

²¹ https://ainowinstitute.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/AI_Now_2019_Report.pdf

²² <https://ai.google/static/documents/ai-principles-2023-progress-update.pdf>

²³ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence-altai-self-assessment>

²⁴ Dawson, D., Schleiger, E., Horton, J., McLaughlin, J., Robinson, C., Quezada, G., & Hajkowicz, S. (2019). Artificial intelligence: Australia’s ethics framework-a discussion paper.

3.7.2 Consortiums dedicated to AI.

Another source of information are large consortia working on projects related to the development of AI technologies. We pay particular attention to those consortia that are more related to medical AI systems. We have identified a wide range of consortia, from academic-led initiatives to high-level national strategies. We have selected the following active consortia.

- **AI Safety Institute Consortium (AISIC):** More than 200 organizations aligned together with US National institute of Standards and Technology (NIST). Their efforts will be focused on developing science-based and empirically backed guidelines and standards for AI. It is an active and open consortium.
- **Commonwealth Artificial Intelligence Consortium (CAIC):** Consortium focused on leveraging AI tools to support small states and empower Commonwealth's young people. The consortium includes global technological firms, world-leading research institutes, non-profit organizations and Commonwealth's members.
- **Trustworthy Planning and scheduling with Learning and Explanations (TUPLES):** Consortium that aims to build trusted planning and scheduling systems that are safe, robust, explainable, and efficient. The consortium is composed of various leading AI laboratories, top scientists and researchers, and three specialized companies.
- **First Spanish industrial consortium focused on AI (IndesIA):** The consortium, which includes a variety of companies from multiple sectors, is dedicated to promoting the use of data and the implementation of AI in both leading corporations and Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs).
- **National Consortium of Intelligent Medical Imaging (NCIMI):** a network of NHS hospitals, clinical leaders, industry experts in the fields of AI and medical imaging, world-leading academic researchers plus patient groups and charities. Consortium led by the University of Oxford.
- **Research Consortium for Medical Image Analysis (RECOMIA):** Non-profit organization promoting research on AI and medical image.
- **Machine Learning in Medical Imaging Consortium (MaLMIC):** The consortium aims to accelerate research and development of machine learning solutions for unmet needs in medical imaging through collaborations between academic and clinical researchers, and with Canadian industry.

3.8 Relevant projects for medical imaging enhanced with AI.

In this section, we will cover some of the most relevant projects for AI applied to medical imaging. We pay special attention to those projects funded by the European Commission. We present a list of relevant projects in alphabetical order:

- **AI4LIFE:** The project aims to facilitate life scientists' access to FAIR and open data, focusing especially on AI-powered image analysis methods.²⁵
- **CanSERV:** Aims to achieve a pan-European collaboration to bring precision medicine solutions to benefit the cancer patient community.²⁶
- **CHAMELON:** Accelerating the lab-to-market transition of AI tools for cancer management.²⁷
- **EUCAIM:** The European Union has launched an initiative for Cancer Imaging as part of Europe's Beating Cancer Plan (EBCP). To this end, a European federated infrastructure for medical cancer imaging, known as EUCAIM, is currently under development. The goal of European Federation for CANcer IMages (EUCAIM) is to build a pan-European digital hybrid federated infrastructure of cancer-related radiological and nuclear medicine images and related information, ready to be used to develop Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools for Precision Medicine.²⁸
- **EuCanImage:** European cancer image platform linked to biological and health data for next-generation AI and precision medicine in Oncology.²⁹
- **Euro-BiolImaging:** Analogous to the EUCAIM initiative, the European Union founded Euro-BiolImaging,³⁰ a domain-specific program for biomedical imaging. Although the scope of this project encompasses imaging from a broader perspective than AI, it has facilitated the support and enhancement of other specific AI projects.
- **FUTURE-IA:** Instead of research projects, FUTURE AI is an international, multi-stakeholder initiative for defining and maintaining concrete guidelines that will facilitate the design, development, validation and deployment of trustworthy AI solutions in medicine and healthcare based on six guiding principles: Fairness, Universality, Traceability, Usability, Robustness and Explainability.³¹

²⁵ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101057970>

²⁶ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101058620>

²⁷ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/952172>

²⁸ <https://cancerimage.eu/>

²⁹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/952103>

³⁰ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/262023>

³¹ <https://future-ai.eu/>

- **iMagine:** The project will provide a selection of free at the point of use image datasets, AI-empowered high-performance image analysis tools, and best practice documents for scientific image analysis. These services and materials enable better processing and analysis for imaging marine and freshwater data.³²
- **INCISIVE:** Multimodal AI-based toolbox and an interoperable health imaging repository for the empowerment of imaging analysis related to the diagnosis, prediction and follow-up of cancer.³³
- **Medical Open Network for Artificial Intelligence (MONAI):** Self-described as a set of open-source, freely available collaborative frameworks built for accelerating research and clinical collaboration in Medical Imaging. They have developed different frameworks for labelling, implementing healthcare imaging AI models and deploying solution in clinical production environments.³⁴
- **PRIMAGE:** Predictive in-silico multiscale analytics to support cancer personalized diagnosis and prognosis, empowered by imaging biomarkers.³⁵
- **ProCancer-I:** AI platform integrating imaging data and models, supporting precision care through prostate cancer's continuum.³⁶

The conducted review reveals that the majority of efforts made in the field underscore the needs for standards. Most of the initiatives fall short of providing concrete, technical support on how to fulfil this need to correctly develop a new AI system. There is a pressing need for more in-depth standardization documentation. We believe that the CHAMELON project is in a privileged position to lead and contribute to this standardization need and promote a more robust and efficient AI development pipeline.

³² <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101058625>

³³ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/952179>

³⁴ <https://monai.io/core.html>

³⁵ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/826494>

³⁶ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/952159>

4 Literature Review on AI standards applied to Medical Imaging

In this section, we have explored the existing literature to incorporate expert views on existing standards, frameworks, metrics and guidelines to ensure adequate development and, where possible, clinical implementation of AI models in the field of health imaging. This study will involve a systematic review of existing publications, and its results will be compared with the best practices implemented during the CHAIMELEON project to provide guidance. The study will also help us to identify relevant projects and initiatives and pave the way for the application of AI in real clinical settings.

4.1 Systematic Review Methodology

Database searches were conducted through Google Scholar, accessing a database with approximately 200 million registries. In April 2024, a simple query searching for publications in the field of Artificial intelligence revealed more than 1.3 million scientific works contained in the database.

The Systematic Review was inspired by the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) (hereafter referred to as PRISMA).³⁷ PRISMA is a reporting guideline designed to address systematic reviews that includes a checklist of 27 items recommended for reporting in systematic reviews. PRISMA has been widely endorsed and adopted, as evidenced by its co-publication in multiple journals, citation in over 60,000 reports (Scopus, August 2020), endorsement by nearly 200 journals and systematic review organisations, and adoption in various disciplines. A brief diagram of the PRISMA Methodology followed in this study is explained here:

- The study included 4 different queries (see Figure 4).
- Each query included a combination of keywords that could be part of the Title, the Abstract and the Full Text of the document.
- All queries were restricted to academic papers published between January 2016 and October 2024.
- The study only included works that were considered journal articles.
- The study only accepted academic papers with a valid DOI as an identifier.

³⁷ Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71

- For each query, we created two subsets. First, we prioritised the papers by the number of citations (identifying the most relevant works). Second, we sorted the documents by publication date (to include those recent scientific papers that could be of interest for our study but with few citations due to their recent publication).
- As a result, we obtained 4 databases searches prioritised by citations and 4 databases prioritised by the publication date, 8 databases in total.
- For the 4 databases searches prioritized by citations, we included at least the first 25% of the scientific works identified in the initial query with a minimum of 20 cites per work (1650 works).
- For the 4 databases prioritized by publication date, we revised the title of the 12% of the most cited works identified between January 2016 and February 2024 (850 works in total). In addition we selected for revision the 60% of the most cited works published between February 2024 and October 2024 (1,450 works). The total number of works revised of the 4 databases prioritized by publication date resulted in $850+1450=2,300$.
- This means that $1650+2300=3,950$ records were screened through the revision of title and journal of publication from the initial database of 8,401 of works, 4,451 papers were excluded because: 1) they were not related to the field of interest of our study or 2) they were considered publications with a low number of citations.
- From the valid cohort of 3,950 papers, one person reviewed the title and journal of the publication to select the papers that were more relevant to the purpose of our study. For the analysis of the most questionable papers, the abstract was also reviewed. The review ended with the selection of 194 papers for further review and the exclusion of 3,756 papers.
- An experienced AI specialist, revised the abstract of the 194 papers and excluded those publications unrelated to the implementation of standards, guidelines, clinical implementation protocols of AI, the development of metrics to assess AI, and the development of frameworks and projects to translate AI into clinical practice. The analysis concluded with a database of 127 papers published between January 2016 and October 2024.
- The selected collection of 127 publications was used to propose a sandbox of guidelines to support AI in medical imaging, and to advance our recommendations.

The selection of works schema following the PRISMA methodology is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. PRISMA Methodology for the identification of relevant publications.

In figure 5, we present a summary of the queries and keywords used during the systematic review

Figure 5. Schema explaining the queries, decision tree and results from the PRISMA methodology

4.2 Quality of the collected works

In the following lines, we have evaluated the quality of the collected papers selected for our study. This analysis was limited to the final 127 papers, which were selected as being more related to the implementation of standards and guidelines for medical imaging AI systems.

The study started in January 2016, with one paper published and it finishes on October 2024. We found a significant increase in 2020, the year of the COVID crisis. In that year, there was not only an increase in the number of publications related to the development of AI tools applied to medical imaging to improve diagnosis, but also relevant publications related to the development of standardisation strategies and guidelines for the integration of these technologies into medical practice.

First, we present a chart of the most active authors. In our database of 127 relevant scientific papers, we have identified Elmar Kotter from the Department of Diagnostic and Interventional Radiology, Faculty of Medicine, University of Freiburg, Germany, as the most active author.

Our study also includes important contributions from researchers involved in the CHAIMELEON project, such as Angel Alberich Bayarri (3 publications)^{38,39,40}; Philippe Lambin (3)^{41,42,43} Emmanuel Neri (1)⁴⁰ and Luis Martí Bonmati(1)³⁸.

Figure 6 Identification of most active authors in the 127 publications database

We also present a heat map of the most active institutions. We have collected more publications from American institutions. Harvard University, Stanford and the University of California are the most prominent institutions in our collection of 127 publications. In Europe, we highlight the INSERM (7 publications), the University of Freiburg and the Scientific Institute for Research, Hospitalisation and Healthcare (IRCCS) in Italy with 6 publications and the Charite Hospital in Berlin (also part of the CHAIMELEON project) with 5 publications.

³⁸ Kocak, B., Alberich-Bayarri, A., Marti-Bonmati, L. et al. (2024, January 17). METHodological RadiomIcS Score (METRICS): a quality scoring tool for radiomics research endorsed by EuSoMI. *Insights Into Imaging*, 15(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13244-023-01572-w>

³⁹ Alberich-Bayarri, A. et al. (2020, June 4). ESR Statement on the Validation of Imaging Biomarkers. *Insights Into Imaging*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13244-020-00872-9>

⁴⁰ deSouza, N. M., Neri, E., Alberich-Bayarri, A., et al. (2019, August 29). Validated imaging biomarkers as decision-making tools in clinical trials and routine practice: current status and recommendations from the EIBALL* subcommittee of the European Society of Radiology (ESR). *Insights Into Imaging*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13244-019-0764-0>

⁴¹ Huang, E. P., M. L., Lambin, P., et al. (2022, November 28). Criteria for the translation of radiomics into clinically useful tests. *Nature Reviews Clinical Oncology*, 20(2), 69–82. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41571-022-00707-0>

⁴² isvikis, D., Lambin, P., et al. (2022, July 9). Application of artificial intelligence in nuclear medicine and molecular imaging: a review of current status and future perspectives for clinical translation. *European Journal of Nuclear Medicine and Molecular Imaging*, 49(13), 4452–4463. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00259-022-05891-w>

⁴³ Salahuddin, Z., Woodruff, H. C., Chatterjee, A., & Lambin, P. (2022, January). Transparency of deep neural networks for medical image analysis: A review of interpretability methods. *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, 140, 105111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compbiomed.2021.105111>

Figure 7. Identification of most active institutions in the 127 databases

The analysis of the publication date showed that the interest in guidelines and technical standards started in 2018 and showed a continuous progress over the years. It seems that the impact of the COVID pandemic has a negative effect in the years 2021, 2022 and 2023. It also seems that the announcement and publication of the EU AIA has a significant impact on scientists and AI experts with an increase of more than 400% in the number of publications compared to 2023.

Figure 8 Number of scientific papers by publication year in the 127 publications database

Finally we present the most frequent journals of our 127-works collection. 57 of the 127 publications (45% of all publications) were published in the 13 journals included in the figure below. All these journals present a Q1 as the best quartile and have a high impact score.

The average impact score of our collection is 12,34.⁴⁴ The most frequent journal in our collection was Insights into imaging, a journal of the European Society of Radiology (ESR).

Figure 9 Scientific Journals with more publication in the 127 publications database.

A thorough analysis of the 127 papers revealed that there is no comprehensive sandbox of relevant technical and operational standards for the development of medical imaging AI systems.

Although the collection of 127 papers includes several review studies that provide general recommendations for the technical implementation of AI systems,⁴⁵ We couldn't find any research paper explaining sufficient factors and KPIs involved in the entire medical imaging AI systems lifecycle.

The collection of 127 papers includes interesting publications on standardising some steps of the medical imaging AI lifecycle, such as the contributions of initiatives such as TRIPOD, CONSORTIA or CLAIM, which provide insightful resources and recommendations for standardizing the early stages (or design phase) of the development of a medical imaging AI system. The collection of 127 papers also includes recommendations for evaluating the

⁴⁴ Journal Impact score and Quartile calculated for the period 2022-2023 through www.resurchify.com

⁴⁵ A) Susan Cheng Shelmerdine, Owen J Arthurs, Alastair Denniston, Neil J Sebire - Review of study reporting guidelines for clinical studies using artificial intelligence in healthcare: *BMJ Health & Care Informatics* 2021;28:e100385. B) Tambon, F., Laberge, G., An, L. et al. How to certify machine learning based safety-critical systems? A systematic literature review. *Autom Softw Eng* 29, 38 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10515-022-00337-x>. C) Arora, A., Alderman, J.E., Palmer, J. et al. The value of standards for health datasets in artificial intelligence-based applications. *Nat Med* 29, 2929–2938 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-023-02608-w>

technical performance of a medical imaging AI system (such as the METRICS RELOADED⁴⁶ initiative or the work published by Tanguay et al⁴⁷). However, these papers and initiatives do not provide guidelines or recommendations about those standards that are more related to the expected impact of a Medical Imaging AI system; few publications cover the ethical dimension of AI systems (e.g., METRICS RELOADED or CLAIM do not address aspects such as GDPR compliance, fairness, etc.).

On the one hand, most of the 127 papers in the collection refer to publications that provide recommendations on technical aspects of medical imaging AI systems. For example, about 50% of the publications in the collection of works are dedicated to the importance of transparency, trustworthiness, and explainability of the Medical Imaging AI systems. During our study, we also noted an increased awareness within the scientific community of the robustness of the AI medical imaging system under development. In the collection of papers, there are 27 publications related to the robustness of AI systems.

On the other hand, the scientific community has published fewer works related to data privacy, GDPR compliance, fairness, and other important ethical components of a medical imaging AI system. There are of course some interesting papers⁴⁸ on the ethical implications of AI and the need for technical and operational standards in the field of ethics, but at the time of our study, the number of publications was lower than the other “more technical” aspects of a Medical Imaging AI system. In addition, the analysis of the 127 papers served to identify other aspects of a medical imaging AI system that are receiving more attention from the scientific community, such as the need to establish new technical and operational standards to assess the interoperability of the AI system, and how to implement more environmentally friendly AI models, also known as green AI.

4.3 Conclusions from the Quality Assessment of the Systematic Review

The conclusions are presented here:

- The selection of papers followed a **validated methodology** (PRISMA)
- The **number of documents** that were fully reviewed is significant: 127 Papers.

⁴⁶ Maier-Hein, L., Reinke, A., Godau, P. et al. Metrics reloaded: recommendations for image analysis validation. *Nat Methods* 21, 195–212 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-023-02151-z>

⁴⁷ Tanguay W, Acar P, Fine B, et al. Assessment of Radiology Artificial Intelligence Software: A Validation and Evaluation Framework. *Canadian Association of Radiologists Journal*. 2023;74(2):326-333. doi:10.1177/08465371221135760

⁴⁸ Currie, G., Hawk, K.E. & Rohren, E.M. Ethical principles for the application of artificial intelligence (AI) in nuclear medicine. *Eur J Nucl Med Mol Imaging* 47, 748–752 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00259-020-04678-1>

- The final collection of works included in the study were published by **renowned American and European Institutions** like Harvard, Stanford, UC, MIT, INSERM, University College of London, University of Freiburg, IRCCS from Italy or Charité.
- The final collection includes **top researchers** in AI applied to medical imaging. Various researchers participating in the development of the CHAIMELEON project were identified as important authors of some of these works.
- The 127 final collection includes top publications in high-impact journals and it can be used to advance the design of a sandbox for the development of technical and operational standards oriented towards AI medical imaging systems.
- The analysis of the 127 final collection showed that there is no methodology or sandbox of technical and operational standards to cover the entire lifecycle development of an AI Medical Imaging system
- The analysis of the 127 final collection provides insightful information about how to standardize the design of an AI model, the training, validation and technical assessment of the AI system as well as other aspects related to the ethical implications and the potential impact of the AI medical Imaging for patients, clinicians and healthcare organizations.
- The all the above, the database with 127 defined in our systematic review was considered **as valid and of high quality for the identification of research publications that can contribute to the development of a Sandbox of technical and operational standards** for the development of medical imaging AI systems.

5 Proposal for AI in healthcare and medical imaging standards

5.1 Focusing the study on AI applied to Medical Imaging

The analysis of scientific publications, standardisation initiatives, and the various strategic papers and national/international initiatives presented in sections 3 and 4, clearly demonstrate the present and future impact of artificial intelligence in the medical field.

AI is widely used in disease diagnostics, treatment planning and evaluation, clinical pathways development and many other unmet clinical needs. This study is focused on the use of AI in medical imaging and more concretely on disease identification in medical imaging. This means that the discussion about the standardization of AI in medical imaging will be focused on those algorithms tailored to the detection and/or segmentation of certain features on the image that could be used for screening, classification of diseases, and mainly, for detection purposes. We include in our study radiomics as a tool to extract quantitative features from images to predict patient outcomes.

For the avoidance of doubt, we exclude from this study AI applications targeted at facilitate the work of clinicians such as AI tools intended to facilitate reporting or support clinical decision-making.

This decision is aligned with the objectives of the CHAIMELEON project as well as with the current level of the development of this technology. The last update from the FDA about the development of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning (AI/ML)-Enabled Medical Devices (published in October 2023), identified 692 entries, with the field of Radiology as the first medical discipline with more developments in AI. The FDA update informed that 87% of devices authorized in 2022 were in the field of Radiology, followed by 7% in Cardiovascular and 1% each in Neurology, Haematology, Gastroenterology/Urology, and Ophthalmology.⁴⁹ The FDA identifies medical imaging diagnostics in radiology as the most active field in AI and therefore the field with a higher demand for standardization.

⁴⁹ U. S. Food and Drug Administration, Center for Devices and Radiological. Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning (AI/ML)-Enabled Medical Devices; 2021. <https://www.fda.gov/medical-devices/software-medical-device-samd/artificial-intelligence-and-machine-learning-ai-ml-enabled-medical-devices>. accessed April 2nd 2020

5.2 The Impact of the AI Act. The need for Standardization AI medical imaging systems

During the development of this document, the EU Parliament approved the European AI Act (EU AIA) on 13 March 2024.⁵⁰ The new law was published on July 12th, 2024. The EU AIA aims to regulate AI technologies based on the risks that their use is likely to raise to the health, safety, and fundamental rights of individuals. The EU AIA applies to all AI systems, including AI systems oriented to medical imaging. These AI systems should be included in the 3rd category (High Risk AI systems) due to their significant impact on health and safety of the patients. Besides, most of these AI systems are also critical systems for the provision of healthcare services in private and public organizations.

Figure 10 Risk based approach of AI systems in the EU AI Act

Following the risk-based approach of the EU AIA, a high-risk AI system must follow specific, but horizontal, conformity assessment procedures before it can be placed on the market or used in any EU Member State. The EU AIA does not go into detail on how high-risk AI systems must comply with the essential requirements of the EU AIA and introduces the need for harmonised standards. Although harmonised standards are being developed by the European Standardisation Organisations (ESOs) such as CEN, CENELEC, or ETSI (see section 2 of this document), a significant effort is needed in the different fields of expertise to ensure tailor-made harmonised standards to support innovation in different sectors such as healthcare, education, financial services, etc

⁵⁰ Available at https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-9-2024-0138_EN.pdf

A critical aspect of the new law is that the EU AIA establishes a presumption of conformity for high-risk AI systems. This means that the manufacturer or developer of a high-risk medical imaging AI system must either develop the system to harmonised standards or complete a conformity assessment before placing the new AI diagnostic tool on the market. This supposes new responsibilities for developers to meet the essential requirements for high-risk AI systems. Some of these responsibilities are presented in Table 4.

Examples of New Responsibility for AI stakeholders in the EU AIA
<i>1)Mandatory requirements to observe the principles of: (i) human agency and oversight; (ii) technical robustness and safety; (iii) privacy and data governance; (iv) transparency; (v) promoting equal access, gender equality and cultural diversity, while avoiding discriminatory impacts and unfair biases; and (vi) promoting social and environmental well-being</i>
<i>2) AI Systems must meet requirements for transparency, meaning that the AI systems are developed and used in a way that allows appropriate traceability and explainability, while making humans aware that they communicate or interact with an AI system.</i>
<i>3) There is an explicit requirement that not only the risks to health and safety must be considered throughout the entire product life cycle, but also the risks to “fundamental rights”</i>
<i>4) The requirement for the datasets to be, to the best extent possible, complete and free of errors</i>
<i>5) Oversight of systems is required: ‘where appropriate, such measures should guarantee that the system is subject to in-built operational constraints that cannot be overridden by the system itself and is responsive to the human operator.</i>
<i>6) Providers are required to design and develop accurate, robust and cybersecure AI Systems</i>

Table 4. Examples about the nature of responsibilities of developers and deployers of AI-system in the EU AIA⁵¹

Although there are future steps in the EU AI Act that can generate ambiguity, including precise standards and guidelines across the different sectors and fields of knowledge, the EU AIA highlights that standardization should play a key role in providing technical solutions to providers to ensure compliance with the Regulation. For example, in the case of high-risk AI medical imaging systems like those that contribute to diagnosing a disease or to defining clinical pathways, the EU AI ACT assumes that the AI system will attain compliance with the

⁵¹ Gilbert, S. The EU passes the AI Act and its implications for digital medicine are unclear. npj Digit. Med. 7, 135 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-024-01116-6>

requirements when it is in conformity with relevant harmonized standards, (Article 40). In case harmonized standards do not exist or are insufficient, the European Commission may adopt common specifications, per Article 41, conformity with which also leads to a presumption of compliance. In section 2.3 of this document, we presented the main initiatives of EU and non-EU Standardizations Organizations in the field of Artificial Intelligence. The European Commission is looking to obtain standards that provide “procedures and processes for the development of Highly risk AI systems.

The next section of this document intends to address the lack of standards in the field of medical imaging and Artificial intelligence. We have accomplished a thorough analysis of scientific literature to define a group of guidelines that must be taken into account during the development of a medical imaging AI system. These guidelines are presented as a sandbox to facilitate the development of new technologies across Europe.

Although our sandbox of guidelines includes very specific tools and steps for developing high-risk AI medical imaging systems, several guidelines like trustworthiness, fairness, or robustness can also be extended to other fields of digital health.

5.3 Standardization Phases to foster AI in Health Imaging

There is a tremendous R&D effort and massive budget for the development of AI systems across Europe. Health is one of the fields of knowledge attracting more interest and the application of AI algorithms to the analysis and automatic interpretation of medical imaging is probably the first field of application of AI. However, the translation of a new AI solutions to clinical reality requires consistent guidelines and development recommendations as well as rigorous evaluations of these algorithms. During the assessment of an algorithm, particularly for high-risk applications such as medical AI systems, its performance must be carefully evaluated with standardized metrics to measure its effectiveness. However, performance alone is not enough to ensure that the algorithm is suitable for clinical practice use. Algorithm security, fairness or robustness are critical to ensure algorithms perform reliably and do not introduce bias. The impact on the clinical workflow is also essential as the algorithm should integrate smoothly into the existing processes.

The analysis carried out in this study demonstrated an insufficient level of standardization for the development, evaluation, and implantation of AI systems in the medical field. The evidence found may have multiple adverse consequences, including reducing the credibility of research

findings, misdirection of future research, and, most importantly, yielding tools that cannot be integrated into the clinical practice.

The systematic review of more than 8.400 publications ended with a collection of papers (restricted to 127 scientific publications). In the 127 scientific publications collection, we found information, guidelines, checklists and projects related to the 3 phases of any project related to the development of a new AI medical imaging system:

Figure 11. Phases of development of a medical Imaging AI system

Our systematic review and the additional searches in the documentation of technical committees and major initiatives in the field of medical imaging clearly show that there is a lack of standards in the field of AI applied to medical imaging. It also served to identify projects, methodological recommendations, and tools and checklists that may contribute to the robust development and future compliance of any medical imaging AI system with the forthcoming regulations, not only in Europe but also in other regions and countries.

The first phase of development involves the R&D phase for designing an AI medical imaging system. The process has strong similarities with other R&D projects dealing with patient data, hospital protocols or healthcare interoperability.

The clinical trials industry has been a major factor in this. A search on ClinicalTrials.gov⁵² using the term 'artificial intelligence' returns 1,868 trials, 929 of which are looking for participants. Most of these AI projects have shown promising results and are starting to interact with patients. The potential impact of these technologies is huge, and experts in the field have

⁵² <https://clinicaltrials.gov/search?term=Artificial%20Intelligence> Accessed on April 2nd, 2024

proposed guidelines and recommendations to ensure that these projects are well-designed and ready to interact with patients and ultimately be used in real clinical scenarios.

A significant number of impactful R&D projects and methodologies found in our study are part of the **EQUATOR Network**, (EQUATOR: Enhancing the QUALity and Transparency Of health Research), which was formed by renowned scientists to collect credible guidelines to promote new health technologies. A quick search of the EQUATOR database⁵³ reveals at least 17 guidelines related to the development of research on AI applied to health (not always related to health imaging AI algorithms). Some of the most attractive projects are listed here:

- **TRIPOD**: This guideline is recommended for reporting of systematic reviews and meta-analyses of multivariable prediction models for individual prognosis or diagnosis. Although TRIPOD can be either used for prognosis and diagnosis, it seems more appropriate for prognostic studies. TRIPOD was mentioned in 6 documents of our collection study.^{54,55,56,57,58,59}
- **SPIRIT-AI Extension**: Reporting guidelines for clinical trial protocols evaluating interventions with an artificial intelligence (AI) component. Similarly, the SPIRIT-AI extension methodology was mentioned in 6 documents of our collection study.^{60, 61}

⁵³ https://www.equator-network.org/?post_type=eq_guidelines&eq_guidelines_study_design=artificial-intelligence-machine-learning-studies&eq_guidelines_clinical_specialty=0&eq_guidelines_report_section=0&s= Accessed on April 2nd, 2024

⁵⁴ Omoumi, P., Ducarouge, A., Tournier, A., Harvey, H., Kahn, C. E., Louvet-de Verchère, F., Pinto Dos Santos, D., Kober, T., & Richiardi, J. (2021, March 5). To buy or not to buy—evaluating commercial AI solutions in radiology (the ECLAIR guidelines). *European Radiology*, 31(6), 3786–3796. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00330-020-07684-x>.

⁵⁵ Mateen, B. A., Liley, J., Denniston, A. K., Holmes, C. C., & Vollmer, S. J. (2020, October 2). Improving the quality of machine learning in health applications and clinical research. *Nature Machine Intelligence*, 2(10), 554–556. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42256-020-00239-1>

⁵⁶ Kocak, B., Akinci D'Antonoli, T., Ates Kus, E., Keles, A., Kala, A., Kose, F., Kadioglu, M., Solak, S., Sunman, S., & Temiz, Z. H. (2024, January 5). Self-reported checklists and quality scoring tools in radiomics: a meta-research. *European Radiology*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00330-023-10487-5>

⁵⁷ Crigger, E., Reinbold, K., Hanson, C., Kao, A., Blake, K., & Irons, M. (2022, January 12). Trustworthy Augmented Intelligence in Health Care. *Journal of Medical Systems*, 46(2). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10916-021-01790-z>

⁵⁸ Kocak et al (2024, January 17). METHodological RadiomiCs Score (METRICS): a quality scoring tool for radiomics research endorsed by EuSoMII. *Insights Into Imaging*, 15(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13244-023-01572-w>

⁵⁹ Cruz Rivera et al(2020, September). Guidelines for clinical trial protocols for interventions involving artificial intelligence: the SPIRIT-AI extension. *Nature Medicine*, 26(9), 1351–1363. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-020-1037-7>

⁶⁰ Weikert, T., Francone, M., Abbara, S., Baessler, B., Choi, B. W., Gutberlet, M., Hecht, E. M., Loewe, C., Mousseaux, E., Natale, L., Nikolaou, K., Ordovas, K. G., Peebles, C., Prieto, C., Salgado, R., Velthuis, B., Vliegthart, R., Bremerich, J., & Leiner, T. (2020, November 19). Machine learning in cardiovascular radiology: ESCR position statement on design requirements, quality assessment, current applications, opportunities, and challenges. *European Radiology*, 31(6), 3909–3922. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00330-020-07417-0>

⁶¹ Rajpurkar, P., Chen, E., Banerjee, O., & Topol, E. J. (2022, January). AI in health and medicine. *Nature Medicine*, 28(1), 31–38. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-021-01614-0>

- **CLAIM:** Perhaps the most interesting, because it provides guidelines for reporting artificial intelligence (AI) in Medical Imaging studies and referred to in 5 research papers of our collection of works.⁶²
- **CONSORT AI:** recommendations for clinical trial reports evaluating interventions with an AI component. It incorporates instructions and skills required for use, handling of the input/output data of the AI algorithm, the human-AI interaction and results of any error case analyses.
- **STARD:** It refers to Guidelines for diagnostic accuracy studies to the Standards for Reporting of Diagnostic Accuracy Studies. Diagnostics Accuracy studies are critical in medical imaging research. These guidelines are important for the execution of R&D projects in the area of AI applied to medical imaging
- **CLEAR;** These guidelines are not included in EQUATOR. They are oriented to radiomics and initially conceived for supporting authors and reviewers in the evaluation of research works, but with interesting guidelines to design an appropriate R&D project.⁶³

All these guidelines help us to standardize the R&D process for the adequate development of AI systems. In Figure 10 we present a representation of its utility, inspired by the work of Vasey et al.⁶⁴

Figure 12. Phases of AI systems development and evaluations tools

⁶² A) Mongan J, Moy L, Kahn CE Jr. Checklist for Artificial Intelligence in Medical Imaging (CLAIM): A Guide for Authors and Reviewers. *Radiol Artif Intell.* 2020 Mar 25;2(2):e200029. doi: 10.1148/ryai.2020200029. B) Tejani AS, Klontzas ME, Gatti AA, Mongan JT, Moy L, Park SH, Kahn CE Jr; CLAIM 2024 Update Panel. Checklist for Artificial Intelligence in Medical Imaging (CLAIM): 2024 Update. *Radiol Artif Intell.* 2024 Jul;6(4):e240300. doi: 10.1148/ryai.240300.

⁶³ Kocak, B., Baessler, B., Bakas, S., Cuocolo, R., Fedorov, A., Maier-Hein, L., Mercaldo, N., Müller, H., Orlhac, F., Pinto dos Santos, D., Stanzione, A., Ugga, L., & Zwanenburg, A. (2023, May 4). CheckList for EvaluAtion of Radiomics research (CLEAR): a step-by-step reporting guideline for authors and reviewers endorsed by ESR and EuSoMI. *Insights Into Imaging*, 14(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13244-023-01415-8>

⁶⁴ Vasey, B., Nagendran, M., Campbell, B., Clifton, D. A., Collins, G. S., Denaxas, S., Denniston, A. K., Faes, L., Geerts, B., Ibrahim, M., Liu, X., Mateen, B. A., Mathur, P., McCradden, M. D., Morgan, L., Ordish, J., Rogers, C., Saria, S., Ting, D. S. W., McCulloch, P. (2022, May 18). Reporting guideline for the early stage clinical evaluation of decision support systems driven by artificial intelligence: DECIDE-AI. *BMJ*, e070904. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj-2022-070904>

5.4 CHAIMELEON Sandbox of Guidelines for Standardization of medical Imaging AI systems

The first guidelines (GD) refer to the standardization process for the design or definition of a Medical Imaging AI system. This includes a set of 7 guidelines (from GD1 to GD7). Some of these recommendations have been addressed by the **CLAIM Tool**.⁶² The CLAIM Tool guidelines were published in 2021 with the support of the RSNA and are inspired by the STARD guidelines already mentioned in this document. These guidelines should be considered as a checklist of “best practices” to guide the presentation of their research.

GD1 about **Study design**. It includes recommendations for assessing the appropriateness of prospective or retrospective studies and defining the appropriate study objective, such as modelling, exploratory study, feasibility study, non-inferiority trial, etc

GD2 about **Data Management**: This section includes guidelines to evaluate the methodology to handle data during the implementation of the R&D Phase:

- Data sources
- Data Eligibility criteria: how, where, and when potentially eligible participants or studies were identified (eg, symptoms, results from previous tests, inclusion in registry, patient-care setting, location, dates)
- Data pre-processing steps
- Methodology for the selection of data subsets, if applicable
- Definitions of data elements, with references to common data elements
- De-identification methods proposed during the R&D activity
- And how missing data were handled

GD3 about **the Ground Truth** that justifies the development of the AI model. It requires both clinical and technical expertise, anticipating issues such as how to extract data from hospital information systems, how to annotate data, how to anticipate discrepancies, and how and by how many experts the ground truth should be established, etc. Important aspects are here:

- Definition of ground truth reference standard, in sufficient detail to allow replication.
- Rational explanation for choosing the reference standard (if alternatives exist)
- Source of ground truth annotations; qualifications and preparation of annotators
- Annotation tools
- Measurement of inter and intra-rater variability; methods to mitigate variability and/or resolve discrepancies.

GD4 on data partitions. It provides a list of recommendations for determining the size of the dataset used to develop the AI model. In this guideline (GD4) the researcher needs to address the following aspects:

- The intended sample size and how it was determined.
- How data have been allocated to partitions; specify proportions
- The level at which the partitions are disjoint (e.g., image, study, patient, institution).

GD5 on the AI model. This GD is designed to provide as much information as possible about the complete model to adequately explain the model to another investigator or clinician. These are the aspects that need to be considered:

- Detailed description of the model, including inputs, outputs, intermediate layers and connections
- Description of software libraries, frameworks, and packages
- Initialisation of model parameters (e.g. randomisation, transfer learning, etc).

GD6 on how the model is trained. This section includes recommendations on:

- Details of the training approach, including data augmentation, hyperparameters, and number of models trained.
- Method used to select the final model.
- Assembly techniques, if applicable.

GD7 on how the model might be evaluated. These guidelines should anticipate the researcher's strategy for evaluating the AI model. An appropriate R&D strategy describes:

- Proposed metrics of model performance.
- Statistical measures of significance and uncertainty (e.g. confidence intervals)
- Robustness or sensitivity analysis.
- Methods of explainability or interpretability (e.g. saliency maps) and how they have been validated.
- Capacity of the model to be validated or tested on external data.

Although 35 of our collection of 127 scientific papers include arguments related to the technical Evaluation of AI systems in the field of medical imaging, fewer efforts have focused on recommendations that address the key issues to consider when evaluating AI solutions. The 127 collection of papers includes some inspiring works from relevant clinical areas like ophthalmology,⁶⁵ neurology (**OCAR-IB**)^{66[OBJ]} Cancer (**PATH ML**)^{67[OBJ]} Nuclear Medicine (**RELIANCE**),⁶⁸ or cardiology,^{69,70} but the approach is not 100% transferable to medical imaging in general. A significant number of these papers propose technical validations of the AI models, which are inherently linked to metrics of a particular disease.

Our collection of 127 scientific papers also includes research publications that provide guidance on some key aspects of a thorough technical validation of an AI system. The collection includes interesting works to address the explainability⁷¹ of the AI Model or publications with excellent recommendations to address ethical⁷² and trustworthy⁷³ aspects of the proposed AI system. Although these documents are interesting, in our opinion they are not

⁶⁵ Sampson, D. M., Dubis, A. M., Chen, F. K., Zawadzki, R. J., & Sampson, D. D. (2022, March 18). Towards standardizing retinal optical coherence tomography angiography: a review. *Light: Science & Applications*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41377-022-00740-9>

⁶⁶ Petzold, A., Albrecht, P., Balcer, L., Bekkers, E., Brandt, A. U., Calabresi, P. A., Deborah, O. G., Graves, J. S., Green, A., Keane, P. A., Nij Bijvank, J. A., Sander, J. W., Paul, F., Saidha, S., Villoslada, P., Wagner, S. K., & Yeh, E. A. (2021, May 19). Artificial intelligence extension of the OSCAR-IB criteria. *Annals of Clinical and Translational Neurology*, 8(7), 1528–1542. <https://doi.org/10.1002/acn3.51320>

⁶⁷ Rosenthal, J., Carelli, R., Omar, M., Brundage, D., Halbert, E., Nyman, J., Hari, S. N., Van Allen, E. M., Marchionni, L., Umeton, R., & Loda, M. (2021, December 8). Building Tools for Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence in Cancer Research: Best Practices and a Case Study with the PathML Toolkit for Computational Pathology. *Molecular Cancer Research*, 20(2), 202–206. <https://doi.org/10.1158/1541-7786.mcr-21-0665>

⁶⁸ Jha, A. K., Bradshaw, T. J., Buvat, I., Hatt, M., KC, P., Liu, C., Obuchowski, N. F., Saboury, B., Slomka, P. J., Sunderland, J. J., Wahl, R. L., Yu, Z., Zuehlsdorff, S., Rahmim, A., & Boellaard, R. (2022, May 26). Nuclear Medicine and Artificial Intelligence: Best Practices for Evaluation (the RELAINCE Guidelines). *Journal of Nuclear Medicine*, 63(9), 1288–1299. <https://doi.org/10.2967/jnumed.121.263239>

⁶⁹ Weikert, T., Francone, M., Abbara, S., Baessler, B., Choi, B. W., Gutberlet, M., Hecht, E. M., Loewe, C., Mousseaux, E., Natale, L., Nikolaou, K., Ordovas, K. G., Peebles, C., Prieto, C., Salgado, R., Velthuis, B., Vliegthart, R., Bremerich, J., & Leiner, T. (2020, November 19). Machine learning in cardiovascular radiology: ESCR position statement on design requirements, quality assessment, current applications, opportunities, and challenges. *European Radiology*, 31(6), 3909–3922. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00330-020-07417-0>

⁷⁰ Weikert, T., Francone, M., Abbara, S., Baessler, B., Choi, B. W., Gutberlet, M., Hecht, E. M., Loewe, C., Mousseaux, E., Natale, L., Nikolaou, K., Ordovas, K. G., Peebles, C., Prieto, C., Salgado, R., Velthuis, B., Vliegthart, R., Bremerich, J., & Leiner, T. (2020, November 19). Machine learning in cardiovascular radiology: ESCR position statement on design requirements, quality assessment, current applications, opportunities, and challenges. *European Radiology*, 31(6), 3909–3922. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00330-020-07417-0>

⁷¹ Jin, W., Li, X., Fatehi, M., & Hamarneh, G. (2023, February). Guidelines and evaluation of clinical explainable AI in medical image analysis. *Medical Image Analysis*, 84, 102684. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.media.2022.102684>

⁷² Buruk, B., Ekmekci, P. E., & Arda, B. (2020, March 31). A critical perspective on guidelines for responsible and trustworthy artificial intelligence. *Medicine, Health Care and Philosophy*, 23(3), 387–399. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11019-020-09948-1>

⁷³ Thiebes, S., Lins, S., & Sunyaev, A. (2020, October 1). Trustworthy artificial intelligence. *Electronic Markets*, 31(2), 447–464. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12525-020-00441-4>

sufficient for the implementation of a practical standardised protocol for the evaluation of AI in medical imaging in general.

In this document, we present a flexible and scalable sandbox of guidelines to guide the development of AI systems applied to medical imaging, covering several diseases and almost all technical aspects and requirements that should be considered to achieve a positive conformity assessment in the EU AIA.

Some of our recommendations may not apply to every situation, we intend to provide a technical evaluation framework to analyse critical aspects of the AI system under assessment. Under these premises we have worked on 5 additional guidelines (from GD8 to GD12) inspired by the research papers of Tanguay et al;⁷⁴ the **ECLAIR** guidelines⁷⁵ (created to provide a list of practical points to address when considering whether to invest in an AI solution in medical imaging), the **RADAR** framework⁷⁶, (created to provide a comprehensive value assessment methodology of artificial intelligence (AI) in radiology) and the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI published in April 2019 by the **high-level expert group on Artificial Intelligence** set up by the European Commission.⁷⁷

Finally, the list of guidelines found in the thorough analysis of these documents was compared with the **FUTURE AI**⁷⁸ Guidelines, a recent initiative that contains valuable recommendations for facilitating translation towards clinical practice of medical AI systems. Based on the analysis of all these publications we propose the following Guidelines (GD8 to GD 12) for the technical Assessment of AI systems in Medical Imaging

GD8 on the technical performance of AI systems. This is perhaps the most complex guideline because AI in medical imaging is a broad field. The development of AI systems in medical imaging involves several use cases, data acquisition technologies, and data

⁷⁴ Tanguay, W., Acar, P., Fine, B., Abdoell, M., Gong, B., Cadrin-Chênevert, A., Chartrand-Lefebvre, C., Chalaoui, J., Gorgos, A., Chin, A. S. L., Prénovault, J., Guilbert, F., Létourneau-Guillon, L., Chong, J., & Tang, A. (2022, November 6). Assessment of Radiology Artificial Intelligence Software: A Validation and Evaluation Framework. *Canadian Association of Radiologists Journal*, 74(2), 326–333. <https://doi.org/10.1177/08465371221135760>.

⁷⁵ Omoumi, P., Ducarouge, A., Tournier, A., Harvey, H., Kahn, C. E., Louvet-de Verchère, F., Pinto Dos Santos, D., Kober, T., & Richiardi, J. (2021, March 5). To buy or not to buy—evaluating commercial AI solutions in radiology (the ECLAIR guidelines). *European Radiology*, 31(6), 3786–3796. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00330-020-07684-x>

⁷⁶ Boverhof, B. J., Redekop, W. K., Bos, D., Starmans, M. P. A., Birch, J., Rockall, A., & Visser, J. J. (2024, February 5). Radiology AI Deployment and Assessment Rubric (RADAR) to bring value-based AI into radiological practice. *Insights Into Imaging*, 15(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13244-023-01599-z>

⁷⁷ HLEGAI. (8 April 2019). High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, EU - Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI. <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>. <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>.

⁷⁸ Lekadir, K., "FUTURE-AI: International consensus guideline for trustworthy and deployable artificial intelligence in healthcare", <i>arXiv e-prints</i>, 2023. doi:10.48550/arXiv.2309.12325.

processing tools, which together probably provide the largest amount of information of AI systems in healthcare with a great variety of applications, such as cancer diagnosis, disease prediction or image harmonisation, among others. Tanguay⁷⁴ et al proposed an inspiring work with several technical performance metrics depending on the use case under analysis. This is presented in the table 5 and it will be developed in further detail in section 6: **GD8 on the technical performance of AI systems**. This is perhaps the most complex guideline because AI in medical imaging is a broad field. The development of AI systems in medical imaging involves several use cases, data acquisition technologies, and data processing tools, which together probably provide the largest amount of information of AI systems in healthcare with a great variety of applications, such as cancer diagnosis, disease prediction or image harmonisation, among others. Tanguay⁷⁴ et al proposed an inspiring work with several technical performance metrics depending on the use case under analysis. This is presented in the table 5 and it will be developed in further detail in section 6:

Detection	Triage	Radiomics	Segmentation	Augmentation	Classification	Prediction
Free-recall receiver operating (ROC) curve					Area under the ROC curve	Area under ROC curve
Sensitivity	Sensitivity					
Specificity	Specificity					
cost of error		cost of error				
Intersection over union (IOU)			Intersection over union (IOU)			
Mean average precision (mAP)				∞		
F1 Score						
	Impact on workflow					
		Accuracy			Accuracy	Accuracy
		Added value patient management				
			Dice index	Dice index		

Table 5. Examples of technical evaluation metrics for Medical Imaging AI systems

GD 9 on Accuracy: Accuracy refers to the ability of an AI system to make correct judgments, for example to correctly classify information into the proper categories, or its ability to make correct predictions, recommendations, or decisions based on data or models. Although Tanguay et al⁷⁴ considered the importance of Accuracy in just projects of Radiomics,

Classification and Prediction, we must consider that Accuracy should be also extended to other use cases such as the detection of certain objects in the image or the ability to segmentate specific regions of interest in medical imaging with high-level of precision.

GD10 on Reliability: Similarly to the previous GD, Tanguay et al⁷⁴ considered that Reliability is perhaps more adequate for projects related to segmentation or augmentation of certain regions of the image. However, if we consider that a reliable AI system is an AI model that works properly with a range of inputs and in a range of situations, we can also talk about reliable medical imaging AI systems related to detection, triage, radiomics, or prediction.

GD 11 on Reproducibility: This Guideline aims to describe the ability of an AI system to exhibit the same performance when repeated under the same conditions in different projects, datasets, etc. It is a critical guideline to ensure the deployment of the medical imaging AI system under development at a large scale.

GD 12 on Robustness: Cybersecurity is becoming a major concern for healthcare organisations, and this guideline has become increasingly important in recent years. A robust AI system should be able to withstand external attacks. In particular, a robust AI system should not have vulnerabilities that allow the AI model to be hacked (model leakage) (e.g. a change in the model can cause false positives in cancer diagnosis), with serious consequences for patients (e.g. inadequate treatment of poorer health outcomes) and healthcare systems (e.g. operational disruptions, loss of trust).

Finally, the CHAIMELEON sandbox also includes several Guidelines more related to the potential impact of the AI system. The impact involves data privacy, ethical considerations, and other important aspects like interoperability and environmental implications.

GD 13 on Data Protection & Privacy: It could be part of GD12, but it is important to highlight the importance of Data protection & Privacy to ensure compliance with the new AI regulations. It is necessary to standardise the assessment of the privacy and data protection of the algorithm, to ensure that the processing steps of the medical imaging AI system ensure privacy and data protection throughout the lifecycle of the system under development. This means that the AI system must comply with the GDPR rules, EU AIA and similar directives in this regard. For example, a medical imaging AI system for lung cancer detection must guarantee the privacy of the information initially provided about the patient in the image, as well as the information generated in the course of their interaction with the system (the diagnosis/result).

GD14 on Traceability: This guideline refers to the capacity of the AI system to track the users handling the data and under what circumstances they are processing the data. The Traceability capacities of the system to document the decisions made by the AI system during its operations and any changes or modifications (e.g. a new segmentation object) in the original medical image.

G15 on Explainability: This is “a must” guideline in any modern AI system. It refers to the need for explainability methods to provide sufficient information to justify the AI model and its results, and to allow users to understand the results generated by AI systems. Explainability may also include aspects of interpretability. Although Explainable AI (XAI) has become an attractive area of research, there are no standardised protocols in the field of medical

	Co-12 Property	Description	
Content	Correctness	Describes how faithful the explanation is w.r.t. the black box. Key idea: Nothing but the truth	
	Completeness	Describes how much of the black box behavior is described in the explanation. Key idea: The whole truth	
	Consistency	Describes how deterministic and implementation-invariant the explanation method is. Key idea: Identical inputs should have identical explanations	
	Continuity	Describes how continuous and generalizable the explanation function is. Key idea: Similar inputs should have similar explanations	
	Contrastivity	Describes how discriminative the explanation is w.r.t. other events or targets. Key idea: Answers “why not?” or “what if?” questions	
	Covariate complexity	Describes how complex the (interactions of) features in the explanation are. Key idea: Human-understandable concepts in the explanation	
	Presentation	Compactness	Describes the size of the explanation. Key idea: Less is more
		Composition	Describes the presentation format and organization of the explanation. Key idea: How something is explained
		Confidence	Describes the presence and accuracy of probability information in the explanation. Key idea: Confidence measure of the explanation or model output
User	Context	Describes how relevant the explanation is to the user and their needs. Key idea: How much does the explanation matter in practice?	
	Coherence	Describes how accordant the explanation is with prior knowledge and beliefs. Key idea: Plausibility or reasonableness to users	
	Controllability	Describes how interactive or controllable an explanation is for a user. Key idea: Can the user influence the explanation?	

imaging. Table 6. Explanation Quality Properties from Nauta et al

An interesting review of XAI applied to medical imaging by Borys et al⁷⁹ suggests the recent methodology of Nauta et al.⁸⁰ In this work, Nauta proposed a quantitative evaluation of XAI methods using 12 conceptual aspects that can serve as a categorisation scheme for reviewing the evaluation practice.

GD16 on Fairness: Modern AI systems in medical imaging need to enable inclusion and diversity throughout the life cycle of the AI system. Fairness is always important when developing a solution that involves significant tasks that require the involvement of human data. This is a common situation for AI systems in medical imaging. The patients evaluated by an AI system are entitled to equal rights and should be treated impartially, regardless of race, age, gender, language, nationality or birth. Addressing the issue of fairness in the AI model, training datasets, visualisation of results, etc. is critical to ensuring that these AI systems can be relied upon for decision making. Addressing fairness in medical imaging AI systems involves several challenges, including the need for high-quality, diverse datasets and the development of robust fairness metrics. It also presents opportunities for innovation.

GD17 on interoperability and Integration. This guideline is usually hidden in other broad concepts like clinical output, and usability of data access.⁸¹ In this document, we believe that interoperability is a critical aspect of whatever medical imaging AI system. In this Guideline we intend to promote AI systems that can handle the frequent databases in hospitals (usually in formats like DICOM⁸² or OMOP⁸³) as well as the capacity of the system to integrate the results into the existing infrastructure of hospitals and their clinical workflows. This includes ensuring compatibility with PACS (Picture Archiving and Communication Systems) and EHRs (Electronic Health Records), among other basic things. In this Guideline it is very important to

⁷⁹ Borys, K., Schmitt, Y. A., Nauta, M., Seifert, C., Krämer, N., Friedrich, C. M., & Nensa, F. (2023, May). Explainable AI in medical imaging: An overview for clinical practitioners – Saliency-based XAI approaches. *European Journal of Radiology*, 162, 110787. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejrad.2023.110787>

⁸⁰ Nauta, M., Trienes, J., Pathak, S., Nguyen, E., Peters, M., Schmitt, Y., Schlötterer, J., van Keulen, M., & Seifert, C. (2023, July 13). From Anecdotal Evidence to Quantitative Evaluation Methods: A Systematic Review on Evaluating Explainable AI. *ACM Computing Surveys*, 55(13s), 1–42. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3583558>

⁸¹ A) Brad Genereaux, Kevin O'Donnell, Harald Zachmann, and the IHE Radiology Community Integrating the Healthcare Enterprise-5 IHE Radiology White Paper. AI Interoperability in Imaging. Revision 1.1 – Published. Date: October 12, 2021. B) Kondylakis, H., Kalokyri, V., Sfakianakis, S. et al. Data infrastructures for AI in medical imaging: a report on the experiences of five EU projects. *Eur Radiol Exp* 7, 20 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41747-023-00336-x>

⁸² Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM). (2008). <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-74571-6>

⁸³ Park, W. Y., Jeon, K., Schmidt, T. S., Kondylakis, H., Alkasab, T., Dewey, B. E., You, S. C., & Nagy, P. (2024, February 5). Development of Medical Imaging Data Standardization for Imaging-Based Observational Research: OMOP Common Data Model Extension. *Journal of Imaging Informatics in Medicine*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10278-024-00982-6>

check the uses of international standards, the existence of API, promote adequate data models as well as the use of standardized vocabularies (e.g., SNOMED-CT, LOINC).

GD18 Green AI. Technological advances in artificial intelligence and its applications are

Figure 13. AI Lifecycle components with environmental impact

increasingly drawing attention to the environmental sustainability of AI systems. This guideline aims to assess or guide AI researchers and developers on the environmental sustainability of AI systems, a field known as Green AI. It aims to broaden the discourse on Green AI by exploring current approaches to environmental assessment and eco-design of AI systems.⁸⁴ This includes, among others, the analysis of the algorithmic model, the training requirements, the data management during the development and execution of the algorithms, the type of hardware needed to run the AI system and its life cycle, etc.

⁸⁴ Clemm, Christian & Stobbe, Lutz & Wimalawarne, Kishan & Druschke, Jan. (2024). Towards Green AI: Current status and future research. 10.48550/arXiv.2407.10237.

6 CHAIMELEON Sandbox of Guidelines

In this section, the proposed guidelines are detailed. For each of the 18 guidelines, a comprehensive definition is provided, including the most relevant information necessary for a thorough understanding, along with the corresponding references. Additionally, the section outlines how CHAIMELEON has contributed to the implementation of each guideline.

6.1 GD1 Study Design

Guideline	GD1 Study Design
Definition	It emphasizes the importance of gathering comprehensive information early in the development of AI medical imaging systems, proposing a strategic "study design" document to ensure thorough documentation and planning throughout the AI project's lifecycle.
Description	
<p>As reported throughout this document, regulations such as the EU Artificial Intelligence Act (AIA) emphasize the importance of gathering comprehensive information during the development process of AI systems, particularly for medical imaging AI systems. Guideline 1 proposes starting with the definition of a strategic document named "study design". Although the level and amount of information about the AI medical imaging system is limited at early stages, it is recommended to gather information as soon as possible, beginning with very strategic and high-level information. GD1 is inspired by the recommendations of the Checklist for Artificial Intelligence in Medical Imaging tool (CLAIM TOOL) [1]. This tool provides recommendations for the design and reporting of clinical studies using AI in healthcare and can be considered a good reference to ensure that the AI medical imaging system gathers comprehensive information from the start of the AI project. For drafting the study design document, a list of chapters is proposed that goes beyond the recommendations of the CLAIM tool (sections 1 to 7 of this guideline). It is suggested to enhance the study design with a short description of the subchapters or items that could be incorporated into each of the 14 sections suggested in this Guideline 1 - Study Design. If the AI developer does not have enough information to complete all sections at the beginning of the study, the missing sections should be completed later through the elaboration of new updates or versions of the Guideline 1 - Study Design document. The GD1 - Study Design document will help AI developers to carefully consider the different aspects and impacts of the AI medical imaging system. It should be considered a live document that can be updated through the different development stages. It can also be used for communication and</p>	

dissemination purposes, describing the vision and understanding of the project at the most critical and influential stage of the AI system's lifecycle, the definition stage. The full list of chapters is presented here. Section 1 – Defining a Title and Abstract: A good title and a precise abstract provide a roadmap for the AI project, helping to define its purpose, communicate its value, and align all stakeholders. This facilitates communication and dissemination during the implementation of the project, ensuring it remains focused, impactful, and well-understood by all involved parties. Section 2 – Provide an Introduction: This section should present the background of the AI project, introducing the clinical and scientific issues addressed by the medical imaging AI system. It is also important to introduce the AI project rationale, goals, and, if possible, anticipate the desired impact on patients, health professionals, and health systems. Summarize related literature and highlight how the investigation builds upon and differs from previous work. Section 3– Outline Objectives, Hypotheses and Ground truth: This chapter should define the clinical or scientific question and specify the AI study's hypothesis a priori. Defining the objectives of the AI medical imaging system is necessary to establish a clear direction and purpose for the project from the early stages of development. It also ensures the identification and processing of future information generated during the various development stages. The hypothesis will guide the research by introducing the most important research questions and potential experimental steps, presented at a high level. Additionally, provide a broad description of the ground truth behind the AI study, identifying and explaining at a high level the verified and validated data that serves as a reference point for the development of the AI medical imaging system. A high-level introduction of the gold standard against which the AI model's predictions will be compared is sufficient at this stage. Section 4 – Outline Data Design strategy: This section should introduce the type of data intended for use in the development of the AI system. This includes a brief analysis of the type of images necessary for the project (e.g., modality, acquisition protocol, contrast-enhanced, images from anatomy pathology, radiology, the technique used, specific series, the disease addressed, the format, etc.). Additionally, presents the strategy of the AI study in relation to the use of retrospective or prospective data, or a combination of both. If sufficient information is available, introduce the data partition strategy. Finally, include a monitoring record-keeping strategy to ensure that all necessary records of the design, development, testing, and deployment stages of the AI medical imaging system are gathered. Section 5 – introduce the AI Model strategy: Section 5 – introduce the AI Model strategy: This section should outline the plans for the development, training, and evaluation of the AI system. A general description of these three

stages will help to understand future steps of the development process. The model of the algorithm or the proposed AI components (software libraries, intermediate layers, statistical methodology for evaluation, etc.) may vary during the execution of this strategy. However, following the recommendations of critical documents like the EU AIA, it is important to gather credible, extensive documentation throughout the AI system's lifecycle, including potential changes in the development, training, or testing phases.

Section 6 – Anticipate the Performance Metrics: As introduced in section 6.4 of this document, defining performance metrics in AI projects within the medical imaging field presents several challenges due to the variability of use cases. Different AI medical imaging use cases require different metrics. This guideline proposes anticipating the group of performance metrics that will be required to assess the AI medical imaging system based on the specific clinical application and the nature of the data. Provide a short description to anticipate the metrics to be used and, if possible, the formula or calculation method. To maintain coherence with other guidelines included in the CHAIMELEON sandbox, follow the recommendations of Tanguay et al.[\[2\]](#), which are explained in more detail in Guideline 8.

Section 7 – Explain Transparency and Reproducibility: Transparency and reproducibility of AI medical imaging systems are vital for building trust, ensuring accountability, mitigating risks, and supporting ethical development. They also play a central role in new regulations like the EU AIA Act, which aims to create reliable and transparent frameworks for AI technologies in Europe. Study Design intends to explain the overall strategy of the project in relation to transparency, reproducibility and other dimensions of the project. These items are addressed in more detail in other guidelines of the CHAIMELEON sandbox. By addressing transparency at early stages, AI developers should demonstrate their commitment to total accountability and their ability to provide sufficient information to any notification body, client, or user that may require details of the AI medical imaging system. Additionally, in Guideline 1, it is recommendable to introduce high level concepts such as the system's model architecture or the strategy to maintain and access the code used to develop and train the AI model, and to gather and maintain comprehensive documentation for the acquisition of performance metrics, resources, and plans to reproduce the studies, as well as the ability to track changes in the code and data.

Section 8 – Address the ethical implications: Guideline 1 suggests an introduction to anticipate the strategy of the AI development team to address important ethical aspects of the AI medical imaging system. At early stages, inform about the potential groups of patients that will be part of the study, avoiding minority groups or unjustified exclusions based on age, race, or gender. If possible, present the regulations and legal frameworks related to the

AI medical imaging system (e.g., EU AIA, MDR, NIS2 directive) and provide a short introduction about data privacy or anonymization approaches. Section 9 – Explain the Clinical Integration: As part of Guideline 1 - Study Design, introduces how the AI medical imaging system will be integrated into clinical workflows and its potential impact on patient care. If possible, explain how the AI system will interact with different stages of the patient journey to enhance, rather than disrupt, patient management workflow. Include a short stakeholder involvement analysis to identify the different users that could be affected by the implementation of the AI system into clinical practice (e.g., doctors, nurses, IT staff, patients). Section 10 – Explain the Interoperability strategy of the AI system: Although the CHAIMELEON Sandbox includes a specific guideline about interoperability (GD 17), include an introduction to define the strategy of the AI development team in relation to integrating the AI medical imaging system with the existing IT infrastructure of healthcare organizations. Consider a broad implementation of the system (in many hospitals and across different countries) by ensuring compatibility with a wide range of PACS, EHRs, etc. Encourage the use of standards (e.g., DICOM, HL7, OMOP) and APIs, etc. Section 11 – Start to think about the Green AI implications: Similarly to the previous section, the CHAIMELEON Sandbox includes GD18 to explain the environmental implications of the AI system under development. Considering the current and future impact of AI systems on CO2 emissions, it is suggested to introduce a chapter in Guideline 1 to address the environmental impact of the AI medical imaging system at the early stages of development. This includes, if possible, an analysis of the AI system lifecycle, the computational infrastructure that will be used, requirements of the AI model during the development, training, and execution stages, as well as the hardware requirements to appropriately run the algorithm. If AI developers can provide or intend to provide any system or metrics to analyse the carbon footprint, these should also be introduced in Section 11 of Guideline 1. Section 12 – Include a Risk Management strategy: During the preparation of Guideline 1 - Study Design, AI developers are encouraged to define a risk management strategy that spans the entire lifecycle of the AI medical imaging system. This involves identifying, analysing, and mitigating potential risks at each stage of development, training, and implementation. Section 13 – Include a continuous Monitoring and Post-Market Surveillance (only for solutions to be integrated into the clinical workflow): The EU AIA requires ongoing monitoring of AI systems even after deployment. This includes collecting and analysing performance data to identify and address any emerging risks or issues throughout the lifecycle of the AI medical imaging system. The AI developer should include in Guideline 1 - Study Design a strategy to gather continuous

feedback from users (both clinical and non-clinical), establish clear KPIs to continuously monitor the AI system, and, if possible, define the involvement of the Quality Management team of the organization developing the AI system to ensure consistent processes for data collection, analysis, and reporting during the AI system lifecycle. Section 14 – Include Other Information: Finally, as part of Guideline 1 - Study Design, it is suggested to include a section for other relevant information not covered in the previous sections. This could include information about: (a) Funding and support (b) Acknowledgements and identification of team members and stakeholders who will participate in different stages of development, which can be important for intellectual property issues (c) Identification of potential conflicts of interest. (d) Any communication or dissemination plan's information (e) Information on planned follow-up studies or future research directions of the AI system, which can have future implications on intellectual property strategies.

Finally, we propose that GD 1 as the first document of a complete file about the development, implementation and post-monitoring of the AI system. Like other documentation generated during the implementation of the CHAIMELEON Sandbox, we suggest defining a centralized and adequate storage location and clear document access control policies to restrict who can view, edit, and delete documents generated during the application of the CHAIMELEON SANDBOX. We also suggest the implementation of regular backups and clear naming protocols to identify file names and versions of the different documents related to the AI system and including the Guideline 1 -study Design.

CHAIMELEON Contributions

The CHAIMELEON project has published an interesting scientific publication presenting the overall strategy of the CHAIMELEON project [3]. The publication can serve as a source of inspiration to address some of the chapters recommended in the guideline description. For example, the paper presents the overall architecture and main components of the repository. It also explains the strategy for populating the repository and outlines the data strategy. Another critical aspect is related to the interoperability strategy and the expected experiments to validate the repository with internal and external users.

The CHAIMELEON Project, as part of the AI4HI initiative, contributed to the creation of the FUTURE-AI guide (Fairness, Universality, Traceability, Usability, Robustness, Explainability), which offer a comprehensive framework that addresses various key aspects for the design of AI medical imaging systems (add reference here). These aspects are further detailed in GD14, GD12, GD15 and GD16.

Among the specific recommendations in the FUTURE-AI guide is the early identification of potential sources of bias, allowing researchers to anticipate and properly address any undue influence on results. The guide also emphasizes the importance of collecting detailed information about the attributes of the data and individuals involved in the study, contributing to a more accurate and comprehensive evaluation of the results obtained. Another key aspect is the implementation of a risk management process throughout the AI lifecycle. This involves proactively analysing and mitigating any potential risks associated with the development, validation, implementation, and use of AI in biomedical and clinical research. Furthermore, the FUTURE-AI guide recommends clearly defining the intended clinical environments and variations between them, which facilitates the adaptation and generalization of results in different contexts. It stresses the importance of using standards established by the community to ensure the quality and interoperability of research, as well as evaluating the intended use and user requirements from an early stage.

Finally, the guide highlights the importance of providing training materials and activities for end users, which helps improve the understanding and effectiveness of AI in its real-world application. Together, these recommendations provide a comprehensive and structured approach to address the design of AI medical imaging systems. In addition to these specific recommendations, the FUTURE-AI guide also establishes six general recommendations that apply to all principles of trustworthy AI in healthcare.

- Engage stakeholders continuously: Throughout the lifecycle of the AI tool, developers should interact regularly with interdisciplinary stakeholders, such as healthcare professionals, citizens, patient representatives, ethics experts, data managers, and legal experts. This interaction will facilitate understanding and anticipation of needs, obstacles, and paths toward acceptance and adoption.
- Ensure data protection: Adequate measures must be implemented to ensure privacy and data security throughout the AI lifecycle. This may include privacy-enhancing techniques, data protection impact assessments, and proper data governance post-implementation.
- Define an appropriate evaluation plan: To increase trust and adoption, a proper evaluation plan should be defined, including test data, metrics, and benchmarks.
- Comply with AI regulations: The development team must identify applicable AI regulations and anticipate regulatory obligations based on the classification and projected risks of the medical AI tool.

- Investigate ethical issues: In addition to known ethical issues in medical AI, AI developers, domain specialists, and ethics professionals must identify, discuss, and address all ethical, social, and societal issues specific to the application as an integral part of the development and implementation of the AI tool.
- Investigate social issues: In addition to clinical, technical, legal, and ethical implications, a medical AI tool may have specific social and societal issues that need to be considered and addressed to ensure a positive impact on citizens and society.

These general recommendations complement the specific guidelines of the FUTURE-AI guide, providing a strong and comprehensive framework for the development of AI systems in health imaging.

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6.2 GD2 Data Management

Guideline	GD2 Data Management
Definition	Good practices for data quality and data integration
Description	
<p>Data management is a critical component in the development of AI systems; effective data management ensures that AI systems are developed, validated, and deployed with the highest standards of accuracy, reproducibility, and ethical compliance. In addition, key legislative frameworks such as the Artificial Intelligence Act (AIA), emphasise the importance of robust data management practices to improve the performance, transparency and accountability of AI systems. We have already mentioned that the Checklist for Artificial Intelligence in Medical Imaging (CLAIM) (1) provides key recommendations for data management during the R&D phase of AI systems. It also emphasises the importance of transparency and reproducibility in AI research. These guidelines are designed to address the unique challenges posed by the use of AI in medical imaging, where data quality and integrity have a direct impact on clinical outcomes. The following sections detail the data management steps recommended by the CLAIM tool for handling data during the R&D phase of the project, and can be extended to the entire lifecycle of the AI system.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data sources: Identifying and documenting data sources is the first step in ensuring the reliability and validity of an AI system. Researchers developing AI systems must provide a detailed account of all data sources used, including databases, registries and real-time data streams. This transparency allows for the replication of studies and verification of results, which are essential for advancing the field. • Data eligibility criteria: Establishing clear eligibility criteria for data inclusion is critical to maintaining the integrity of the dataset. It is important to detail how, where and when potentially eligible participants will be recruited for training, testing and validation experiments of the AI system. This includes detailing the symptoms, test results or registry entries that qualify data for inclusion. Such careful documentation ensures that the dataset is representative and relevant to the research objectives. • Data pre-processing Steps: Data pre-processing is a critical step in preparing data for analysis. AI developers must outline all preprocessing steps, including data cleaning, normalisation and transformation steps. This process ensures that the data 	

is in an appropriate format for analysis and that any potential biases or errors are addressed early in the AI system's lifecycle.

- **Methodology for Selection of Data Subsets:** In some cases, it may be necessary to select specific subsets of data for analysis. This is discussed in more detail in GD4 of this document (Data Partitions). It is important to document the criteria and methods used for this selection to ensure that the process is unbiased and representative of the full dataset. This transparency is essential for the reproducibility of the study and the validity of the results.
- **Data element definitions and the data model:** Providing clear definitions for all data elements is essential for consistency and clarity in AI research. It is recommended that reference be made to the common data models proposed for the development of the AI system in order to standardise data and improve consistency, interoperability and comparability across different studies and systems involved in the AI system lifecycle.
- **De-identification methods:** As we have seen in GD9 (Data Protection and Privacy), the protection of patient privacy is a fundamental concern in the development of medical imaging AI systems. Therefore, it is necessary to detail the methods used to de-identify personal data, such as anonymisation or pseudonymisation techniques, and to ensure compliance with data protection regulations such as the GDPR. This is a critical step not only to protect patient privacy, but also to improve ethical standards and strategy from the early stages of AI system development.
- **Dealing with missing data:** Missing data is a common challenge in medical imaging research. AI developers should describe their strategies for handling missing data, including any imputation methods used or criteria for excluding incomplete data. Appropriate handling of missing data is critical to maintaining the integrity and validity of the AI system at all stages of development.

The data management steps recommended in this guideline are compatible with the recommendations of the EU AIA (2) and the FAIR Principles (3), which are more focused on improving the quality and transparency of research data. While these steps provide specific recommendations for data management during the development of the medical imaging AI system, the FAIR Principles provide a broader framework for making data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. Adopting these steps and the FAIR principles is essential to provide a robust foundation for high-quality, reproducible and ethical research to develop high-impact medical imaging AI systems.

Challenges to adopting data management recommendations

The main challenge for implementing appropriate data management policies is primarily related to the commitment and resources of the organisation developing the medical imaging AI system. AI project leaders need to create the environment and provide the tools and team resources to navigate and manage the complex data landscape of healthcare systems, healthcare datasets and healthcare regulatory requirements. It is therefore essential to consider data management at an early stage, to provide the necessary infrastructure and financial resources, to follow the above recommendations and , to count on a skilled team to implement the proposed recommendations.

CHAIMELEON Contributions

The process of identification, collection, curation, anonymization and routing of data to the CHAIMELEON central repository was done through software tools developed and provided by project partner MEDEX. Imaging data preprocessing: Within the user interface of Radiomics Enabler® application, users from the clinical team can select radiological exams from relevant patients based on inclusion and exclusion criteria (data eligibility criteria), these were defined by the clinical partner lead of each cancer type. Relevant imaging exams and series in DICOM format were retrieved from the hospital's PACS in batches, and de-identified through a configurable automated process. A viewer module within the application allowed for quality check of the images of each batch by the user, and controlling the de-identification of any DICOM tag of each series extracted. Once images were validated, they were ready for export. For the projects with clinical data associated with the images, the user had to launch the export to the DICOM node, based on DCM4CHEE, deployed in the CHAIMELEON platform, only once clinical data was also ready for export (see below). For hospitals that did not allow direct connection of Radiomics Enabler® to their PACS, an alternative workflow was set up (see Figure 1) to retrieve the imaging data stored on a DICOM-node repository at the facility. Clinical data preparation: Extraction of a patient's imaging data from the PACS hospital using Radiomics Enabler® triggered the creation of a blank eCRF in the ezCRF® application. The patient was identified using the same code as the one created in Radiomics Enabler at the de-identification stage, to ensure the correspondence between clinical and imaging data. The user from the clinical team was able to then populate each cancer type with clinical data, according to the variables selected by the clinical experts. Two workflows were possible for eCRF completion: manual edition of eCRFs through the web-user interface of ezCRF, or automatic feed. For the latter workflow, users had to complete a spreadsheet template specific to each use case and provide it to

the Medex team, which would in return run an automatic ingestion pipeline, to complete the eCRFs. The status of each eCRF was manually changed in the user interface to created > editing > completed > validated > delivered. Created eCRF corresponded to empty ones, while editing eCRF were the ones with completion in progress. Once all clinical data was included, the eCRF was ready to be changed to “completed” status. Only then, a quality check, both visual and automated, was conducted by Medex team, and if data were missing or incorrect, a query was issued and the status put to “query”. Once all data were correct, the eCRF was in “validated” stage, and ready to be exported.

Before export, Medex applied a date shifting to all dates of the validated cases as follows: (1) The diagnosis date (or imaging date for some cancer types) was selected and (a) the date was shifted to the First of January of the same year (eg: 17/03/2019 became 01/01/2019) (b) When the original date was the 1st of January, the year was replaced by the year before (eg: 01/01/2018 became 01/01/2017) (2) The delta between the original and newly generated data was applied to all other dates from the eCRF and imaging metadata. Applying the date shift to the data unlocked the export. On one hand, Medex launched the export of the clinical data as a dictionary to Quibim Precision via REST API, while the user launched the export of images to CHAIMELEON DICOM node in Radiomics Enabler®. At export, patient ID was further de-identified using a hashing, and once export was complete, the corresponding key for the hash was removed.

Data model: OMOP is the CDM that was initially chosen to 1/ make possible the data comparison across sites, and 2/ be in line with other major European initiatives promoting the secondary use of real-world data, such as EHDEN, in order to achieve sustainability for the CHAIMELEON repository beyond the funding period. It appeared important to integrate data from all sources into a common data model. However, conversion of imported data to OMOP has proven to be a great challenge, at various levels, as it does not always apply to real world data. As an example, in OMOP CDM, dates are mandatory, which is not always compatible with real life cases from the clinics. Because a missing date is not compliant with the OMOP CDM, the information cannot be mapped. Similarly, OMOP CDM cannot interpret information relating to a non-existent object. For example, if clinicians know that a patient has no history of cancer, this cannot be translated into OMOP CDM. In practice, it has been observed when handling the data that the required information from one cancer to another would greatly vary (due to the nature of the clinical data themselves), which implies to deal with each cancer separately. In addition, harmonization of data from various sites appeared more demanding than expected; for example, some non-OMOP information had to be

retained as they remained essential to the project. To mitigate these issues, a hybrid structure was defined, based on the eCRF's structure completed with OMOP information. For all clinical variables that could be mapped to OMOP CDM, the corresponding OMOP information is present in the dictionaries exported to Quibim Precision.

CHAIMELEON Datalake

Imaging exams exported to CHAIMELEON DICOM node were automatically imported in Quibim Precision using MIUC (Medical Imaging Universal Connector), developed by Quibim. DICOM metadata was used to organize the exams properly in CHAIMELEON datalake. The Patient ID was used to identify the case in the database and perform the matching with the corresponding clinical data, while additional private tags, defined between Medex and Quibim, were used to identify the project (i.e., cancer type) to which the exam was associated and the site of origin. The first was used to properly organize the case in the database while the second, based on a code (not the name of the institution itself) was used for tracking purposes (data governance and monitoring).

Dataset creation

Once the data was imported in Quibim Precision, users employed the interface to build datasets/cohorts of cases. Quibim Precision included an environment, based on a case explorer, where the user selected the cases to include in a dataset. Then, the user defined a dataset name and description and created the dataset. For dataset creation, Quibim Precision sent all the information to the dataset service through a REST API (<https://chaimeleon-eu.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/api-doc>). If the creation was successful the user received a link to track the process in the creation, which were accessible in the Dataset Explorer (<https://chaimeleon-eu.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/datasets?invalidated=false>)

Datasets management

Datasets are a key element in CHAIMELEON. They represent a coherent collection (in terms of access permission, collection purpose and clinical relevance) of medical imaging studies and associated clinical data.

A dataset includes an aggregated metadata that describes the collection. Part of this metadata relates to features of the studies (e.g. image modalities) and patients (e.g. maximum, minimum and mean age) and other part relates to descriptions, timestamps, contact points, collection purposes, etc. CHAIMELEON uses the MIABIS schema, although it is being transitioned to HealthDCAT-AP in the context of EUCAIM.

Datasets can go through 4 statuses:

- Draft. This is the initial status. A draft dataset is not yet finalised, and all its properties can be updated (name, version, description, purpose, type, collection method). A draft dataset is only visible and accessible by the user who created it.
- Released. A released dataset becomes available to all the authenticated and authorised users joined to the project. A signature of all the images is created and this information is added to the description. No changes can be applied afterwards in order to guarantee the reproducibility of analysis/training. If the user wants to change or improve it, a new version has to be created.
- Published. When a dataset is published its metadata is automatically deposited publicly in Zenodo.org in order to obtain a DOI. After that, all users registered in the platform (even not joined to the project) can use it if they are added to the ACL (access control list) of the dataset.
- Invalidated. Whenever some problem is detected in any dataset, it can be marked as invalidated, so nobody can use it, nor the user who created it.

A user can access a dataset creating a VRE (virtual research environment), which allows the use of the computational resources to do analysis or model training in the platform. Any use of datasets will be registered by the Tracer Service. That history is based on a blockchain in order to grant it is never modified. More details are given on the traceability guideline (GD14).

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6.3 GD3 Ground Truth

Guideline	GD3 Ground Truth
Definition	Ground truth is the actual, verified data that is used to assess the accuracy of AI models. It represents the "truth" against which predictions made by the model can be compared.
Description	
<p>The establishment of the Ground Truth during the design and development of a medical imaging AI system requires both clinical and technical expertise, anticipating issues such as how to extract data from hospital information systems, how to annotate data, how to anticipate discrepancies and by how many experts the ground truth should be established, etc.</p> <p>Challenges for the definition of Ground Truth:</p> <p>The correct definition of the ground truth in AI medical imaging systems involves several challenges [2]:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Bias and Variability: It's important to ensure the ground truth is unbiased. Bias can arise from data selection, annotator expertise, or the annotation process. Variability can also occur between different annotators (inter-rater variability) or the same annotator over time (intra-rater variability), impacting consistency. ● Standardization: Inconsistent imaging protocols, equipment, and annotation tools can affect the ground truth. Varying systems and protocols across hospitals and clinics make it difficult to establish a uniform ground truth. ● Data Quality and Quantity: Reliable ground truth requires high-quality, annotated data. However, acquiring large amounts of such data is challenging due to privacy issues, regulations, and the time-consuming annotation process. ● Annotator Expertise: The accuracy of the ground truth depends on the annotators' qualifications and experience. Finding and training experts with the necessary clinical and technical skills can be difficult. ● Discrepancies and Disagreements: Conflicts among annotators, particularly in complex cases, are common. It's crucial to have methods for resolving these differences to establish a reliable ground truth. ● Ethical and Legal Concerns: Issues like patient consent and data privacy present challenges. Ensuring compliance with regulations and protecting patient confidentiality is critical 	

In order to overcome these challenges, we can follow the recommendations included in the latest version of the Checklist for Artificial Intelligence in Medical Imaging (CLAIM) [1]. This framework includes detailed guidelines on defining ground truth, including the qualifications of annotators, some annotation tools, and methods to measure and mitigate data variability. The list of guidelines is the following. (1) Definition of ground truth reference standard, in sufficient detail to allow replication (2) Rational explanation for choosing the reference standard (if alternatives exist) (3) Source of ground truth annotations; qualifications and preparation of annotators (4) Annotation tools (5) Measurement of inter- and intra-rater variability; methods to mitigate variability and/or resolve discrepancies.

There exist two types of ground truth data: (a) Labelled Data: In supervised learning, ground truth often consists of labelled datasets where each input is paired with the correct output. For example, in image classification, each image would be labelled with the correct category (b) Reference Data: In other contexts, ground truth can refer to reference data that is used to validate the results of an AI model, such as expert assessments or measurements taken from the real world.

CHAIMELEON Contributions

In CHAIMELEON, the ground truth is generated with retrospective data using clinical endpoints that serve as ground truth reference, aligned with the second type of ground truth described before (1) Regulatory Considerations: The medical field is heavily regulated, and AI systems must comply with standards set by regulatory bodies such as the FDA in the United States or the EMA in Europe. This includes rigorous validation processes to ensure that AI models are safe, effective, and reliable for clinical use. These validation processes often are affected directly by the ground truth reliability (2) Clinical Variability: Medical data can exhibit significant variability due to differences in patient populations, disease presentations, and treatment protocols. This variability can affect the ground truth, as what is considered "normal" or "abnormal" may differ across demographics and clinical settings. AI systems must be trained on diverse datasets to generalize well across different populations (3) Expert Annotations: Ground truths in medical AI often rely on annotations performed by medical experts, such as radiologists or pathologists. These experts provide the necessary context and insights that are critical for training AI models. However, expert opinions can vary, leading to potential inconsistencies in the ground truth (4) Evolving Standards: Medical knowledge is continually evolving, which means that ground truths can change over time. AI systems must be adaptable to incorporate new findings and guidelines to remain relevant and accurate (5) Ethical Considerations: The use of AI in medicine raises

ethical questions regarding bias, transparency, and accountability. Ensuring that ground truths are established in a fair and unbiased manner is essential to prevent disparities in healthcare outcomes (6) Integration with Clinical Practice: AI systems must be designed to integrate seamlessly into existing clinical workflows. The ground truth must be relevant to real-world clinical scenarios to ensure that AI tools are practical and beneficial for healthcare providers. In summary, while the concept of ground truth is fundamental in AI, its application in the medical field requires careful consideration.

In CHAIMELEON there is mostly reference data as type of Ground truth instead of labelled data, which means that the ground truths refer to real world assessments gathered from the patients' clinical history. During the Open Challenge different endpoints were targeted with different ground truth variables:

- Prostate cancer: Models were trained to predict patient risk based on the Gleason score, information obtained from the pathology reports.
- Rectal cancer: Models were trained to predict two main radiological findings, gathered from the radiological reports, the endorectal vascular invasion (EVI), and mesorectal fascia invasion (MFI).
- Colon cancer: Models were trained to predict the pathological TNM, retrieved from the pathology report.
- Breast cancer: Models were trained to predict the histological subtype, retrieved from the pathology report.
- Lung cancer: Models were trained to predict the patients' survival time, retrieved from the patients' clinical history.

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6.4 GD4 Data Partitions

Guideline	GD4 Data Partitions
Definition	Data partitioning process involves the division of the existing datasets into different subsets. The new subsets should contain the necessary amount and quality of data to ensure appropriate training, validation and testing of the algorithms.
Description	
<p>In the medical field, the clinical context of the project and the research questions that the clinicians want to learn from its outcome comprise the foundations for the process of shaping the characteristics of data partitions for applying AI techniques. The use of data is therefore critical for the development of AI systems, particularly high-risk AI systems for healthcare applications. The size, quality and other parameters such as accuracy or consistency of the data available for model development are often beyond the control of AI experts. In the common scenario of data scarcity, AI system developers should find alternatives to make adequate use of the available data. The process includes data management methodologies to ensure that the available and usually scarce data, is sufficient to meet training, validation and testing objectives. These methods include techniques for partitioning the available data into at least development, validation and test subsets. In the development of Medical Imaging AI systems, data partitioning is essential for developing AI models that can perform well when, for example, a new patient is exposed to the AI system's diagnostic result. Proper data partitioning must ensure the accuracy, robustness, fairness or reliability of the medical imaging AI system. All of these parameters are critical to the successful implementation of the AI system in a real healthcare setting, and the implementation of effective data partitioning strategies significantly improves the reliability and performance of AI systems in healthcare. In order to implement adequate data partitions techniques, we recommend following the AI -model development principles proposed by Maier et al. (1) It is imperative that data sets used for model development and evaluation are different. (2) It is vital that all types of patterns/events contained in the available data that are relevant to the modelling purpose are included in the model development subset. (3) It is ideal that all types of patterns/events contained in the available data are also included in the model evaluation subset. The most common approach to data partitioning is to create three subsets of the first (or sometimes last) percentage of the available time series of data for model development, validation and testing. Common splits are 70%-20%-10% or 80%-10%-10% for training,</p>	

validation and test sets respectively. This approach is also very common because researchers tend to develop and validate their AI systems with retrospective health data (allocating around 90% of the existing data) and test the model with prospective patient data (increasing the dataset by about 10%). Although valid, the approach should be carefully considered and revised to ensure that the model is not perverse and that it respects the three principles outlined above. For instance the data contained in the 3 different subsets should guarantee a random distribution, the existence of extreme values in a particular subset can have a massive impact on the results, changes in during data acquisition time series (like a new medical imaging equipment, or the incorporation of a new clinical process, etc) can distort the results.

CHAIMELEON Contributions

The CHAIMELEON repository is defined as the infrastructure and services that store anonymised health data and host the computational services for inspecting, processing, analysing, visualising and referencing these data and the corresponding outputs generated from them. Within this complex and comprehensive platform, we emphasise the existence of a large dataset with an enriched (curated, harmonised, annotated and consistent) collection of images and associated anonymised clinical data. The central repository aims to contain approximately 13,000 cases of medical imaging studies related to breast, lung, prostate, rectal and colorectal cancers, positioning the platform as an optimal infrastructure for the development, validation and testing of AI medical imaging systems. In the context of the CHAIMELEON project, the consortium granted access to external users to train, validate and test their algorithms using the CHAIMELEON data available at that time. The participation of external users was organised through an Open Challenge public call, where participants developed AI solutions for each cancer type. While participating in the Open Challenge , external users accessed both imaging exams and available clinical data within the CHAIMELEON infrastructure for each cancer type separately. Each dataset was divided into three different subsets: Training: set of cases used to adjust model weights, composed by 80% of the cases. Validation: set of cases used to validate the trained model on new unseen data. Additionally, this dataset could be used to tune some hyperparameters. It was composed of 20% of the cases and it was hidden to the participants. Testing: set of cases used for the final evaluation of the trained model on completely independent cases. It was composed of 20% of the cases and it was hidden to the participants. The method used for data partitioning was the Stratified Partitioning [1]. Stratified partitioning ensures that each CHAIMELEON subset (training, validation, and test) has the same distribution of classes as

the original dataset. The method ensured that all studies maintained the same class distribution across all subsets, which is crucial for achieving more reliable and unbiased model performance metrics.

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6.5 GD5 AI Model

Guideline	GD5 AI Model
Definition	Mathematical representation or algorithm that is designed to perform specific tasks by learning from data. It is the core of an AI based application and the direct responsible of the predictions
Description	
<p>AI Models are distinguished based on the training data used. (1) Supervised Learning: uses models that are trained on labelled datasets, where the input data is paired with the correct output. The model learns to map inputs to outputs by minimizing the error between its predictions and the actual outcomes. Common algorithms include linear regression[1], decision trees[2], and support vector machines[3]. Also, deep neural networks, specifically Convolutional Neural Networks are used in the medical imaging domain following a supervised learning strategy with classification, detection, or segmentation purposes, where radiological annotations or patients' clinical records are used as ground truth. (2) Unsupervised Learning Models: In contrast to supervised learning, unsupervised learning models work with unlabelled data. The model attempts to identify patterns or groupings within the data without prior knowledge of the outcomes. Techniques such as clustering (e.g., K-means) and dimensionality reduction (e.g., PCA) are commonly used. Unsupervised learning is useful for exploratory data analysis and anomaly detection (3) Self-supervised Learning Models: Self-supervised models are a type of machine learning approach that leverages unlabelled data to learn useful representations without the need for explicit supervision. In self-supervised learning, the model generates its own labels from the input data by creating tasks that allow it to learn from the inherent structure of the data itself. For example, in natural language processing, a common self-supervised task is predicting the next word in a sentence based on the preceding words. In computer vision, a model might learn to predict missing parts of an image or to distinguish between different transformations of the same image.</p> <p>What is inside an AI model? An AI model typically consists of several layers, each serving a specific function in processing input data. The most common architecture used in many applications is the neural network, particularly deep learning model. (1) Input Layer: This is the first layer of the model, where data is fed into the system. Inputs can vary widely depending on the application; for instance, in a medical imaging model, the input might be pixel values from an imaging scan. (2) Intermediate Layers: These layers, often referred to</p>	

as hidden layers, perform various transformations on the input data. Each layer consists of multiple neurons, which apply activation functions to the weighted sum of inputs. Common types of intermediate layers include: (a) Convolutional Layers: Used primarily in image processing, these layers apply convolution operations to extract features from the input images. (b) Recurrent Layers: Utilized in sequential data processing, such as time series or natural language, these layers maintain a memory of previous inputs. (c) Fully Connected Layers: These layers connect every neuron from the previous layer to every neuron in the current layer, allowing for complex feature interactions. (3) Output Layer: The final layer produces the model's predictions. The output can be a single value (e.g., a probability score for binary classification) or a vector of values (e.g., class probabilities in multi-class classification). Connections between layers are established through weights, which are adjusted during the training process. Each connection has an associated weight that determines the influence of one neuron on another. The model learns these weights through backpropagation, a method that calculates gradients of the loss function with respect to each weight and updates them accordingly after each iteration to reduce the error against the reference (ground truth) which will be translated to precise predictions when this error is reduced enough.

Frameworks and Libraries: To implement AI models, various software libraries and frameworks are available, each offering unique features and capabilities: (1) TensorFlow: An open-source library developed by Google, TensorFlow is widely used for building and training deep learning models. It provides a flexible architecture that allows for deployment across various platforms. (2) PyTorch: Developed by Facebook. PyTorch is known for its dynamic computation graph, which allows for more intuitive model building and debugging. It is particularly popular in research settings. (3) Keras: A high-level API that runs on top of TensorFlow, Keras simplifies the process of building neural networks. It provides user-friendly methods for creating layers, compiling models, and fitting them to data. (4) Scikit-learn: While primarily focused on traditional machine learning algorithms, Scikit-learn offers tools for data preprocessing, model evaluation, and hyperparameter tuning, making it a valuable resource for AI model development.

CHAIMELEON Contributions

For the harmonization MRI algorithm, an autoencoder based architecture is trained to bring synthetic generated contrasts from diverse MRI captures to the same common dynamic intensity range, this self-supervised approach takes contrast altered copies of each 2D slice that have been generated by performing subtle modifications on the frequency domain, and

a U-Net based network is trained with this generated paired dataset. Moreover, GAN-based architectures [4] are as well utilized to create an AI harmonization tool to harmonise multi anatomic CT scans. Super-resolution in CT imaging is essential for enhancing the spatial resolution of medical images, which plays a critical role in improving diagnostic accuracy [5]. By increasing the resolution, finer anatomical structures and subtle pathological changes that might be missed in lower-resolution images can be detected more clearly. This leads to better visualization of tissues, allowing clinicians to differentiate between normal and abnormal regions with greater precision. Additionally, super-resolution helps reduce noise and artifacts that could otherwise distort the image, enhancing the overall quality of the diagnosis. For tasks like segmentation and other automated image analysis methods, higher-resolution images contribute to more accurate and reliable results. Moreover, super-resolution techniques support the use of low-dose imaging, which reduces patient exposure to radiation while still maintaining high image quality, thus optimizing patient safety. The proposed model outperforms other network architectures like Autoencoder[6] and UNet[7] in terms of the reconstruction accuracy.

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6.6 GD6 Model Training

Guideline	GD6 Model Training
Definition	Refers to details of the training approach, including data augmentation, hyperparameters, number of models trained, method used to select the final model and assembly techniques, if applicable.
Description	
<p>Model training involves the process of teaching a machine learning model to recognize patterns in data by adjusting model parameters based on input data and expected outputs. This phase is crucial in the development of AI-driven healthcare solutions, where accurate and reliable model performance can have significant implications for patient outcomes. Depending on the available computational resources and the specific requirements of the task, various approaches to model training are utilized: (1) Local Single-Machine Training: This is a common approach for training smaller models or for initial prototyping. A single machine, often equipped with a GPU, is used to train the model. This setup is easy to manage and debug, making it ideal for testing new algorithms or developing models in their early stages. However, due to hardware limitations, local single-machine training may struggle to scale efficiently for large datasets, limiting its application in more data-intensive healthcare tasks (2) Local Cluster Training: For larger datasets or more complex models, local cluster training is often used. This method employs multiple machines or nodes to distribute the computational load, using techniques such as data parallelism or model parallelism. By enabling the use of larger datasets and more computational power, local cluster training helps improve both training speed and model performance [1]. This approach is more suitable for complex tasks like cancer diagnosis or treatment planning, which require vast amounts of data and advanced deep learning techniques (3) Federated Learning: Federated learning is an emerging training paradigm designed for scenarios where data privacy is paramount, as is often the case in healthcare. Rather than centralizing data in a single location, federated learning allows models to be trained across multiple decentralized devices or institutions. Only the model updates, and not the sensitive data, are shared between nodes. This ensures that sensitive healthcare data, such as medical images or patient records, remain local, while still benefiting from collaborative model training across multiple sources.</p>	

Apart from the computational resources used for training, AI developers should define the training strategy followed, such as training from scratch or transfer learning, the cost/loss function used during training, or the optimizer used for learning rate optimization.

CHAIMELEON Contributions

The CHAIMELEON project plays a pivotal role in enhancing model training approaches within the healthcare domain, particularly for cancer research, by offering a repository of anonymized imaging and clinical data from the most prevalent cancers in Europe, including lung, breast, prostate, and colorectal cancers. This resource facilitates several model training strategies: (a) For Local Single-Machine Training, CHAIMELEON's curated datasets can be used in the prototyping stages of model development. To facilitate the classification phase of the CHAIMELEON Open Challenges, participating researchers were allowed to download a specifically curated subset of the data from the repository to experiment with their models and validate initial hypotheses on their individual machines. (b) For Local Cluster Training, the extensive and high-quality data provided by CHAIMELEON enables researchers to utilize distributed computing resources to train complex models. As such, by leveraging the CHAIMELEON cluster environments, larger models for cancer prediction or treatment analysis can be trained efficiently using CHAIMELEON's datasets, improving both training speed and model accuracy. The ability to distribute data across nodes makes CHAIMELEON an essential resource for data-intensive tasks.

As the CHAIMELEON repository provides access to rich and diverse sets of medical imaging and corresponding clinical data pairs from multiple data providers, it facilitates supervised training of machine learning models, which is otherwise greatly challenged by the scarcity of paired medical data sets. At the same time this diverse real world data set made accessible through the CHAIMELEON platform can greatly benefit unsupervised training approaches, e.g., given rise to improved pattern recognition or feature extraction. CHAIMELEON's contributions to these various training methods, particularly in its support of privacy-preserving federated learning, make it a key enabler for the development of advanced AI solutions in oncology and healthcare.

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6.7 GD7 Model Evaluation

Guideline	GD7 Model Evaluation
Definition	Process of assessing the performance of a trained machine learning model on unseen data to determine its accuracy, robustness, and generalization capability.
Description	
<p>Model Evaluation addresses the assessment of trained machine learning (ML) models on unseen data to determine their accuracy, robustness, and generalization capability. In medical imaging, this step is pivotal because clinical decisions may depend on the outputs of AI tools. A strong evaluation framework ensures that models can handle the variability in imaging protocols, scanner types, and patient demographics commonly encountered in real-world clinical practice.</p> <p>Current Challenges</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Complexity of Medical Imaging Data: Medical imaging data—encompassing MRI, CT, X-ray, or histopathological slides—poses unique challenges: large volumes, heterogeneous acquisition settings, and the need for expert, often labour-intensive annotations (Litjens et al., 2017). Small errors in labelling can substantially affect model performance. Moreover, large-scale public datasets are less common than in general computer vision, making rigorous evaluation and reproducibility more difficult. 2) Overfitting and Generalization: Overfitting is a recurring concern: a model may achieve high performance on a training set but struggle with new data from different hospitals or scanner types (Esteva et al., 2019). To mitigate this, standard practice in medical imaging often goes beyond simple train-test splits to include methods such as multi-fold cross-validation, which provides a more robust estimate of performance by cycling through multiple training/validation splits. 3) Domain Shifts and Out-of-Distribution Scenarios: Medical imaging data can differ significantly depending on the equipment vendor, acquisition parameters, and patient demographics. When confronted with images that deviate from its training distribution (out-of-distribution, OOD), a model may generate unreliable predictions (Hendrycks & Gimpel, 2017). Realistic evaluation protocols must therefore 	

incorporate domain shift testing to ensure that models perform well even under different clinical conditions.

Current Evaluation Methodologies. Different metrics and techniques are used depending on the type of model and task [1].

- 1) Local Evaluation: In traditional single-institution settings, models are assessed on a local test set. Although useful as an initial check, this approach may not reveal how a model generalizes to diverse data sources.
- 2) Cross-Validation: K-fold cross-validation better estimates model performance by splitting data into multiple folds and rotating the validation fold. This reduces the likelihood that results are driven by any particular data split [2].
- 3) Federated Evaluation: In federated learning, each institution trains and evaluates models on its own private data, aggregating results centrally [3]. This allows multi-site assessment while respecting data privacy regulations.
- 4) Out-of-Distribution (OOD) Evaluation: OOD testing measures model performance on data that deviate from the training distribution. Medical imaging is highly prone to domain shifts (e.g., scanner brand), making OOD evaluation critical for real-world robustness[4].

Ongoing Research Challenges

- Data Scarcity and Class Imbalance: Certain pathologies are rare; obtaining enough representative samples can be difficult, leading to imbalanced datasets.
- Explainability: Clinicians increasingly expect interpretability regarding how AI models arrive at their predictions (Guidotti et al., 2018).
- Regulatory Considerations: Legal requirements (e.g., GDPR) must be met, especially in multi-center studies.
- Continuous Monitoring: Even after deployment, models must be re-evaluated as data distributions shift over time (e.g., new imaging protocols).

CHAIMELEON Contributions

Within CHAIMELEON, model evaluation was approached from multiple angles to address the domain shifts and data variability challenges highlighted in the previous section. First, the project's harmonization models were locally tested on multiple centers' datasets to verify that scanner- and site-related inconsistencies were minimized, thereby enhancing the

reproducibility of radiomic features across different sources. Subsequently, these harmonization models were uploaded to the CHAIMELEON platform for more extensive cross-validation and out-of-distribution (OOD) testing, ensuring broader generalizability and robust performance when encountering data from diverse clinical settings. In addition to standard classification or segmentation metrics, rigorous statistical analyses—such as paired t-tests or Wilcoxon signed-rank tests—were employed to compare model performance before and after harmonization, thereby quantifying improvements in downstream tasks (e.g., anatomical structure segmentation) and confirming the reproducibility of extracted radiomic features. This multi-stage, multi-institutional validation framework directly addresses the critical gap of ensuring reliable, real-world applicability of AI models, demonstrating how harmonization can alleviate site-specific biases while maintaining clinically relevant performance.

In addition, the appropriate evaluation of models developed during the open challenge was guaranteed since developers had no access to either validation and testing datasets. Additionally, a single evaluation over the testing dataset was granted to prevent overfitting.

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6.8 GD8 AI Technical Performance

Guideline	GD8 AI Technical Performance
Definition	AI technical performance refers to a set of metrics and techniques to evaluate the ability of an AI system to process medical data for a given task.
Description	
<p>Technical performance in AI for medical imaging is a multidimensional task, as AI models cover a wide range of applications, including disease classification, lesion segmentation, image harmonization, and treatment outcome prediction. Each of these tasks requires specific evaluation metrics that ensure the AI system meets clinical requirements and generalizes across different datasets and patient populations. When metrics fail to adequately measure the performance of AI models, it hinders the translation of these systems to practice [1].</p> <p>Classification is the task of assigning one or more labels to an image, such as in disease classification or risk stratification. Evaluating classification tasks requires metrics that measure the system’s discrimination power. Accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity provide essential insights into how well an AI model distinguishes between normal and pathological cases. The area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC-ROC) is frequently used to assess a model’s ability to differentiate between classes across different threshold settings, allowing the analysis of the trade-off between specificity and sensitivity. Precision and recall are crucial for evaluating performance in imbalanced datasets, where false positives and false negatives must be carefully balanced. For multi-class classification problems, metrics that show the performance of multiple classes in a single value such as the Balanced Accuracy (BA) or Mathews correlation coefficient (MCC) are recommended, as well as per-class metrics such as the F-score [2]. Binary metrics can be also calculated for multiclass problems using macro averaging that averages the performance across classes, giving the same weight to each class or using micro averaging that gives equal weight to each single instance. In AI systems applied to medicine, multiple challenges should be considered when selecting evaluation metrics. High class imbalance is a common issue, in which certain classes are significantly more prevalent in a dataset due to for example disease prevalence or unequal access to the data of a specific group. In such cases it is recommended to use metrics that account for the performance of multiple classes such as BA and to evaluate performance of each class separately. A typical example of a class</p>	

imbalance problem is a screening application, in which most of the cases will be negative and positive cases rarely. Additionally, small test sets pose a challenge in AI in healthcare due to limited data accessibility. It is therefore recommended to report confidence intervals alongside metrics results to ensure robust evaluation. Beyond methodological aspects, it is important to align AI systems with its intended use case, including a cost-benefit analysis when evaluating it. For example, in a disease classification problem, while accuracy is an important indicator of the overall system performance, false negatives carry significant consequences, as their increase increases the risk of a disease to be overlooked. Therefore, sensitivity may be prioritised to minimize such risk and enhance clinical utility. In survival prediction or time-to-event analysis, metrics like the concordance index (C-index) measure the model's ability to rank patients by their risk of experiencing an event such as disease progression or death.

Segmentation tasks, where AI is responsible for delineating anatomical structures or pathological regions, classifying each pixel to a specific class. Here the metrics are first calculated per image and then aggregated over the set of images. Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) remains a widely used metric and it measures the pixel-wise agreement between a predicted segmentation and its ground truth. Intersection over Union (IoU) is together with DSC a metric used to measure the overlap between the reference and the prediction. Both these metrics are recommended unless the target structures are small. Additionally, boundary-based metrics can be used to complement the segmentation tasks such as the normalized surface distance (NSD) and hausdorff distance (HD), which assesses boundary precision by capturing the largest surface deviation between predicted and actual segmentations. For segmentation and detection of small objects, such as in a task of lesion detection the overlapping metrics may not be the best performance indicator as in small regions, differences of a few pixels highly impact on these metrics. In this case, it can be considered an object detection problem where the metric depends on the localization representation [2]. If the lesions are represented as masks, the IoU or DSC over a given threshold can be selected as a measure for correctly detected lesions. If the lesions are represented with the centre points, the lesion can be classified as detected when the distance between the predicted and the ground truth is lower than a certain predefined value. Once objects have been located and assigned to the reference ones, a confusion matrix can be generated, and classification metrics can be used for the detection problem. However, true negatives are not available which excludes many of the well-known classification metrics

(accuracy, specificity and AUROC). We recommend the use of False positives and sensitivity as well as multi-threshold metrics as free-response receiver operating classification curve (FROC) score.

Finally, evaluating image harmonization in the context of medical imaging involves assessing how well image data from different sources, scanners, or protocols have been standardized while maintaining the relevant features for analysis. To quantitatively assess harmonization, metrics like histogram matching can be used to compare intensity distributions before and after harmonization, while Mean Squared Error (MSE) or Mean Absolute Error (MAE) can measure discrepancies. Mutual information is another metric to assess the statistical relationship between datasets. Image quality metrics like Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) ensure that harmonization does not degrade image quality, and techniques such as the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test or Kullback-Leibler divergence compare the statistical distributions of pixel intensities before and after harmonization. We recommend evaluating image harmonization methods by comparing the performance of using the harmonized images on a given task.

CHAIMELEON Contributions

The CHAIMELEON Open Challenges, extended to the entire scientific community, presented an opportunity to train and refine AI models to address clinical questions about five types of cancers including prostate, lung, breast, colon and rectal. CHAIMELEON contributed to the definition of a set of performance scores that summarizes multiple evaluation metrics into a single numerical value for each clinical problem, allowing to compare the performance of each of them while considering multiple dimensions of a problem. Each score was carefully designed to align with the specific use case, ensuring the solution is applicable to address the clinical question.

For the prostate use case, the AI solution aimed at differentiating between low- and high-risk prostate cancer to avoid unnecessary aggressive procedures in low grade patients while providing the most advanced therapy for high-grade cases. CHAIMELEON proposed a performance score that integrates various classification metrics, calculated as a weighted sum of AUC, sensitivity, specificity and balanced accuracy. This metric is designed to account for multiple dimensions of the problem ensuring both low and high-risk cases are accurately classified and appropriately reflected in the final score. The objective of the lung cancer task was to predict the overall survival (OS) using baseline CT imaging and radiomics features. To evaluate the model's performance the metric

selected was the C-index as it measures the model's ability to correctly rank the predicted OS times.

The rectal cancer use case consists of two different tasks: predicting the presence of extramural vascular invasion (EVI) and mesorectal fascia invasion (MFI). To determine the best performing solution for the use case, the performance of the two classifiers needed to be evaluated in a single final score. The performance of each task was calculated using the same formula as in the prostate use case, while the final score was defined as the average of both tasks scores.

The colon cancer task aims at using CT scan and additional clinical data to predict the tumour pathological category (T), the regional nodes pathological category (N) and the metastasis pathological category (M). This task involves three classifiers: the T and N classifiers, which are multiclass and the M classifier, which is binary. The score of each classifier was calculated following the example of the prostate use cases, however for the multiclass classifiers, the micro-sensitivity and micro-specificity was calculated. The weighted sum of the three classifiers produces the final score. The weights associated with each classifier were selected by its importance in the clinical practice, assigning a weight of 0.4 to the T-score and 0.3 to the N-score and M-score.

Finally, the breast cancer task predicts the tumour histological subtype using mammography images combined with clinical data. The breast use case consists of a single multiclass classifier that predicts the following subtypes: ductal carcinoma in situ (DCIS), invasive ductal carcinoma (IDC), invasive lobular carcinoma (ILC), and others. To evaluate the performance, the same approach used in the other use cases was applied, a weighted sum of the classification metrics presented in the prostate cancer use case, but calculating the micro-sensitivity and micro-specificity for the multiclass setting.

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6.9 GD9 Accuracy

Guideline	GD9 Accuracy
Definition	Metric used to measure the proportion of correctly predicted outcomes (both true positives and true negatives) out of the total number of predictions made by a model
Description	
<p>In the context of medical imaging and machine learning, accuracy is a critical metric that reflects how well a model correctly classifies or segments data into its respective categories. However, accuracy must be interpreted with caution, especially in medical imaging tasks where class imbalance (such as rare diseases) is common [1]. For example, in medical diagnostics, a model might achieve high accuracy by predominantly predicting the more frequent class, but it might still perform poorly on critical, less frequent cases (e.g., false negatives in disease detection) [2].</p> <p>(1) Class Imbalance: In medical imaging, datasets often contain a disproportionate number of healthy samples compared to diseased samples. In such cases, accuracy alone may not adequately reflect the model's true performance. Supplementary metrics such as precision, recall, and the F1-score are often used in conjunction to provide a fuller picture. Precision measures the proportion of true positive predictions among all positive predictions, while recall (or sensitivity) measures the proportion of true positives identified out of all actual positives. The F1-score, which is the harmonic mean of precision and recall, provides a balanced measure of the model's performance, especially in imbalanced datasets [3].</p> <p>(2) Threshold Setting: In binary classification tasks, the accuracy of a model can vary depending on the decision threshold used to classify outputs as positive or negative. Fine-tuning this threshold is essential to balance sensitivity (recall) and specificity, especially in medical tasks where false positives or false negatives may have significant clinical implications. For instance, in cancer detection, a lower threshold might increase sensitivity, ensuring that more true positives are identified, but at the cost of increasing false positives. Conversely, a higher threshold might reduce false positives but at the risk of missing true positives. Therefore, selecting an appropriate threshold is crucial for optimizing the model's performance in clinical settings⁴.</p> <p>(3) Segmentation Accuracy: In medical image segmentation tasks, accuracy extends beyond simple classification. For segmentation, it measures how well the model predicts the correct pixels or regions in an image and is often complemented by metrics like Dice</p>	

similarity coefficient (DSC) or Intersection over Union (IoU) to assess how well the predicted boundaries align with ground truth labels. The Dice coefficient measures the overlap between the predicted segmentation and the ground truth, while IoU measures the ratio of the intersection area to the union area of the predicted and ground truth regions. These metrics are particularly important in tasks such as tumour segmentation, where precise delineation of the tumour boundaries is critical for treatment planning [5].

(4) **Challenges in Achieving High Accuracy:** Achieving high accuracy in medical imaging AI systems is fraught with challenges. One major challenge is the variability in imaging data due to differences in imaging equipment, acquisition protocols, and patient populations. This variability can lead to inconsistencies in model performance across different datasets and institutions. Additionally, the lack of large, annotated datasets for rare diseases or conditions can hinder the development of accurate models. Furthermore, the interpretability of AI models in medical imaging is crucial, as clinicians need to trust and understand the model's predictions to integrate them into clinical workflows. Ensuring that AI models are not only accurate but also interpretable and generalizable across diverse datasets remains a significant challenge in the field.

(5) **State of the Art in Accuracy Improvement:** Recent advancements in deep learning, particularly convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and transformer-based architectures, have significantly improved the accuracy of medical imaging AI systems. Techniques such as transfer learning, where pre-trained models on large datasets (e.g., ImageNet) are fine-tuned on medical imaging data, have shown promise in improving model performance, especially in scenarios with limited annotated data. Additionally, data augmentation techniques, such as rotation, flipping, and elastic deformations, are commonly used to increase the diversity of training data and improve model robustness. Ensemble methods, which combine predictions from multiple models, have also been employed to enhance accuracy by reducing variance and improving generalization.

(6) **Ethical Considerations:** While improving accuracy is essential, it is equally important to ensure that AI systems are fair and unbiased. Models trained on datasets that are not representative of the target population may exhibit biases, leading to disparities in performance across different demographic groups. For example, a model trained predominantly on data from one ethnic group may perform poorly on data from another group. Therefore, ensuring that training datasets are diverse and representative is crucial for developing fair and accurate AI systems.

CHAIMELEON Contributions

The CHAIMELEON project has made significant contributions to improving accuracy in medical imaging AI systems, particularly through the development and validation of harmonization methods. The goal of harmonization is to reduce non-biological variability in imaging data while preserving the intrinsic biological differences that are meaningful for diagnosis or treatment. By addressing the variability in imaging data across different institutions and imaging protocols, CHAIMELEON has enhanced the reproducibility and reliability of radiomic features, which are critical for the accuracy of downstream AI models.

(a) **Radiomic Feature Harmonization:** One of the key contributions of CHAIMELEON is the development of methods to harmonize radiomic features across different imaging sites. Radiomic features, which are quantitative descriptors extracted from medical images, are sensitive to variations in imaging equipment and protocols. These variations can lead to inconsistencies in feature values, which in turn affect the performance of AI models. CHAIMELEON researchers have employed statistical techniques, such as ComBat harmonization, to adjust for these variations and ensure that radiomic features are consistent across different imaging settings. This harmonization process has been shown to significantly improve the reproducibility of radiomic features, as measured by metrics such as the intra-class correlation coefficient (ICC) and coefficient of variation (CoV) [6].

(b) **Test-Retest Reproducibility:** Another important contribution of CHAIMELEON is the evaluation of test-retest reproducibility of radiomic features. In this approach, images from the same patient acquired at different times are compared to assess the stability of radiomic features. Ideally, the extracted radiomic features should remain stable between the two imaging sessions, despite differences in imaging conditions. CHAIMELEON researchers have demonstrated that harmonization techniques can improve the test-retest reproducibility of radiomic features, providing further validation of the harmonization methods. This improvement in reproducibility is crucial for ensuring that AI models trained on harmonized data perform consistently across different imaging conditions and institutions [7].

(c) **Impact on Downstream AI Models:** The harmonization efforts in CHAIMELEON have had a direct impact on the accuracy of downstream AI models, such as those used for tumor segmentation and classification. By reducing the variability in radiomic features, harmonization has improved the generalization capability of these models, enabling them to perform well on data from different institutions and imaging protocols. For example, in a study conducted within the CHAIMELEON project, researchers compared the performance of a tumor segmentation model before and after harmonization. The results showed that the

model's accuracy, as measured by the Dice coefficient, improved significantly after harmonization, particularly on data from institutions that were not part of the training set.

(d) **Integration with Clinical Workflows:** CHAIMELEON has also focused on integrating harmonized AI models into clinical workflows to ensure that they are not only accurate but also clinically useful. This involves working closely with clinicians to understand their needs and constraints and developing models that can be easily integrated into existing clinical systems. For example, CHAIMELEON researchers have developed user-friendly interfaces that allow clinicians to interact with AI models and interpret their predictions. This integration has been critical for gaining clinician trust and ensuring that AI models are adopted in real-world clinical settings.

By focusing on the reproducibility of radiomic features across diverse datasets and imaging conditions, CHAIMELEON aims to improve the accuracy of medical imaging AI systems. To achieve this, advanced harmonization techniques, such as deep learning-based methods, have been explored. These techniques leverage the power of neural networks to learn complex mappings between different imaging protocols, providing more robust and flexible harmonization solutions.

Furthermore, CHAIMELEON has investigated the use of federated learning, which enables the training of AI models on distributed datasets without sharing sensitive patient data. This approach not only enhances model accuracy by leveraging data from multiple institutions but also ensures data privacy.

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6.10 GD10 Reliability

Guideline	GD10 Reliability
Definition	Consistency and dependability of an AI system in producing accurate and expected outcomes under various conditions
Description	
<p>According to the National Institute for Standards and Technology (NIST), “reliability [of AI systems] is defined in the same standard as the “ability of an item to perform as required, without failure, for a given time interval, under given conditions” (Source: ISO/IEC TS 5723:2022). Reliability is a goal for overall correctness of AI system operation under the conditions of expected use and over a given period of time, including the entire lifetime of the system.” [1]</p> <p>The NIST definition of reliability is very much aligned with the view of the High-Level Expert Group on AI of the European Commission who underlines the strong relationship between reliability and reproducibility (covered by GD 11) in their published Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence. In these guidelines, they state that “It is critical that the results of AI systems are reproducible, as well as reliable. A reliable AI system is one that works properly with a range of inputs and in a range of situations. This is needed to scrutinise an AI system and to prevent unintended harms. Reproducibility describes whether an AI experiment exhibits the same behaviour when repeated under the same conditions. This enables scientists and policy makers to accurately describe what AI systems do. Replication files can facilitate the process of testing and reproducing behaviours.” [2]</p> <p>Tanguay et al considered that Reliability is perhaps more adequate for projects related with segmentation or augmentation of certain regions of the image [3]. However, if we consider that a reliable AI system is the AI model that works properly with a range of inputs and in a range of situations, we can also talk about reliable medical imaging AI systems related to detection, triage, radiomics or prediction. The main components to define a model reliability are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accuracy: The degree to which the model's predictions or outputs match the actual outcomes. High accuracy indicates reliable performance. • Robustness: The model's ability to maintain performance when faced with unexpected inputs or changes in the environment. A robust model should not fail dramatically under slight variations. 	

- Consistency: The model's ability to produce similar results when given the same input multiple times. Variability in outputs can indicate reliability issues
- Generalization: The ability of the model to perform well on unseen data that was not part of the training set. A reliable model should generalize well beyond its training examples.

These four pillars of an AI model's reliability stated by Tanguay et al can be extended by a fifth dimension:

- Uncertainty: A model's ability to report the (un)certainty of the respective prediction and/or providing means to make them explainable can further help to characterize the reliability of each individual output and thereby help build trust in real world applications.

The complex nature of modern AI methods, which are oftentimes considered black boxes as they rely on semi-heuristic modelling is one of the main differences compared to traditional data processing methods relying on mathematical and/or statistical foundations. As such, ensuring the reliability of advanced AI tools is challenging. To assess and validate the reliability of AI tools despite the lack of theoretical foundations, the field to date relies on continuous evaluation and monitoring to ensure that the systems' performance is consistent and as intended across different application conditions and for various input data - within the predefined application scenario(s). At the same time, significant research effort is put into embedding AI tools into a mathematical formulation to provide another level of reliability proof.

CHAIMELEON Contributions

Several mechanisms and systems to guarantee the reliability of AI models have been implemented in CHAIMELEON tools and AI development. Next generation AI algorithms are often trained in well-defined/curated and hence homogenous datasets to minimize variability in proof-of-concept studies. Also, data privacy regulations pose a significant challenge for collecting large-sized training datasets. As a result, despite demonstrating promising results in the initial training and validation scenario, AI model reliability might be poor when rolled out to real-world clinical workflows. The core aim of CHAIMELEON is to build a structured repository that hosts a large collection of real-world data, acquired at multiple clinical sites with a different scanner landscape and various clinical protocols in place. Making such a heterogeneous database available and usable to AI developers builds the backbone to training reliably AI tools. In addition to making large-scale real-world data accessible, the

CHAIMELEON platform hosts readily available data harmonization models. Those allow effective use of the heterogeneous data by balancing out natural variability in the data on the one hand and on the other hand facilitate straightforward incorporation of additional training data or improving model performance when applied to out of distribution data. Reliability of AI models is very much dependent on the specific use case. For the end-user of the respective AI tool – independent if the user is based in a technical or clinical setting – it is important to have access to clear instructions and/or guidelines on the correct usage of the AI model in order to avoid misuse and to achieve the best performance and reliable model results. As part of CHAIMELEON, a lot of effort has hence been put into providing clear instructions (in the form of github pages and tutorial videos) on the usage of the hosted AI tools. Another emphasis of the CHAIMELEON project is to develop approaches that help to improve explainability of AI models. Those tools are incorporated into the CHAIMELEON platform and made available to the user community. As model reliability is closely linked to trustworthiness, we thereby equip the CHAIMELEON users with tools that facilitate the interpretation of the hosted models and help them understand the impact of individual features on model prediction. Beside the above listed key components, all the other measures that we have taken, e.g. as explained in GD11: Reproducibility and GD12: Robustness, equally contribute to the aim of ensuring reliability of the AI models hosted in and developed with the CHAIMELEON repository.

Extensive internal, external and clinical validations have been performed to ensure not only the performance but also the reliability of these tools. Let us take the harmonization models as a reference to illustrate the various levels of stress testing and validation: First, data that has been processed with harmonization algorithms was used for model training and testing independently with internal segmentation tasks to compare performance versus using the original (non-harmonized) data for the same AI task. The models were then integrated in CHAIMELEON platform where the internal and external usability tests were carried out. First, partners within the CHAIMELEON project were experimenting with and testing the AI tools. Second, an extensive external test was done with the Open Challenges, in which external users were conducting experiments and compete against each other's using and creating AI models within CHAIMELEON platform, making use of the hosted AI tools and thereby stress testing their inherent reliability. Third, another set of internal experiments are to be performed through an internal comparison of the AI tools, implementing certain AI tasks and challenges to be solved with CHAIMELEON harmonization algorithms, radiomic analysis for harmonized data using CHAIMELEON harmonization models, etc. In parallel, the AI models

(trained by leveraging the harmonization tools) that have been awarded as part of the Open Challenges are currently undergoing an extended clinical evaluation. All these features and operations build upon each other and contribute to guarantee AI reliability in the CHAIMELEON platform.

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6.11 GD11 Reproducibility

Guideline	GD11 Reproducibility
Definition	Capacity of a test or experiment to be reproduced or replicated by others or by the author of the experiment after a period of time.
Description	
<p>AI has enabled tremendous breakthroughs across various domains, including the medical field where new AI-driven applications are more and more entering the clinical routine, automating otherwise complex or tedious tasks. AI tools have demonstrated their great potential in supporting clinical decision making specifically in data analysis tasks such as in diagnostics, personalized treatment planning or prediction of patient outcomes [1]. AI has also made significant strides in robotic surgery or drug development. Despite the immense success and the great promise AI brings for healthcare applications, a significant challenge has emerged at the same time which is the lack of reproducibility in AI research [2]. Reproducibility of AI-obtained results is of utmost importance in medical applications, where reliability, precision and accuracy are crucial for patient health. Such a reproducibility crisis as we are seeing it now is not only challenging the healthcare sector. However, in a review published in 2021, McDermott et al “found that machine learning for health compared poorly to other areas regarding reproducibility metrics, such as dataset and code accessibility” [3]. The authors see one of the main underlying obstacles in the scarcity of clinical data that hampers training such predictive models or to phrase it differently reduces generalizability of such AI models that might suffer from bias and/or overfitting. At the same time, such a reproducibility crisis is neither only challenging the healthcare sector, nor only the AI field but is impacting the research communities overall. This is why there are more and more community-driven efforts that address the need for reproducibility by advocating for publication of detailed methodologies and the underlying code, the use of standardized evaluation benchmarks or through publication of guidelines or organization of reproducibility challenges. Also, there are important initiatives like the CHAIMELEON project aiming to create large real-world datasets that are open to the whole research community.</p> <p>What does reproducibility mean in the context of AI research? In general, reproducibility of (AI) experiments implies several dimensions: (1) Reproducibility of the environment: The boundary conditions in which an experiment is carried out are key to ensuring that the results obtained are the same. In Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) environments, this involves having information about the hardware and software resources</p>	

used, as well as the ability to configure these environments in a convenient manner. (2) Reproducibility of the experiment: The steps, metrics and processing pipelines should be registered in a way that can be replicated. As such, this dimension incorporates two main building blocks of AI research, namely the dataset and the AI algorithm itself.

CHAIMELEON Contributions

CHAIMELEON has intensively focused on the reproducibility of the environments, by providing virtual environments and persistent data packaging methods. CHAIMELEON uses the Infrastructure as Code (IaC), which uses a high-level descriptive coding language to automate the provisioning of IT infrastructures. In particular, CHAIMELEON uses: (1) Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications (TOSCA) [4] to define the components, configuration and interactions of the CHAIMELEON platform backend, including the CEPH storage and the Kubernetes backend. (2) Kubernetes manifests: Kubernetes is the “de-facto” standard for the management of container clusters. Applications in Kubernetes are described through manifests that describe the different containers, configurations, network connectivity, data volumes and any other component required for setting up the virtual environment. CHAIMELEON uses two types of descriptions: (a) Native Kubernetes manifests in YAML [5], which provide fine-grain control in the configuration of the components and can be extended through operators and custom resources. (b) HELM Charts [6], which provide a higher-level of abstraction and facilitate the deployment of complex components. All the core services developed in CHAIMELEON are coded into YAML manifests [7]. For third-party components CHAIMELEON uses the official manifest descriptions, which could be in Helm (e.g. Keycloak). The virtual environments of the users are also coded into Helm manifests. (3) Dockerfiles: The applications running in the platform are embedded into containers. CHAIMELEON uses both official containers for third-party applications and customized containers for the services and the virtual environments. A methodology for the creation of secure Docker container images has been elaborated [8]. All Dockerfiles are registered in GitHub [9] (in the repositories starting with “image_batch”). All images are tagged with versions, so environments can be reproduced even if a new version of the environment is available (except in the cases that new versions are applied to patch vulnerabilities of the components). In addition to the reproducibility of the environment, it is key to ensure that the datasets are kept consistent along the time. CHAIMELEON uses a read-only storage backend for the DICOM images and an indexing system that provides the users with a view of the data available, including only the studies indexed in the dataset.

As datasets' views are not deleted and datasets have a persistent identifier, the experiments can use the same data even if new versions of the datasets have been created.

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6.12 GD12 Robustness

Guideline	GD12 Robustness
Definition	Capacity of a test or experiment to be reproduced or replicated by others or by the author of the experiment after a period of time.
Description	
<p>Cybersecurity is a major concern for health institutions and this guideline focuses on the security aspects of AI. These systems expose new vulnerabilities that must be considered to ensure a robust system against an adversarial agent. For example, a model can perform very well on authentic data but be manipulated into behaving maliciously when given manipulated data. A trustworthy and robust AI system should have the capacity to be resilient to such attacks. There are three stages in the ML life cycle each with their own unique challenges: (1) Train Phase: The first threat that faces machine learning models occurs during model training [1,2]. To ensure that a medical imaging model can be trusted, it is critical that steps be taken to protect the data on which these models are trained. For example, one should examine the data supply chain, search for anomalies in the data, and by applying digital signatures to DICOM files at their creation and verify those signatures during consumption [3]. Doing so can help detect any manipulations to the data that have been made to poison an AI trained on this data. In Chameleon, we perform a process similar to digital signatures where the hash of uploaded data is stored and monitored to detect the moment the media is tampered [4]. We also offer users to scan their data for synthetic (deepfake) content. (2) Store Phase: The second threat occurs during storage of the model. During this phase adversaries can tamper the model’s weights to inject hidden behaviors (a.k.a. backdoors). They can also analyse the model to craft stronger attacks against the AI once it is deployed [5]. These threats can be mitigated by maintaining proper access control and employing other conventional cyber security mechanisms that ensure data integrity and track data provenance. In CHAIMELEON, users have credentials and operate in isolated environments. Moreover, interactions with model files are logged and can be audited. (3) Execute Phase: The third threat happens during model deployment, when executing the model on data to make predictions. Using queries alone, adversaries can use techniques to steal the model [6] or covertly alter the model’s predictions (e.g., change the diagnosis or segmentation of an image without changing the image’s semantics) [7]. These attacks are referred to as model extraction and adversarial examples respectively. To mitigate model extraction, model owners can either monitor the entropy/realism of the images sent to their</p>	

models and limit the number of daily queries allowed. This is because model extraction attacks typically involve millions of queries and may include unrealistic imagery to sample model boundaries. Regarding the threat of adversarial examples, users of medical imaging models should not blindly trust model predictions but rather use them to identify areas in an image that may have gone unnoticed. Explainability tools (i.e., XAI) should be used on a regular basis, especially when the reasoning for a model's prediction is not immediately evident to the user. These tools can help highlight the reasons why the model made its decision and can thus uncover attacks due to contrary evidence. In CHAMELEON, we provide XAI tools to not only help the user gain trust in their model but also identify these potential attacks.

CHAIMELEON Contributions

The three stages are covered in CHAMELEON: (1) we perform a process similar to digital signatures where the hash of uploaded data is stored and monitored to detect the moment the media is tampered. We also offer users to scan their data for synthetic (deepfake) content. (2) Users have credentials and operate in isolated environments. Moreover, interactions with model files are logged and can be audited. (3) In CHAMELEON, we provide XAI tools to not only help the user gain trust in their model but also identify these potential attacks.

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6.13 GD13 Data Protection and Data Privacy

Guideline	GD13 Data Protection & Privacy
Definition	Capacity to ensure compliance with data protection rules in AI systems, including the development of good practices in compliance with GDPR principles
Description	
<p>Implementing AI systems in compliance with data protection rules requires the development of appropriate good practices while developing or deploying technologies to ensure compliance with data protection and privacy policies.</p> <p>In the development of health-related research tasks as well as in AI research, a serious mistake with fatal consequences is often made believing that developers will be able to comply with the law on their own. The application of the risk-based approach and the data protection by design methodology of the GDPR requires the training of all personnel. This means that researchers and developers must be familiar with the applicable principles from an ethical and legal point of view. But this is clearly insufficient if an expert legal team does not support development in all its phases (pre-design, requirements, design, programming, testing, release and life of the product)[1].</p> <p>The above values also apply in the field of artificial intelligence. Article 4 of the AI Act on AI literacy emphasises the need to ensure that every user, depending on the role they play in an AI-based information system, should receive adequate training to understand the state of the art. This includes legal and ethical aspects.</p> <p>Good Practices to ensure Data Protection & Privacy compliance.</p> <p>In the context of the EU, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is a comprehensive data protection framework that sets guidelines for the collection, processing and storage of personal data within the European Union. In the specific case of medical imaging AI systems, GDPR compliance is critical due to the sensitive nature of the health data used to develop the AI algorithms. [2] As with other EU projects that manage large amounts of personal data, AI developers should consider comply with various legal requirements stated in GDPR, IA Act and other relevant laws. As basic principles we can mentioned the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lawfulness, fairness and transparency. The AI developer must ensure that the data collected for the purpose of developing the medical imaging AI system have a legal base to be used. 	

- **Data minimization:** The AI developer must only collect the data that is necessary for its function. This means avoiding the collection of excessive or irrelevant data.
 - **Data subject rights:** During the implementation of the project, the AI developer must ensure that all patients or data subjects have the right to access their data, request corrections and request deletion (the right to be forgotten).
 - **Accuracy:** This principle is related not only to data quality in the GDPR, but also to the data governance requirement in the AI Act. Data quality in all its dimensions (cataloguing, curation, validation, etc.) and ensuring its variety and diversity of data are essential to guarantee the explainability of outputs and the exclusion of the risk of bias.
 - **Storage limitation:** The data retention period is a very complex issue. In development we must be able to define this period, which will be different in the prototyping phase and during the system's life cycle. It will also depend on the need to define whether it is necessary to retain a set of data in order to be able to reproduce the functioning of the AI in the event of incidents or misfunctions.
 - **Security:** The GDPR understands security as confidentiality, integrity and resilience. Article 32 requires the adoption of a security framework based on an adequate risk analysis. AI Act coherently integrates robustness and reliability as crucial elements. This implies that an additional layer of risk analysis focused on the specific risks for AI must be added.
 - **Accountability:** This principle implies an essential philosophy. It is necessary to implement means for compliance and liability is understood as proven accountability. This is consistent with the documentation duties provided for high-risk systems in the Ai Act and detailed in its Annex IV
- In addition, it is also recommended that the AI developer implements other compliance best practices that can facilitate the regulations and directives contained in this EU AIA.
- **Risk management:** Implementing robust risk management systems to identify, assess, and mitigate potential risks throughout the entire lifecycle of the AI system.
 - **Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs):** Conducting regular DPIAs to assess the impact of data processing activities on privacy and implementing measures to mitigate identified risks.
 - **Fundamental Rights Impact Assessments.** Risks to the fundamental rights of the AI and the measures adopted should be documented. This task can be part of the DPIA.
 - **Human oversight:** Ensuring that AI systems operate under human oversight, particularly in critical healthcare scenarios.

CHAIMELEON Contributions

The main objective of the CHAIMELEON project is to establish a large structured repository of health imaging data as an open source for artificial intelligence (AI) experiments in cancer management. During the development of the CHAIMELEON project and taking into consideration the nature and the sensitivity of the ehealth data incorporated to the CHAIMELEON repository, the consortium implemented legal and ethical frameworks as well as several good practices to handle health data in accordance with GDPR. In parallel, researchers participating in the CHAIMELEON project also developed specific tools to ensure data protection and privacy.

CHAIMELEON contributions to Good Practices ensuring Data Protection & Privacy

For the implementation of the CHAIMELEON repository the CHAIMELEON project implemented several good practices to ensure compliance of the ICT tools with fundamental ethical principles is integral to any research

activities funded by the European Union (EU). This was carried out during an “ Ethics Appraisal procedure” included in WP 1 to ensure compliance with the ethical principles governing biomedical research over the first phase of the project, which is aimed at obtaining the images.

In parallel, the legal experts participating in the CHAIMELEON project also conducted several actions during the execution of WP2 to guarantee GDPR compliance of the CHAIMELEON repository. This work included the development of practical recommendations for drafting:

- Informed consent procedures
- Ethics impact Assessments on AI tools
- Verification of the GDPR compliance status: including specific documents that can inspire other projects like trustworthiness evidence forms, data processor agreement forms, joint controllership Agreement forms, risks analysis forms and other.

Additionally, legal reports and risk analyses were developed and incorporated into the Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA), which led to the CHAIMELEON Re-identification Challenge. Considering the need for technical validation of the de-identification processes applied to medical imaging data, the Re-identification Challenge has been carried out in the context of CHAIMELEON.

Furthermore, data sharing agreements and data transfer agreements were developed and reviewed by the European Data Protection Supervisor. Those agreements were used during the project to either share or transfer information in compliance with the GDPR regulation. The project also employed a Data Protection by Design approach, for which specific training sessions were conducted, and continuous interactions were held regarding GDPR compliance with the Data Protection Officers (DPOs) of the institutions participating in CHAMELEON.

Finally, the project addressed GDPR compliance challenges stemming from the lack of homogeneity in the regulatory frameworks across EU member states, highlighting the need for harmonised data protection practices in cross-border research initiatives. The compliance was according to regulations approved during the lifetime of the project, like the IA Act, the Data Governance Act, and the proposal of the European Health Data Space.

The work done was included in several WP1 and WP2 deliverables that can serve as a source of inspiration for AI developers to ensure good practices during the development of their AI medical imaging systems

CHAIMELEON technological developments ensuring Data Protection & Privacy

In parallel to the development of good practices for GDPR compliance, the AI experts of the CHAMELEON consortium also developed tools to ensure and enhance Data protection and privacy. In CHAMELEON, we provide tools for data harmonization that enables users to augment their data to remove confidential features prior to model training. Data extraction attacks can also require a significant number of queries to extract a single image, so query limits are recommended as well.

In CHAMELEON, only trusted (vetted) and authenticated users are allowed to access the training environment. Moreover, personal identifiers are removed from all data imported into the repository to help mitigate this issue

CHAIMELEON Re-identification Challenge

Data de-identification is a key topic in all AI4HI projects, as it is fundamental for complying with legal and ethical frameworks such as the GDPR. While it is crucial for protecting the privacy of individuals, there is a lack of concrete technical (applied and validated) information to ensure the effectiveness of these methods. In particular, regulations provide no technical information on how to properly de-identify medical imaging metadata and there is not any standard de-identification method that ensures patient identity is no longer recognizable based, either directly or indirectly, on their attributes. In conclusion, there is no “official” mechanism even though organizations like NEMA propose different rules, referred to as de-

identification profiles, for DICOM attributes de-identification. Some of the guidelines and regulations consulted in this regard include the GDPR, NEMA PS3.15 Chapter E, the Anonymization of personal data guide from The Voice of German Industry (BDI), the Basic anonymization guide from the Personal Data Protection Commission Singapore (PDPC) and the guide Adoption of pseudonymization techniques: The case of the healthcare sector from the European Union Agency For Cybersecurity (ENISA).

Considering the need for technical validation of the de-identification processes applied to medical imaging data, the Re-identification Challenge has been carried out in the context of CHAIMELEON. This exercise serves as a technical audit to assess the robustness of DICOM image de-identification methods utilized in practice, particularly in some European AI4HI projects. As regulators only provide guidance on how information should be de-identified without specifying the technical framework required to achieve this, the Challenge serves as a tool to practically assess the robustness of these de-identification profiles.

The Re-identification Challenge consisted of a single phase in which the selected 68 participants were tasked to re-identify 38 pseudonymized DICOM studies from multiple European hospitals (including Spain, Portugal and Italy), modalities and anatomical regions. Despite 74% of the participants delivered result, none succeeded in tracing back the identity of the patients. Based on participants' reports of their attempts, some minor vulnerabilities were discovered that allowed them to narrow the population by obtaining their geographical region.

This Challenge is a groundbreaking initiative that may pave the way for robust evaluations of de-identification methods and may culminate in the standardization of de-identification profiles in the field of radiological imaging.

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6.14 GD14 Traceability

Guideline	GD14 Traceability
Definition	Capacity of the AI system to track who are the users handling the data and under what circumstances they are processing the data and to document the decisions made by the AI system during its operations and any changes or modifications.
Description	
<p>Data traceability is the process of tracking the data's transformations and uses, including any action performed since its creation to their usage. Traceability is key for data holders to understand the relevance of the data shared, data users to properly reference them and consumers of output products such as AI models to understand the foundations of the evidence used to build such a product.</p> <p>The focus on traceability ensures accountability, which is vital for building trust among stakeholders in the data economy. Organizations involved in data sharing under the Data Governance Act must implement robust logging, monitoring, and reporting mechanisms to comply with traceability requirements. Data traceability should be non-repudiable (users cannot deny the veracity of the information introduced) and integral (unauthorised modifications can be detected) and should contain enough information for data holders and data users. Traceability is a key feature for the certification of software as a medical device. The traceability framework aligns with other EU regulations, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the Digital Services Act, creating a comprehensive legal environment for data governance.</p>	
CHAIMELEON Contributions	
<p>CHAIMELEON developed a custom solution to trace the actions of the platform's users called Tracer. It incorporates various standards in different areas such as the development framework (SpringBoot), data storage (Ethereum), the communication interface (REST), and user authentication and authorization (OIDC). Starting with the first aspect of the traceability solution, the actual development, Tracer is a web service written in Java, one of the most widely used programming languages today. Java is mature, with its features like syntax and standard library with compatibility that are preserved across versions. The ecosystem is one of the biggest in existence after so many years of the language being used to develop different types of applications (desktop, server, mobile)</p>	

Because of the language wide adoption, frameworks were born to bring together the best practices and to solve common problems. One of them, which became a standard in web development in Javaworld, is SpringBoot, which itself is based on the older, widely used Spring [1]. We selected the former instead of the latter, because it can speed up development by removing bloat and coming with sensible default settings resulting from many years of use by the industry and academia alike, both in production and research. By using SpringBoot we leveraged the hard work of thousands of brilliant engineers, software architects, QA people, and others. Employing SpringBoot not only reduced the development time by solving many of the problems one can encounter when developing a web service but increased the security of our own code. Security is extremely important for Tracer, since it deals with the actual history of user actions executed on a platform with real patient data. Related to the framework we used is the architectural style of the communication interface. We chose the Representational State Transfer (REST) protocol [2] which keeps things clear, simple, and flexible. It's also 100% platform independent and language agnostic (one can use Java, Javascript, Typescript, Go C++ and many others). We followed the standard recommended by many tech giants such as IBM, Google, and Microsoft to keep our solution compliant as much as possible. For instance, we took advantage of the HTTP verbs like GET and POST to distinguish between operations pointing to the same endpoint (e.g. when invoking `/api/traces`, the former loads a list of traces, while the latter adds a new trace). Another important aspect of REST is the returned code after a call. Tracer utilizes the standard codes such as 200 when sending data after a successful execution or 401 to signal that the user is not authorized to execute an operation. All the interactions with our solution are stateless, meaning that there is no actual session kept active by the web server. The operation is validated and executed when received by the server side. Part of the REST standard is the format of the data communication. We selected JSON instead of XML for its brevity which translates into less bandwidth consumption and faster performance when parsing and encoding the data passed between the client and the web service. Last but not least, the resources are identified by specific URIs, e.g. to get all traces one would call `/api/traces`, while the path to get a specific trace with id 100 is `/api/traces/100`. The next standard we used on our platform is the well-known blockchain Ethereum protocol [3]. To protect the tracing data against tampering, we decided to go with the blockchain technology which has one of the foundational properties: the immutability of data. Once something is added, it cannot be removed and/or modified which is basically what a trace

should be (since an executed action cannot be undone directly, only through another action that undoes the result, with this second action being a new and different action by itself).

The Ethereum protocol has become a standard in its own right, since it's not just about cryptocurrencies, you can actually create applications (called contracts) that are executed on the blockchain. We created our implementation of a contract that deals with the traces stored on the blockchain. Tracer stores and retrieves the traces directly from our own private Ethereum network that runs on our Kubernetes platform along with the other services.

This network is not connected to the outside world and has nothing to do with the well-known standard public Ethereum. We deployed Hyperledger Besu which implements the full protocol but was designed to run as small-scale deployments and private networks. Last but not least we took advantage of the OpenID Connect (OIDC) standard [4] to authenticate and authorize the users that access Tracer via the REST API using tokens. We took advantage of the builtin support in the SpringBoot framework.

The actual user information and the validation of the token data is handled externally, by Keycloak (in our case) - the widely deployed open-source identity and access management solution. By using OIDC, we allow access to users that don't have an account on our platform using third party providers such as Google, EGI, and Microsoft. Since security is very important to us, we selected OIDC along with its ecosystem of applications and libraries, instead of a simpler protocol like username and password or application-based token authentication (where the tokens are handled by each application). Another important advantage of OIDC is the seamless integration of multiple applications that adhere to this standard. Since the actual user handling is not done by each application, one can log in on our Dataset Explorer and with the same token can use Tracer, Guacamole (to connect to his/her remote desktop instance), or KubeApps (to manage the deployments on our platform). It is 100% transparent to the user, the tokens are passed around and refreshed behind the scene. The user can continue his or her work without interruption.

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6.15 GD15 Explainability

Guideline	GD15 Explainability
Definition	<p>Explainability in the context of AI medical imaging refers to the ability to make transparent the reasoning and decision-making processes of an AI model. In other words, an explainable AI system should provide outputs that humans, particularly clinicians, can interpret in a meaningful way to understand how specific diagnostic or treatment-related conclusions were reached. Explainability fosters trust among end-users, aligns with regulatory and ethical requirements, and promotes safer clinical adoption.</p>
Description	
<p>Explainability is critical for AI systems in healthcare because diagnostic and treatment decisions carry high risks for patient outcomes. Clinicians and patients need confidence that model outputs are a result of clinically relevant features rather than artifacts or spurious correlations. This requirement is supported by regulatory frameworks such as the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which mandates transparency and accountability in automated decision-making [1].</p> <p>Explainability methods can be broadly categorized into interpretability by design, which incorporates explainability into the model development process, and post-hoc explainability, which focuses on understanding and analysing the model's behaviour after it has been trained. A review paper by Salahuddin et. al [2] highlights the strengths and limitations of various interpretability methods, showcasing a range of approaches with differing levels of sophistication, such as Concept Learning Models, Counterfactual Explanations, and Attribution Maps. For instance, attribution maps visually highlight critical regions in the input image but may not explain how these regions contribute to predictions, while concept learning models focus on high-level clinical features but require extensive annotations and can suffer from information leakage. The diversity in interpretability methods underscores the need to carefully evaluate their suitability for specific clinical applications. The selection of a method should involve a nuanced understanding of its capabilities and limitations, guided by input from clinicians and domain experts. By engaging end-users throughout the development process, developers can align the chosen methods with clinical workflows, ensuring they provide meaningful, actionable insights while avoiding common pitfalls like introducing biases or misleading conclusions. This collaborative approach ensures that AI</p>	

systems meet the demands of high-stakes healthcare environments, fostering transparency and trustworthiness.

As the explainability methods become increasingly complex, the risk of misleading or incomplete explanations also rises. To address this, sanity checks (e.g., randomization tests, expert review) are crucial to validate that an AI model's reasoning aligns with meaningful clinical features rather than coincidental patterns [3]. The System Causability Scale (SCS) offers a structured way to assess whether interpretability methods in the medical domain genuinely benefit end-users and assess its usability [4].

Attribution maps or heat maps are the most commonly used explainability method for getting insight into the complex decision-making process of deep learning models. In one example, Sayres et al. [5] studied Diabetic Retinopathy (DR) grading using Integrated Gradients-based heatmaps. Although helpful in some cases, these heatmaps led to over-diagnosis of DR in normal patients, demonstrating how interpretability tools may introduce biases or false positives. Therefore, application-grounded evaluations conducted with medical experts help gauge if the explanations genuinely address clinicians' needs and if they introduce new biases.

By combining robust interpretability methods, validation protocols, and collaboration with clinicians, explainable AI can ensure both technical reliability and practical usability in high-stakes healthcare applications. To achieve this, several actions can be taken:

- Adopt Sanity Checks: Use randomization tests, occlusion-based methods, and expert reviews to ensure explanations correlate with clinical features.
- Collaborate with Clinical Experts: Involve radiologists, pathologists, and other specialists to co-develop and validate explanation methods.
- Utilize Multiple Techniques: Combine global and local interpretability methods (e.g., saliency maps and feature importance rankings) for a comprehensive view.
- Establish Validation Protocols: Systematically compare explanations to ground-truth annotations or known biomarkers to verify their relevance and reliability.
- This guideline on explainability serves to enhance transparency and trust, ultimately facilitating the clinical adoption of AI systems in healthcare.

CHAIMELEON Contributions

In the CHAIMELEON project, Deliverable 7.4, Approaches to AI Explainability, addresses these needs by reviewing a range of interpretability methods tailored for medical imaging. This deliverable, based on "Transparency of Deep Neural Networks for Medical Image

Analysis: A Review of Interpretability Methods," classifies nine different approaches for understanding deep learning (DL) models' decisions in medical imaging applications [2]. This review paper highlights the strengths and limitations of all the different categories of explainability methods and offers a structured overview to guide the selection of an appropriate explainability method. However, the deliverable also highlights the limitations of post-hoc interpretability techniques, as they only approximate true model behaviour and may compromise the integrity of explanations. This underscores the importance of evaluating these methods rigorously before clinical application to prevent misunderstandings that could affect patient care.

In addition, CHAIMELEON's contributions include practical implementations of explainability tools, such as Shapley Additive Explanations (SHAP) for handcrafted radiomics, which have been integrated into the CHAIMELEON repository. This SHAP-based framework provides clinicians with local and global insights into model outputs, enhancing transparency in diagnostic and predictive tasks. We also explored attribution maps and counterfactual explanations across various use cases, offering practical tools for understanding AI models in clinical contexts. A method leveraging self-supervised learning approaches, specifically Generative Adversarial Networks, was developed to generate counterfactual explanations for a model developed for prostate risk stratification using the CHAIMELEON prostate datasets. Through these contributions, CHAIMELEON helps in taking a step towards explainable AI.

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6.16 GD16 Fairness

Guideline	GD16 Fairness
Definition	Ensuring fairness in AI medical imaging systems involves addressing biases in datasets, developing fairness metrics, and implementing fairness-oriented algorithms. Guideline 16 addresses main challenges at EU level to respond to fairness during the development of AI systems and some practical tools and procedures to overcome these challenges.
Description	
<p>Fairness in AI Medical Imaging Systems. The development of AI systems in medical imaging requires a strong focus on fairness to ensure inclusion and diversity throughout the entire lifecycle of the medical imaging AI system. Fairness is crucial when developing solutions that involve human data processing. Patients evaluated by these systems are entitled to equal rights and should be treated impartially, regardless of race, age, gender, language, nationality, or birth. Addressing fairness in AI models, training datasets, and result visualization is critical to ensuring these systems can be relied upon for decision-making. Ensuring fairness in AI medical imaging systems is particularly challenging within the diverse and multifaceted European Union population. In this context, the work done by the FUTURE-AI initiative is highly recommended. This initiative provides a comprehensive set of guiding principles and best practices for developing trustworthy AI systems in medical imaging. The FUTURE-AI initiative focuses on establishing principles to address not only fairness but also other aspects that could affect certain populations and vulnerable subgroups, such as universality, traceability, usability, robustness, and explainability of the AI system. The FUTURE-AI initiative emphasizes principles and recommendations designed to ensure that AI systems are developed and deployed under fair conditions. It also helps identify some of the challenges that AI developers should address to comply with minimum fairness objectives. Some of the current challenges include: (1) Frequently, AI developers use datasets to learn and make predictions that may not adequately represent the diversity of the EU population, which includes a wide range of ethnicities, ages, genders, and socioeconomic backgrounds. For instance, certain minority groups may be underrepresented in medical imaging datasets, leading to biased models that perform poorly for these groups. (2) Different investments in health infrastructures across member states can directly impact imaging equipment and protocols across different regions and healthcare facilities, causing inconsistencies in the data and the medical imaging AI system in use.</p>	

These inconsistencies can cause failures in AI systems deployed across Europe, resulting in errors that can have dramatic consequences in disease diagnostics or progression.⁽³⁾ Developing fairness metrics to ensure that AI developers develop and execute their AI systems correctly is another challenge. For the selection of fairness metrics, AI developers should work in collaboration with clinical teams, selecting appropriate fairness metrics and ensuring they are applied consistently in the disease context and the rationale of the AI project. Common fairness metrics include: (a) Demographic Parity: Ensuring that the medical imaging AI system's predictions are independent of protected attributes such as race or gender. This means that the proportion of positive outcomes should be the same across different demographic groups. (b) Equal Opportunity: Ensuring that individuals from different demographic groups have equal chances of receiving a positive outcome, given that they qualify for it. This criterion focuses on the true positive rate across groups (c) Equalized Odds: Ensuring that the medical imaging AI system has equal true positive rates and false positive rates across different demographic groups. In the context of more fair medical imaging AI systems, the CHAIMELEON sandbox proposes two activities to address some of the aforementioned challenges. Firstly, Guideline 16 insists on the need to ensure that the medical imaging AI system is trained on datasets that are diverse and representative of the target population. For AI developers operating in the European Union, this task involves collecting data from a wide range of sources and ensuring that all relevant sub-groups are adequately represented. Additionally, data augmentation techniques can be used to artificially increase the diversity of the training data. An additional approach can include federated learning techniques to enhance data augmentation and data diversity, using own computing resources and a network federation of nodes with data stored on local servers to collectively train an AI system on a large and highly diverse dataset. This R&D activity is one of the key objectives of EUCAIM, a large impact ongoing EU project. A complementary activity involves the development and implementation of fairness-oriented algorithms. These algorithms are designed to mitigate biases during the training process and ensure that the resulting models perform equitably across different sub-groups. Some of the most frequent techniques include the development of AI models for re-weighting [2], re-sampling [3] and adversarial debiasing [4] to reduce bias during the development of the AI medical imaging AI system. There are other examples of fairness-aware algorithms to achieve fairness in AI systems.

CHAIMELEON Contributions

As mentioned throughout this document, the CHAIMELEON project worked on developing a structured repository of health images and related clinical data on the most prevalent cancers in Europe (lung, breast, prostate, and colorectal) to facilitate and contribute to the development and validation of AI systems for improved cancer management. The repository contains imaging and clinical data collected for over 4,000 patients, thanks to the contribution of nine hospitals that act as data providers: Fundación para la Investigación del Hospital Universitario la Fe de la Comunidad Valenciana (ES), Università di Pisa (IT), Università degli Studi di Roma la Sapienza (IT), Centro Hospitalar Universitário de Santo António (PT), Policlinico San Donato (IT), Collège des Enseignants de Radiologie (FR), Universiteit Maastricht (NL), and Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin (DE). The contribution of different hospitals with patient data from a highly diverse number of patients dispersed across six member states reinforces the commitment of CHAIMELEON.

Additionally, the CHAIMELEON team worked on developing fairness-oriented algorithms. Specifically, CHAIMELEON AI developers worked on image harmonization approaches to reduce inconsistency and variation in a large repository like CHAIMELEON, which has been fed multicentric datasets with imaging studies acquired through various equipment and methodologies. Although the primary goal of these algorithms was to enhance the reliability and resilience of the CHAIMELEON datasets, they also contributed to enhancing fairness through data harmonization techniques applied to imaging studies from different healthcare facilities and medical imaging equipment. Particularly within the framework of this project, CHAIMELEON researchers worked on developing plain CNN-based computational approaches (U-Net, Auto-Encoder, etc.) and generative-based approaches (WGAN, CycleGAN, LDM).

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6.17 GD17 Interoperability

Guideline	GD17 Interoperability
Definition	The importance of interoperability for the development of medical imaging AI systems
Description	
<p>Interoperability refers to the basic ability of computerized systems to connect and communicate one to another, even if they were developed by different manufacturers in different industries with different ways of interpreting and storing data. In health, interoperability refers to the capability of heterogeneous computer and software systems to exchange and share data from a range of vital sources, including laboratories, clinics, pharmacies, hospitals, and medical practices. Particularly in the context of health imaging and the application of artificial intelligence, we need to consider the ability of systems to exchange and interpret not only medical images, but also the related clinical and administrative information associated with the medical imaging study.</p> <p>To develop a highly interoperable AI health system, we need to analyse, at a minimum, the standards used to exchange information, the data model used to integrate information from different organisations' information models and terminologies, and the ability of the AI health system to provide services, to accept services from other systems available in the healthcare organisation's IT infrastructure, and ultimately to enable them to work together effectively, which is known as service interoperability.</p> <p>1) Interoperability Standards: There are several standards and initiatives that collectively enhance the interoperability of healthcare systems, ensure seamless communication and data exchange, and facilitate the development and implementation of artificial intelligence. Messaging standards in healthcare aim to normalize and standardize communication between Health Information Systems (HIS). HL7 (Health Level Seven) is a widely adopted messaging standard that facilitates integration between heterogeneous HIS. These standards are event-based, meaning that when an event occurs in a source system, it sends a message to destination systems that need the information. HL7's primary standards, HL7 v2 and HL7 v3, are the most implemented, with HL7 v2 being widely used but becoming outdated, and HL7 v3 being robust but difficult to implement.</p> <p>FHIR (Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources) is a newer standard developed by HL7, combining features of existing HL7 standards with modern web standards like XML, JSON, and HTTP. FHIR is designed to be easy to use and implement, addressing limitations of</p>	

previous standards. It supports HL7 and can be integrated into existing solutions, aiming for semantic robustness and electronic validation of data elements.

SNOMED CT is a comprehensive, multilingual clinical healthcare terminology maintained by SNOMED International. It provides codes, terms, synonyms, and definitions for clinical documentation and reporting, supporting effective clinical data recording and improving patient care. SNOMED CT covers a wide range of medical concepts and is essential for interoperable Electronic Health Records (EHR), enabling consistent indexing, storage, retrieval, and aggregation of clinical data.

IHE (Integrating the Healthcare Enterprise) is another important initiative, a non-profit organization that improves information sharing among computer systems in healthcare. IHE develops technical guidelines based on available standards, facilitating interoperability across different systems and vendors.

DICOM standard (DICOM stands for Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine). It is the widely adopted standard for visualising and sharing medical images and associated information (DICOM has become the most popular standard in medicine). Initially, DICOM was used to communicate image data between different systems. Recent developments in standardisation are enabling more and more DICOM-based services for the integration of modalities and information systems (e.g. RIS, PACS). In clinical practice, a medical image is a DICOM file that contains a header in addition to the actual image. All the information stored in the header is catalogued in groups of elements called "DICOM tags". Real-world entities (e.g., images, procedures, or interpretation reports) are represented in the DICOM semantic data model by templates of attributes or data elements, and each tag identifies an attribute. This is important for the development of AI systems applied to medical imaging. The DICOM standard enables the management of image-related information generated after image acquisition, particularly by radiologists reading exams, which is essential for capturing contextual information and enriching data. In addition to DICOM images, DICOM provides standardisation for many other types of data, such as imaging reports, measurements, annotations and segmentations.

2) In terms of information data models, several information data models are widely used to standardise and streamline the management and exchange of health data.

FHIR: While primarily a standard, FHIR also serves as a data model by defining how healthcare information can be exchanged between different systems. It uses modern web technologies like XML, JSON, and HTTP, making it easy to implement and integrate with

existing systems. FHIR supports a wide range of healthcare data, including clinical, administrative, and financial information.

OMOP (Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership) Common Data Model (CDM): OMOP CDM standardizes the structure and content of observational data to enable efficient analyses. It captures clinical information such as patient encounters, diagnoses, drugs, and procedures using standardized vocabulary terms. This model allows for networked studies without sharing sensitive data, as queries can be run on multiple sites and results shared

OSIRIS: A popular data model for data sharing and Interoperability in Oncology. Similar to the OMOP oncology extension, the OSIRIS model is an event-based temporal data model also based on international ontologies and terminologies such as SNOMED CT, FHIR, UMLS, ICD-10, ICD-O-3, ATC, the UICC TNM classification of malignant tumours, etc.

MIABIS (Minimum Information About Biobank data Sharing) data model is oriented to the integration of medical imaging studies and related omics data. MIABIS is designed to standardize the description of biobank data, which includes biological samples and associated data such as clinical, genomic, and imaging information. This model facilitates the sharing and integration of data across different biobanks and research institutions, enhancing interoperability and enabling comprehensive multi-omics analyses.

3) Service Interoperability is a third interoperability layer. It is essential to ensure that different systems, platforms and datasets related to the Artificial Intelligence application can work together efficiently.

Service Interoperability.

Service-oriented architectures are mostly used in distributed environments. The popular paradigm of microservices, in which every functional part of an application is implemented through small, individual, independently deployable services which communicate among them by means of well-defined API. Typically, APIs are implemented using REST (Representational State Transfer) architecture, relying on stateless communication using standard HTTP or HTTPS methods, which enable them to communicate even over the web. In this case, applications comprise an API gateway that sits on the edge of a system or network of microservices and serves as the entry point into the system, providing routing and load balancing, protocol translation and Transformation and caching.

The use of common data formats and communication protocols reduce the complexity of service interoperability. However, one important advance in the deployment of multi-service interoperable platforms has been the container-based environments. By using containers, application run on their preferred environments, reducing the configuration burden that

implies deploying multiple services on the same resource. Kubernetes provides an efficient environment to deploy multiple applications as services, even with requirements that are incompatible among them, and homogenise ports, endpoints, security mechanisms or storage solutions. This has been the approach followed in CHAIMELEON to jointly deploy databases, processing services, storage backends, image processing environments and security solutions.

Interoperability challenges for the development of AI systems.

It is clear that none of the existing data models and health data standards cover all the needs for developing AI imaging systems. We have already discussed the advantages of some standards and data models, but with the information researched so far, it seems that a combination of several models and standards will be required. For example, while DICOM is a consistent and popular standard with a high capacity to define transactions and ensure that any DICOM object can be read in a standard way, it has certain limitations in the development of AI algorithms (limitations for series annotation for automatic segmentation; for image registration; for automatic execution of image analysis algorithms or for traceability of the number and type of studies and series available on a health IT platform/health repository). Similarly, there is no single data model that covers all the needs for the development of medical imaging AI systems. While OMOP and OSIRIS largely cover the needs for clinical data collection and harmonisation, much work is still needed on data models that include medical imaging to ensure reproducibility in image acquisition and interpretation. If we want to include genomic data in our AI system, the MIABIS data model should also be considered. When defining the interoperability strategy, there are other aspects such as security and privacy issues, the scalability and flexibility of the system to handle large and diverse amounts of data, the existing IT infrastructure and equipment that will interact with the AI system, and even organisational issues such as the interoperability strategy of the organisation developing or deploying the system and the skills and knowledge of the IT staff to implement the interoperability strategy.

The main challenges on the service interoperability are related to the semantic representation of the services, which could facilitate the automatic matching of services, reducing human intervention, enforcing authorisation policies across services (authentication issues are well addressed by the use of standard protocols), cross-domain integration (somehow related to the semantics, which will be crucial to integrate services from other disciplines), fault tolerance, to isolate and propagate adequately the errors, and

performance. All these challenges and issues have been addressed during the implementation of the CHAIMELEON platform. The main conclusions are presented below.

CHAIMELEON Contributions

(1) Services Interoperability: We strived to build our IT part of the CHAIMELEON platform on as many standards as possible. Using a standard has many advantages like its wide adoption, clearly defined specifications, and interoperability of applications that follow the said standard. The very core of the platform, Kubernetes [1], has become a standard when it comes to open source, free container orchestration systems. It defines general concepts meant to solve issues like how to launch a job with a predefined life, or a service that is supposed to run continuously. This is no small feat since it allows the applications to be exposed in a standardized way (with all the proprietary/specific tasks behind a unified interface) using containers. The majority of the web services that run on the CHAIMELEON's Kubernetes cluster use Representational State Transfer (REST) protocol [2] to communicate between each other. REST is a standard by itself and widely used along with SOAP and GraphQL among others. Another standard employed on our platform is the OpenID Connect (OIDC) standard [3] to authenticate and authorize the users. This allows seamless use of the applications on our platform. Suppose a user wants to see a list of non-public datasets. (S)he can login on our Dataset Explorer web application using the browser and then access all other based applications without the need to login again using the same browser. (2) Data interoperability: (1) Services Interoperability: We strived to build our IT part of the CHAIMELEON platform on as many standards as possible. Using a standard has many advantages like its wide adoption, clearly defined specifications, and interoperability of applications that follow the said standard. The very core of the platform, Kubernetes [Kubernetes2024], has become a standard when it comes to open source, free container orchestration systems. It defines general concepts meant to solve issues like how to launch a job with a predefined life, or a service that is supposed to run continuously. This is no small feat since it allows the applications to be exposed in a standardized way (with all the proprietary/specific tasks behind a unified interface) using containers. The majority of the web services that run on the CHAIMELEON's Kubernetes cluster use Representational State Transfer (REST) protocol [Fielding2000] to communicate between each other. REST is a standard by itself and widely used along with SOAP and GraphQL among others. Another standard employed on our platform is the OpenID Connect (OIDC) standard [OpenId2013] to authenticate and authorize the users. This allows seamless use of the applications on our platform. Suppose a user wants to see a list of non-public datasets. (S)he

can login on our Dataset Explorer web application using the browser and then access all other based applications without the need to login again using the same browser. (2) Data interoperability: One of our key achievements within the project has been the creation of a robust anonymization pipeline specifically designed for medical images and clinical data. This pipeline is crucial for ensuring patient privacy and data protection while enabling data sharing for research and clinical purposes. The anonymisation pipeline relies on a two-step de-identification process, using a secured hashing method (sha256) and date scrambling function, applied to both images and clinical data. The imaging de-identification is derived from the DICOM standard, keeping only the non-sensitive information deemed relevant for data processing. To assess the effectiveness of the anonymization process, we also developed a re-identification challenge on medical images along with other AI4HI projects. This challenge aims to test the robustness of the pipeline against potential reidentification threats. We anticipate the results of this challenge by the end of this year, and a comprehensive scientific paper detailing the methodology and results will be published to contribute to the broader scientific community. Also, we originally planned to use the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) Common Data Model (CDM) as the standard framework for data integration across the project. However, it appeared that applying OMOP CDM to real world data was not entirely feasible, due to the complexity and completeness of the collected data. Because OMOP CDM did not apply well to routine clinical data in general, and the data we had in particular, we pivoted to developing an OMOP-based customized data model tailored to our specific needs. This model includes all variables clinically relevant to the project, and their correspondence to OMOP CDM whenever applicable. This model effectively incorporates both oncology and radiology data, addressing unique aspects of these domains to facilitate more accurate and meaningful data exchange and analysis. Our customized data model enhances interoperability by ensuring that critical clinical and imaging data can be integrated, accessed, and utilized effectively by various stakeholders, while also meeting the specific requirements of our project. To improve data reuse and re-interpretability, we have also been working on improving the QC (Quality Control) of data supplied to the central CHAIMELEON platform. A recurring problem with RWDs is the curation and standardization of data between several hospitals of different nationalities. Several functions have been developed in that sense: (a) comparison of the input data against the data model; checking the data type and automatic correction when applicable; checking that data from drop-down menus contains eligible values; checking that input data fields exists in data model (b) controlled injection of clinical data in eCRF; option

to overwrite existing data, clear existing 1-to-many fields (c) QC can be applied retrospectively on existing data or on new data before injection (d) data that passed QC can be stored before the eCRF is created, to be automatically imported later on, once the patient is created.

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6.18 GD18 Green AI

Guideline	GD18 Green AI
Definition	AI development techniques focused on reducing energy consumption and carbon footprint.
Description	
<p>Green AI is an emerging paradigm that aims to respond to and integrate the criteria of environmental responsibility and sustainability in AI systems. This paradigm recognises global efforts towards sustainability and integrates both the classical quality metrics of algorithms, precision and speed, as well as metrics related to the ecological footprint. In the recent years we have seen some advancements in regulating AI’s growing environmental impact—with the Artificial Intelligence Impacts Act of 2024, S.3732, 118 Cong. (2024) in the US [1], calling for empirical studies to produce standards for measuring the full range of environmental impacts of AI, and the EU AIA (2024) calling for a standardisation process for determining the environmental impacts of AI. Specifically, Articles 4 and 12 of the EU AIA mention the need for greener AI systems with logging capabilities to record energy consumption and measure or calculate resource use. Vendors should also assess the environmental impact throughout the life cycle of their AI systems. In addition, the EUA AIA calls for new documentation and processes to improve the resource performance of AI systems, including standards for reducing energy and other resource consumption during the life cycle of high-risk AI systems. There is clearly a need for comprehensive models to evaluate the impact of AI systems across its lifecycle [2]. In the context of AI applied to medical imaging, the AI system’s lifecycle involves many of the aspects already explained in this document. (1) Model Development: (a) Algorithm Selection: Different algorithms have varying computational efficiencies and energy requirements. Choosing -efficient algorithms can significantly reduce the environmental impact and the selection of the algorithm should consider software libraries, frameworks and packages as well as all the intermediate layers and connections between data inputs and algorithm outputs. (b) Training: The training phase of AI models is particularly energy intensive. Optimizing training processes and using efficient hardware can help minimize energy consumption. It is therefore important to assess the training approach, data augmentation techniques, hyperparameters or assembly techniques if applicable. (2) Data Management: data handling is especially critical for the development of environmentally low impact AI systems. The management of data involves different subtasks like (a) the analysis of data sources choosing those that require less</p>	

computational resources or lower data transfer steps, (b) data storage and all the necessary assessment to ensure efficient data storage solutions and minimizing redundant data, and (c) data processing and preprocessing steps (like data curation, data harmonization, data partition, etc). (3) Hardware requirements: There is always a hardware component behind an AI system. The rapid growth of Cloud Based solutions do not remove the need for hardware. The selection of the right type of hardware is crucial for optimizing the energy consumption and environmental impact of AI systems. The appropriate involvement of CPUs, GPUs and TPUs offer significant advantages in terms of energy efficiency and performance for AI tasks. For medical imaging AI systems, GPUs are highly recommended for on premises solutions due to their parallel processing capabilities, high throughput, and support from optimized libraries. TPUs are also an excellent choice, especially for large-scale and cloud-based applications, due to their specialized design for AI workloads and superior efficiency. Both types of hardware can significantly enhance the performance and efficiency of medical imaging AI systems. However, a debate arises that calls for evaluating the performance gained with deep learning models that have a large carbon footprint versus simple ML models such as a Random Forest. These simple models can be trained on cheap CPUs with minimal environmental impact and sometimes show a performance close to deep learning models. So, is it justified to generate a high carbon footprint to gain a minimum percentage of performance in the solution? Clearly the answer is complex and depends on the context of the task and its level of TRL. It is understandable to try to maximise the performance of an AI system for automatic cancer detection that is to be clinically validated. But what about for a research model at a low TRL where you are only looking at the quality of the data? Basically, the objective is to make developers aware and analyse whether the cost of the carbon footprint for the deep learning models they are developing is justifiable for the improvement they are going to gain over classical ML models. (4) Operations of the AI system: The operational phase of the AI system should be also analysed. A successful medical imaging AI system involves continuous energy use. Some promising strategies involve the deployment of AI systems on edge devices such as hospital servers or even medical imaging devices themselves [3]. Other environmentally friendly strategies consider the deployment of AI models for medical imaging in cloud environments, using containerization (e.g., Docker) and serverless architectures to dynamically allocate resources based on demand [4]. An analysis of the bibliography has not revealed Green AI assessment models specifically oriented to medical imaging in AI systems.

CHAIMELEON Contributions

During the execution of the CHAIMELEON Project, a central repository for Medical imaging AI systems and development was created. The CHAIMELEON team therefore concentrated considerable efforts on the definition of hardware and computing requirements as well as the optimal infrastructure for the operation of a variety of AI models. In order to assess the performance of the CHAIMELEON repository, the CHAIMELEON engineers considered the use of Absolute metrics, and Relative metrics. Absolute Metrics extract absolute parameters, such as execution time or memory usage and they are relevant for time-critical operations or for resource sizing. Relative metrics involve the analysis of metrics related to the usage of resources such as velocity, speed up, scalability, etc. The following metrics have been considered and could be used to evaluate the performance of the CHAIMELEON Platform during the execution of AI algorithms by internal or external users:

(1) Absolute metrics are straightforward to compute: (a) Execution time, extracted from the job management services (b) Memory footprint, extracted from the operating system.

(2) Relative metrics involve other measurements that may not be straightforward. (a) Velocity: The velocity is the number of operations per second. The standard metric for measuring the velocity is the floating-point operations per second (FLOPS). This is the metric used to evaluate the maximum performance of supercomputers. The velocity requires obtaining the number of operations performed, which is not trivial in iterative processes such as the ones involved in the training of models (it could be more straightforward in the case of the inference). There are mechanisms in the AI libraries to retrieve the number of operations performed (e.g. the `tf.profiler` class in Tensorflow). With this information, the velocity would be the number of operations divided by the time spent. This is the standard way of measuring performance in computing. (b) Average GPU efficiency: GPU cores are idle an important fraction of the time due to the latency on accessing the data in memory. GPU efficiency (percentage of GPU usage) can be sampled along the execution time of a process, providing an indication of the average efficiency. The ideal case is to reach 100% of usage, and efficiency normally increases by increasing sample size, number of threads or other strategies. (c) Speed-up. The Speed-up is the increase (speed-down in the case of decreasing) of speed when some conditions are changed (typically, the number of processing resources). AI model training can be parallelized across several GPU units, accelerating the velocity of the algorithms. The speed-up is defined as the time spent in the standard conditions (e.g. one GPU) divided by the time spent when the number of resources changes. A linear speed-up (velocity gets reduced in the same proportion as resources are

increased) is the ideal case, expecting sub-linear speed-up in most of the cases. Super-linear speed-ups are typically caused by the increase of other resources (e.g. memory) when the number of GPUs are increased. (d) Efficiency. The efficiency relates to the actual usage of the resources. It is computed by dividing the speed-up by the number of resources increased, and gives an estimation of the overheads, idle times or other undesirable effects that affect performance. Efficiency is typically between 0 and 1, being 1 the case of the linear Speed-up (e.g. resources are used on a 100%). All these metrics can be used to assess energy consumption or carbon footprint of an external AI System executed in the CHAIMELEON Platform and over the data stored in the CHAIMELEON repository. It is necessary to develop a mathematical model similar to the recent assessment model published by Napolitano et al [5] to measure the carbon footprint of the different AI systems participating in the AI challenge launched by the CHAIMELEON project.

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